

АҢДАТПА

Бұл дипломдық жұмыс тамақ өндірісіндегі барабанды кептіру процесін автоматтандырылған басқару жүйесін әзірлеуге арналған. Жобада барабанды кептіру технологиялық процесінің толық сипаттамасы, кептіру қондырғысының математикалық моделін құру және оны талдау қарастырылған. Сонымен қатар, жүйені басқару үшін заманауи автоматтандыру құралдары мен бағдарламаланатын логикалық контроллерлер (PLC) қолдану мәселелері зерттелген. Жұмыста барабанды кептіру жүйесінің математикалық моделі жылу және масса алмасу заңдылықтары негізінде жасалған. Бұл модель процестің динамикалық сипаттамаларын зерттеуге, басқару параметрлерін оңтайландыруға және жүйенің тұрақтылығы, бақылануы мен басқарылуын MATLAB ортасында талдауға мүмкіндік береді.

Зерттеу барысында бірнеше басқару әдістері қарастырылды: PID, LQI және робастты H_∞ басқару. Нәтижелер H_∞ реттегіші ең тиімді екенін көрсетті, себебі ол орнығу уақытын азайтады, асқынуды жояды және жүйенің тұрақтылығын жоғары деңгейде қамтамасыз етеді. Ұсынылған автоматтандыру жүйесі кептіру процесінің тиімділігін арттырады, энергия шығынын азайтады және өнім сапасының тұрақтылығын қамтамасыз етеді.

ABSTRACT

This thesis is devoted to the development of an automated control system for the drum drying process in food production. The project includes a detailed description of the drum drying technological process, the development of a mathematical model of the drying system, and an analysis of its dynamic behavior. The study also considers the application of modern automation technologies and programmable logic controllers (PLCs) for effective monitoring and control of the drying process.

The mathematical model of the drum dryer is developed based on the fundamental principles of heat and mass transfer. This model enables the analysis of system dynamics, optimization of control parameters, and evaluation of system stability, controllability, and observability using MATLAB simulation tools. Several control strategies were investigated, including decentralized PID, LQI, and robust H_∞ control. The results demonstrate that the H_∞ controller provides the best overall performance, achieving minimal settling time, zero overshoot, and strong robustness against system uncertainties and multivariable interactions. The proposed automation system improves the efficiency of the drying process, reduces energy consumption, and ensures consistent product quality in industrial food production.

АННОТАЦИЯ

Данная дипломная работа посвящена разработке автоматизированной системы управления процессом барабанной сушки в пищевом производстве. В проекте представлено подробное описание технологического процесса барабанной сушки, разработка математической модели сушильной установки и её анализ. Также рассматриваются вопросы применения современных средств автоматизации и программируемых логических контроллеров (PLC). Математическая модель барабанной сушки построена на основе законов тепло- и массообмена. Она позволяет исследовать динамические характеристики системы, оптимизировать параметры управления, а также анализировать устойчивость, управляемость и наблюдаемость объекта в среде MATLAB.

В работе были рассмотрены различные методы управления, включая PID, LQI и робастное H_∞ управление. Результаты показали, что H_∞ регулятор обеспечивает наилучшие характеристики, включая минимальное время установления, отсутствие перерегулирования и высокую устойчивость к возмущениям и взаимным связям каналов. Предложенная система автоматизации повышает эффективность процесса сушки, снижает энергозатраты и обеспечивает стабильное качество готовой продукции.

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INTRODUCTION

This report presents the development and analysis of an automated control system for the drum drying process in food production. The project includes a comprehensive technological overview, mathematical modeling, MATLAB-based simulation, controller design, and implementation of automation using programmable logic controllers (PLCs). The primary objective is to stabilize product quality by maintaining the required moisture level, optimizing energy consumption, and establishing a robust framework for industrial application in compliance with food safety standards such as HACCP and ISO 22000.

The report emphasizes the necessity of automating food processing operations, as product consistency and safety increasingly depend on precise control of parameters including temperature, steam pressure, and drum speed. The proposed system achieves continuous monitoring and adjustment of process variables through the integration of sensors, feedback loops, and advanced control algorithms. This approach enables real-time regulation of the drying process, minimizes human error, and improves operational efficiency.

The structure of the thesis is organized as follows. Chapter 1 provides a detailed description of the drum drying process, including its physical principles, stages of drying, and key technological components. Chapter 2 defines the control plant, identifies input and output variables, and formulates the control problem. Chapter 3 develops the mathematical model of the system based on heat and mass transfer equations and presents its analysis using MATLAB tools. In Chapter 4, several control strategies are investigated, including decentralized PID, LQI, and robust H_∞ control, with comparative performance analysis demonstrating the advantages of the selected approach. Chapter 5 focuses on the selection of technical equipment, including PLCs, sensors, and actuators, and describes the system architecture. Chapter 6 presents the implementation of the control algorithm and visualization through SCADA systems.

Furthermore, Chapter 7 introduces advanced features, including computer vision-based quality control and an NLP-based assistant for technical documentation. Chapter 8 provides an economic analysis of the proposed system, while Chapter 9 addresses occupational health and safety considerations.

Overall, the developed system represents a comprehensive and modern approach to industrial drying automation, combining advanced control theory, digital technologies, and practical engineering implementation.

1. DESCRIPTION OF THE TECHNOLOGICAL PROCESS

Drum drying process is another heating process that is utilized to dry liquid or semi-liquid materials by placing them in a thin film on the surface of rotating drums that are heated. The product is covered over the outer one of the drums, which are internally heated by steam. As the drum is rotating, the heat is transferred to the material resulting in the rapid drying of a thin layer. As soon as the product becomes moist enough, it is scraped off using a stationary knife and is collected either in the form of a dry powder or flakes. Drying rate is affected by the following parameters: steam pressure, rotation rate of drum, rate of feed and the film thickness. Sensors are also used in automated systems to keep a constant check on temperature, moisture content and pressure in order to ensure that the drying process and product quality is consistent. The control system regulates the steam flow and the speed of the drum within the real time, so that the best condition is maintained and the loss of energy is minimized. The process is common in the food industry in the manufacture of products like baby food, starches, fruit puree, dairy products, tea leaves and instant cereal where the quality must be consistent and the throughput high.

1.1 Principles of drum drying

Drum drying is a specialized method, which is mainly applied on liquid and semi-liquid food material; this is founded on the basic interaction of heat transfer and mass transfer. As opposed to most other drying techniques that involve the use of hot air or radiations, the use of conduction is the primary mode of operation in drum drying, thus making it one of the most efficient methods of drying products that need fast and even-handed drying. Within this process, a fluid product is dispersed in thin film to the surface of a huge rotating drum. Internal heating of the drum is done through steam which supplies a constant flow of thermal energy. The heat moves through the wall of the drum to the thin layer of product as the drum spins, and the moisture easily evaporates. The product is dried and scraped off using a knife scraper as a flake or powder. The ease of the design and its efficiency has resulted in drum drying being an effective technology in food, chemical, and pharmaceutical companies [1].

1.2 Heat and mass transfer in drum drying

Heat transfer and mass transfer are two processes that characterize the drying process and are interdependent. Heat should be provided to give the energy required to release the moisture and the transfer of mass to ascertain that the vapor generated is carried out of the surface of the substance to the drying medium. Heat transfer: during drum drying, conduction is the major source of heat. Thin layer of product is applied on the rotating surface of a drum which is heated and thermal energy is

transferred directly through the metal surface to the wet material. This effective system enables quick heating and even distribution of energy [2].

Mass transfer: Since the moisture is evaporated, the vapor has to diffuse into the atmosphere of surrounding air or steam. The effectiveness of the step is determined by the variation in the pressure of the moisture available in the product and the drying media. When this driving force is low, such as when it is high because of ambient humidity, the rate of drying is slowed down. The intimate interaction between these two transfer processes determines the overall drying kinetics. Any restriction in either heat supply or vapor removal will significantly reduce process efficiency.

1.3 Stages of drying

In the process of drying, there are two large steps commonly used in the process of drum drying:

Constant Rate Period - At the beginning of the process, the product surface retains readily accessible moisture. Heat transfer to the surface results in evaporation at an approximately constant rate, primarily influenced by external factors such as drum surface temperature, drum rotation speed, and ambient air conditions.

Falling Rate Period - Once the easily accessible surface moisture is removed, internal water migration becomes the limiting factor. In drum drying, product thickness, porosity, and internal diffusion mechanisms—such as liquid diffusion, vapor diffusion, or capillary action—govern this stage. Increased resistance to moisture migration slows the drying rate, and as the product nears equilibrium moisture content, the drying rate further decreases. The critical moisture content marks the transition between these phases and varies with material composition and drying conditions. Accurate identification of this point is essential for optimizing drying schedules and preventing over-processing. While industrial drying may utilize conduction, convection, or radiation, drum drying primarily relies on conduction. The process involves applying a thin layer of feed material to the drum surface, where steam inside the drum heats the metal wall and transfers energy to the film. Moisture rapidly evaporates from the film surface. A stationary knife removes the dried material as sheets or flakes, which are subsequently milled into powders. This direct conduction approach enables drum dryers to achieve short drying times and high throughput, making them suitable for heat-sensitive and viscous products such as baby food, starches, purees, and dairy derivatives [2].

1.4 Main units and devices of a drum drying system

A drum drying facility comprises several interdependent units, each designed to ensure efficient heat transfer, controlled product handling, and precise process regulation. The integration of these components enables the production of high-

quality dried materials with uniform moisture content and consistent physical properties [3].

Key devices include the following: drum dryer - this central component consists of a large, hollow, steam-heated rotating drum. Its polished surface is coated with a thin, evenly distributed layer of feed material, facilitating rapid heat transfer to the product via direct conduction. Moisture evaporation occurs almost instantaneously, making this process suitable for heat-sensitive and viscous products. Drum design parameters, such as diameter, width, and rotation speed, directly affect drying time, product thickness, and overall efficiency. steam supply and condensate system - steam serves as the primary heating medium, injected into the drum at controlled pressure and temperature. The latent heat of steam is transferred to the drum wall, maintaining a constant drying surface temperature. Effective condensate removal through steam traps or siphons is essential to prevent poor heat transfer, localized cooling, or inconsistent drying. Inefficient condensate management can significantly increase energy consumption. Knife - a stationary blade is positioned just inside the drum surface, continuously removing the dried product film after moisture elimination. The angle, clearance, and sharpness of the knife must be carefully maintained to avoid damaging the drum surface while ensuring uniform product removal. The discharged material may appear as flakes, sheets, or powders, depending on processing requirements. Infrared thermometer (non-contact sensor): Continuous temperature monitoring is critical to prevent overheating or excessive drying. Infrared thermometers provide real-time, non-invasive measurements of either the drying product layer or the drum surface temperature. These data are integrated into the control system to optimize drying conditions and protect sensitive nutrients or active ingredients. Feed tank and distribution system - the raw material, whether semi-liquid or liquid, is stored in a feed tank and pumped onto the drum. Specialized distribution devices, such as applicator rolls, spray nozzles, or dip-feed systems, ensure the formation of a uniform film on the drum surface. Feed consistency, viscosity, and solids concentration influence film thickness, drying kinetics, and final product quality. Local actuator pins and actuators - these controls, which may be mechanical or electronic, regulate key operating parameters, including knife positioning, drum rotation speed, and steam and condensate valve settings. They provide precise control and adaptability to changing product or environmental conditions, thereby minimizing variability and enhancing reproducibility. PC and control system (e.g., UMAC 6000) - Modern drum dryers rely on computer-based process control. Systems such as the UMAC 6000 integrate programmable logic controllers (PLCs), SCADA interfaces, and process monitoring software to manage operations. Parameters including steam pressure, drum speed, feed rate, product temperature, and condensate removal are continuously monitored.

1.5 Process block diagram

To have a better picture and comprehension of technology workflow of drum drying a process block diagram has been elaborated (Figure 1.1). The diagram gives a structural representation of the system showing the primary units of operation of the system and also showing the direction of flow of material, energy and information [3]. The block diagram simplifies the understanding of complex process interactions by breaking the system into clearly defined functional units. It also highlights the interconnection between different subsystems, allowing for easier identification of control points and process dependencies. Furthermore, the visualization supports the design and analysis of control strategies by illustrating how input variables influence system outputs. This provides a solid foundation for subsequent modeling, simulation, and implementation of the automation system.

Figure 1.1 – Structure diagram of drum drying process

The drying process of the drums starts with a feeding system, in which the liquid or semi-liquid matter is fed on the heated drum surface through a feed tank. To maintain the even transfer of heat and mass in the drying process, application roll or spray nozzles are used to provide a uniform thin film. The hollow drum receives steam at a controlled pressure and temperature to provide the required heat in the process of evaporation of moisture. A system of condensate removal ensures there

is no build up in the drum, which keeps the temperature and efficiency of the drying process steady. The moisture is removed through the rotating process of the drum with the use of a thin film and the dried layer is scraped away using a stationary knife to form flakes or powder. A system of condensate removal ensures there is no build up in the drum, which keeps the temperature and efficiency of the drying process steady. The moisture is removed through the rotating process of the drum with the use of a thin film and the dried layer is scraped away using a stationary knife to form flakes or powder. Table below illustrates the description of indicators and instruments (Table 1.1). Additionally, precise control of operating parameters such as drum rotation speed, steam pressure, and feed rate is essential to ensure consistent product quality and energy efficiency. Instrumentation systems, including temperature sensors, pressure gauges, and flow meters, continuously monitor the process and provide real-time feedback for control adjustments. This allows operators to maintain optimal drying conditions and prevent issues such as overheating or uneven drying. Furthermore, automated control systems can be implemented to enhance process stability, reduce manual intervention, and improve overall reliability.

Table 1.1 – Description of indicators and instruments

Name	Description
TI	Temperature indicator
TT	Temperature transmitter
TIC	Temperature indicator controller
M	Motor
SIC	Steam indicator controller
ST	Setpoint
PT	Pressure transmitter
PLC	Programmable logic controller
V-101, V-102, V-103	Valve
Satellite	Product Inlet point
KShL	Mechanical linkage symbol

The drying process of the drums starts with a feeding system, in which the liquid or semi-liquid matter is fed on the heated drum surface through a feed tank. To maintain the even transfer of heat and mass in the drying process, application roll or spray nozzles are used to provide a uniform thin film. The hollow drum receives steam at a controlled pressure and temperature to provide the required heat in the process of evaporation of moisture

Real-time monitoring of the temperature of the product and the drum is carried out through the use of infrared sensors to ensure thermal stability and avoid excessive heating. Local actuators and auxiliary systems are also involved in the process to control the speed of the drums, knife clearance and the flow of steam. The PLC SCADA control system measures parameters which include the steam pressure,

the speed of the drum, the feed rate and the temperature of the product and this is a continuous process. This allows automatic real time modifications, which ensures the quality of products, energy efficiency, and food safety requirements (HACCP, ISO 22000). Contemporary dryer types of drums use information-based control and predictive maintenance, which improves reliability, traceability, and energy efficiency. Through these developments, there is enhanced sustainability and competitiveness in food production [5].

Figure 1.2 – Block diagram of drum drying process

Step 1 - Initialization of Process Parameters. The process begins with the initialization of the main operating parameters of the system, including temperature (T), moisture content (M), steam pressure (P), feed flow rate (F), drying time (t), energy input (E), and product mass (m). These parameters serve as reference values for the control algorithm and allow the system to establish appropriate operating conditions for the drying process.

Step 2 - Product Feeding and Moisture Evaluation. After the parameters are initialized, the raw material is supplied to the drum dryer through the product feeding system. At this stage, the control system evaluates the moisture content of the product. If the measured moisture exceeds the specified threshold value of 0.111 kg of water per kilogram of product, the system increases the rolling speed of the drum. This adjustment enhances the evaporation process by improving heat transfer and reducing the residence time of the product on the drum surface.

Step 3 - Steam Supply and Thermal Regulation. Once the feeding stage is completed, steam is supplied to the drum dryer to provide the thermal energy necessary for moisture evaporation. During this stage, the system continuously

monitors the steam pressure and temperature. If the pressure exceeds 6 bar or the temperature reaches 142°C, the control system activates the condensate discharge mechanism to maintain efficient heat transfer and stabilize the drying conditions.

Step 5 - Steam Supply and Thermal Regulation. After verifying that the required technological conditions have been achieved, the system proceeds to the final stage where operational information is collected and processed. This information may be used for monitoring, reporting, or supervisory control purposes. Finally, the drying cycle is completed, and the system terminates the process or prepares for the next production cycle. Overall, the described sequence ensures controlled and efficient operation of the drum drying process by maintaining optimal thermal and process conditions at each stage. As a result, the system achieves stable product quality while minimizing energy consumption and operational deviations.

1.6 Description of the general parameters

Explaining the technological process of drum drying, it is necessary to define the key parameters which should be monitored and controlled. These parameters directly influence drying kinetics, quality of the product and energy efficiency. Adequate control enables the operators to attain steady operation, avoid overheating or under drying, and achieve reproducibility in mass production [4]. Parameters that are of the most importance in drum drying systems are: Steam pressure and temperature supplied to the drum, which determine the drum surface temperature and influence drying rate. Drum rotational speed, which regulates film thickness and residence time.

Table 1.2 – Parameters of technological process

Parameter	Typical Range	Unit
Steam Pressure (Ps)	0.3 – 0.6	MPa
Steam temperature (Ts)	120 – 160	°C
Drum surface temperature	105 – 150	°C
Drum speed (n)	0.2 – 2.0	rpm
Film thickness (δ)	0.2 – 0.6	mm
Feed flow rate (F)	20 – 200	L/h
Solids concentration (Cs)	10 – 50	% (w/w)
Knife clearance (h)	0.1 – 0.3	mm
Product moisture content	2 – 6	% (w.b.)
Outlet product temperature	60 – 90	°C
Condensate removal efficiency	≥ 90	%
Ambient air humidity (φ)	30 – 70	% RH

To conclude, modern drum drying system development is a complicated engineering task, which involves specific monitoring and control of numerous parameters, which are sensitive to each other. Constant control of the steam pressure, the temperature of the drum, stream of the feed, and the clearance of the knives also

provides effective heat and mass transfers, and control of the moisture level in the product and discharge temperature assures uniform quality and safety of the products.

1.7 Conclusion

Drum drying is among the most flexible and efficient processes of handling liquid and semi-liquid food products which is very important in preservation and development of food products. Its principle functioning which is a direct heat conduction mode enables it to be operated at a high throughput rate as well as rapid removal of moisture, and a good consistency of products which are too valuable in the modern food industries which deal with baby foods, dairy derivatives, tea leaves and purees. Drum drying increases shelf life by keeping the moisture content at safe and stable levels, improving microbial safety, and minimizing the cost of storage and transportation [4].

2. TECHNICAL PROCESS OF THE CONTROL PLANT

To ensure stable and efficient operation of the drum drying system, the control process must incorporate reliable measurement, control, and monitoring functions. The plant comprises interconnected mechanical, thermal, and fluid subsystems, whose coordinated operation determines the quality of the final dried product. Parameters such as temperature, feed rate, drum rotation, and condensate removal should be automatically regulated to optimize heat and mass transfer. Furthermore, advanced control methods are required to address external disturbances, including variations in feed properties or steam pressure. These considerations will inform the development of an effective automation structure for the drum dryer unit.

2.1 Description of the chosen control object

The automation of the process of drum drying is associated with the management of technological devices like steam valves, feed pumps, positioners of knives, regulators of the speed of the rotary of the drums, and condensate extraction devices. The centralized management is used to implement commands to start/stop, open/close and adjust the parameters. The piece of equipment which is considered the control object is the drum dryer unit [2]. All system parameters are sent to the SCADA system that offers remote (dispatch) and automatic changes of distributed devices and monitoring of process variables. It has to be an open, distributed, and hierarchical system to provide flexibility and reliability of operation. In order to enhance the quality of control of the drying process and homogeneity of the final product, there is a need to come up with the correct mathematical and structural models of the drum drying unit (Figure 2.1).

Figure 2.1 – Description of the control plant

The following tasks are required to achieve the stated objectives. First, the conceptual model of the control object must be substantiated, including identification of the primary disturbances affecting the system, as well as specification of input and output coordinates. A modular scheme of the drying process should be synthesized to accommodate variations in drum size, feed viscosity, solids concentration, and distribution mechanisms. Mathematical models for each module (steam system, condensate removal, feed system, drum dynamics, product moisture) must be developed, and their interactions under different operational conditions defined. To improve the precision of drum drying models, several technological and environmental factors must be addressed [1]. The geometry and rotational speed of the drum directly influence film thickness, which determines the intensity of heat and mass exchange. Even minor changes in drum speed or diameter can result in significant variations in product residence time and drying efficiency [4]. Additionally, tolerance-based control allows the final moisture content to fluctuate within a safe range, enabling flexibility, energy savings, and adaptation to disturbances without compromising product stability and safety [1].

2.2 Structural scheme of the control plant

A drum dryer is the control object of the technological process. The manipulated input in the automated control system is the steam pressure entering the dryer and controlled output is the product moisture content. The disturbances in the process, which are unmeasured like the presence of non-condensable gases and condensate accumulation, are represented by z in the diagram. (Figure 2.2).

Figure 2.2 - Structural scheme of control plant

The diagram above shows the main manipulated variable, steam pressure (p_v), acting on the system and the resulting controlled variable, product moisture content (X_f). The process is also subject to unmeasured disturbances, such as the accumulation of non-condensable gases and condensate, indicated in the diagram as $Z(t)$. These disturbances affect the stability of drying, and their impact is compensated for through the automatic regulation $U(t)$ of steam pressure. [3].

2.3 Specification table

Table below represents the information about the main technical parameters of the control object. Seven variables must be considered when defining the control system for the drum dryer (Table 2.1). The product outlet temperature and the final moisture content serve as output parameters, determining the quality and safety of the dried product [3].

Table 2.1 – Main characteristics of control plant

Nº	Name of the parameter	Quantity	Unit	Description	Input/Output	Type
1	Q	0 – 6	bar	Heating steam pressure	I	A
2	F	22.28	kg/s	Dry gas mass flow rate	I	A
3	$Z(t)$	-	-	Disturbances	I	A
4	$U(t)$	4 – 20	mA	Control signal to steam valve	I	A
5	T_A	60 - 90	°C	Outlet product temperature	Q	A
6	X	0.111 – 0.120	kg/kg DM	Product moisture content	Q	A
7	T_{drum}	105 - 150	°C	Drum surface temperature	Q	A

The feed flow rate, solids concentration, steam pressure, and degree of steam valve opening are input parameters that directly influence process stability and drying kinetics. Additionally, the system is susceptible to uncontrolled disturbances such as fluctuations in steam supply, variations in raw material viscosity, or changes in ambient humidity. These disturbances must be corrected by automatic control to maintain consistent product quality [3].

2.4 Statement of the problem

Despite its extensive application in food sector, the drying process of the drum is extremely susceptible to both technological and environmental disruptions. The changes in steam pressure, changes in the properties of raw materials, and the presence of non-condensable gases or condensate in the system tend to cause variations in the final product moisture content that should be kept within a very limited range of 0.111kg/kg DM. Because moisture content is a vital parameter that is essential to food safety, nutritional value, and product stability, its variability presents a major challenge to control any process. Moreover, uncontrolled fluctuations have a negative influence on the energy efficiency of the dryer and decrease the economic sustainability of the production. In this respect, the main problem is that no effective control strategy exists that could stabilize the drying conditions under different disturbances. The current work thus seeks to come up with a structural and mathematical model of the drum dryer that considers the nonlinear interactions among steam pressure, heat and mass transfer and product dynamics.

The ultimate goal is stabilized process operation which maintains the final product moisture within rigid quality parameters, and at the same time reducing energy use and enhancing system overall performance. In this regard, the study suggests an enhanced automation and real-time control tool, which is executed on a SCADA-based platform, to guarantee the safety of products, their reproducibility, and competitiveness of the drum drying technology in the industrial contexts.

2.5 Conclusion

Drum drying is a very viable and universal process to dry both liquid and semi-liquid foodstuffs as it preserves and improves the quality of the food. This process increases the shelf life, microbial safety and texture and flavors of products including baby food, dairy derivatives, purees and starches by eliminating moisture via direct heat conduction. The effectiveness of the system, however, relies on proper management of parameters such as steam pressure, drum speed, feed flow as well as content of moisture in the products. The modern drum drying systems are a combination of the modern automation, real-time monitoring and control systems that ensure the reproducibility, energy efficiency and adherence to the food safety management standards including HACCP and ISO 22000 [3]. Additionally, the economic competitiveness and environmental sustainability are also achieved through the minimization of losses and energy consumption by the use of drum drying. Finally, drum drying is the place of contact of technology and food safety with industrial sustainability. As the control systems, energy recovery, as well as process optimization further develop, it will keep being one of the cornerstone technologies of the food industry, providing high-quality, safe and marketable products.

3. MATHEMATICAL MODEL OF THE CONTROL PLANT

The design and analysis of automated control systems require the critical step of mathematical modeling. This approach allows engineers to represent the behavior of technological processes through mathematical relationships between inputs and outputs. In this study, the drying process of the drum is modeled to examine how control variables such as steam pressure, drum rotation speed, and feed rate affect final product characteristics, specifically moisture content and temperature. The mathematical model is based on the physical principles of heat and mass transfer that govern the drying process. This model provides a foundation for forecasting system behavior, optimizing control parameters, and ensuring stable and efficient operation. The drum dryer, as the selected control object, is represented in three mathematical forms: differential equations, transfer functions, and state space representations. Each form offers a distinct perspective on the system's dynamic behavior and is subsequently utilized in simulation and controller design using MATLAB.

3.1 Description of the mathematical model

Rotary drum dryers can be mathematically modeled to elucidate how variations in control parameters, such as steam flow rate or valve opening, affect the output variable, specifically the moisture content of the final product. To ensure that the drying process remains efficient, safe, and yields high-quality material, it is necessary to develop a robust mathematical model suitable for control system design and analysis. Because drying involves gradual changes in physical parameters over time, the process can be represented as a dynamic system using ordinary differential equations (ODEs) that describe thermal-hygrometric exchanges along the drum. This approach captures the coupled effects of air cooling and humidification during material drying. The comprehensive model consists of non-linear balance equations that define state variables (air and product temperatures and moisture contents), control variables (air or steam flow rate), and measurable outputs (product exit moisture). Following the methodology established by Friso (2023), the dryer is conceptually divided into two principal zones: one where product moisture exceeds the critical point and another where it falls below this threshold. Each zone is characterized by a system of ODEs derived from heat and mass transfer balances, incorporating parameters such as the convective heat transfer coefficient, thermal energy per kilogram of evaporated water, and the transverse dimension of the product layer. These equations serve as the foundation for developing and validating advanced control algorithms for drum drying systems [7].

3.2 Specification and calculation of general parameters

From drum drying system, there is following parameters:

Table 3.1 – Specification table

Parameter	Symbol	Value	Unit	Description
1	2	3	4	5
Inlet moisture (dry basis)	X_I	1.200	–	Initial moisture content at dryer inlet
Critical moisture	X_C	0.290	–	Moisture at transition from constant to falling rate
Exit moisture (setpoint)	X_E	0.111	–	Desired final moisture content of dried product
Air inlet temperature	T_{AI}	470	°C	Temperature of hot air entering the dryer
Wet-bulb temperature	T_{WB}	62	°C	Product temperature in Zone I–C (constant rate)
Drum diameter	D	2.1	m	Internal diameter of the rotary drum
Drum length	L	12.2	m	Total axial length of the drying drum
Air density	ρ_{air}	1.18	kg/m ³	Average density of drying air
Dry air mass flow rate	G_{DAI}	22.28	kg/s	Mass flow rate of dry air (from empirical correlation)
Dry product inlet flow	G_{DPI}	7.61	kg/s	Mass flow rate of dry product at inlet
Specific heat of dry air	c_A	1005	J/(kg·K)	Heat capacity of dry air
Specific heat of water vapor	c_V	1926	J/(kg·K)	Heat capacity of superheated steam
Thermal energy (Zone I–C)	r_{I-C}	3.892×10^6	J/kg	Energy to evaporate 1 kg of water in constant rate zone
Thermal energy (Zone –E)	r_{C-E}	7.487×10^6	J/kg	Energy to evaporate 1 kg of water in falling rate zone
Convective parameter	αf	1078	W/(m·K)	Product of heat transfer coefficient and transverse dimension
Total heat transfer conductance	$h_A = \alpha f L$	13,152	W/K	Overall convective conductance along drum length

Continuation of Table 3.1

1	2	3	4	5
Air thermal capacitance	$C_a = c_A \rho_{\text{air}}(LD)$	30,400	J/K	Effective heat capacity of air volume in drum
Product thermal capacitance	C_m	1160	J/K	Lumped heat capacity of product (estimated near X_C)
Drying rate gain (temp diff)	κ_{eff}	1.0×10^{-4}	s^{-1}	Linearized effect of ΔT on drying rate
Moisture decay rate	β_{eff}	5.0×10^{-4}	s^{-1}	Natural decay rate of moisture deviation
Moisture–temperature coupling	w'_{eff}	−0.002	–	Sensitivity of drying to product moisture deviation
Steam input gain	K_{steam}	200	W/K	Gain from control input to air temperature change

The product moisture content can be expressed on either a wet basis (w.b.) — kg of water per kg of total wet product, or a dry basis (d.b.) — kg of water per kg of bone-dry solids. The two are related by:

$$X_{db} = \frac{X_{wb}}{1 - X_{wb}}, \quad X_{wb} = \frac{X_{db}}{1 + X_{db}} \quad (3.1)$$

The rotary drum dryer is split into two axial regions:

Zone I-C (length L_{I-C}): product moisture X decreases from inlet X_I to critical moisture X_C . In this zone, product temperature is assumed to be equal to the wet-bulb temperature T_{WB} .

Zone C-E (length L_{C-E}): product moisture falls from X_C to exit X_E . Here, product temperature may exceed T_{WB} .

Notation that will be used through the section:

z – axial coordinate along drum, $z \in [0, L]$;

$T_A(z)$ – air temperature;

$T_P(z)$ – product temperature;

T_w – wet bulb temperature of air-vapor mixture

$X(z)$ – product moisture;

G_{PI} – product mass flow;

$G_{EV}(z)$ – cumulative vapor mass generated up to current z ;

α – connective heat transfer coefficient;
 f - transverse dimension (sum of perimeters of product elements in a section);

These variables form the basis for describing the heat and mass transfer processes occurring inside the rotary drum. Using the axial coordinate z , the evolution of air temperature, product temperature, and moisture content can be expressed as continuous functions along the dryer length.

Figure 3.1 - Open-Loop MIMO State-Space model

The distinction between Zone I–C and Zone C–E is essential because the governing drying mechanism changes at the critical moisture X_C . The notation above will be used consistently in the subsequent derivations and balance equations.

3.2.1 I-C zone

In the start (zone I-C) the product surface remains at the T_{WB} , meaning that the convective heat delivered from the air is immediately consumed for evaporation. To describe this region, consider heat flux from the air to the product:

$$dq = \alpha f (T_A - T_{WB}) dz \quad (3.1)$$

Heat flux reduces the air temperature as it travels along the dryer. Under the assumption that there is no heat loss through the walls, the decrease in air enthalpy must equal to heat flux:

$$dq = -(G_{DAI} c_A + G_{EV} c_V) dT_A \quad (3.2)$$

Because evaporation is the only mechanism generating vapor, every incremental amount of vapor is created at the expense of thermal energy(3):

$$dq = r_{I-C} dG_{EV} \quad (3.3)$$

Equating for dq in (3.2) and (3.3) gives differential relation between air temperature and vapor flow:

$$-(G_{DAI}c_A + G_{EV}c_V)dT_A = r_{I-C}dG_{EV} \quad (3.4)$$

This equation is separable and can be integrated directly. Integrating from the inlet to the point where moisture reaches X_C , it leads to:

$$\ln\left(\frac{G_{DAI}c_A + G_{EV(I-C)}c_V}{G_{DAI}c_A}\right) = \frac{c_V}{r_{I-C}}(T_{AI} - T_{AC}) \quad (3.5)$$

which connects vapor production to the air cooling in I-C zone.

Next, substitute heat-transfer relation (3.1) to the air-energy balance (3.2), which produce(6):

$$(G_{DAI}c_A + G_{EV}c_V)dT_A = -\alpha f(T_A - T_{WB})dz \quad (3.6)$$

Again, it can be separated. However, because G_{EV} grows along the axis and influences the local air heat capacity, integral does not reduce to elementary functions, it gives exponential integral $Ei(\cdot)$:

$$e^{\frac{c_V}{r_{I-C}}(T_{AI} - T_{WB})} \left(Ei\left(\frac{c_V}{r_{I-C}}(-T_{AC} + T_{WB})\right) - Ei\left(\frac{c_V}{r_{I-C}}(-T_{AI} + T_{WB})\right) \right) = -\frac{\alpha f}{G_{DAI}c_A} L_{I-C} \quad (3.7)$$

which determines the length of the first zone for a given inlet temperature T_{AI} and wet-bulb temperature T_{WB} .

$$G_{EV(I-C)} = G_{PI} \frac{X_I - X_C}{1 + X_I} \quad (3.8)$$

Finally, because moisture in this region evaporates at the constant rate required to bring the product from its inlet moisture X_I to the critical value X_C , the total mass of vapor generated in the I-C zone is given by mass balance that represented above.

3.2.2 C-E zone

After reaching X_C , removal of moisture is no longer done by free-surface evaporation but by diffusion-controlled evaporation inside the solid, making the surface temperature rise above the wet-bulb value. So $T_p(z)$ can no longer assumed constant.

In region C-E, the evaporated moisture per unit length continues to increase the vapor flow $G_{EV}(z)$, and therefore changes effective heat capacity of the moist air. As in I-C zone, energy balance remains:

$$dq = -(G_{DAI}c_A + G_{EV}c_V)dT_A \quad (3.9)$$

while latent consumption of this heat to evaporate moisture in this region is expressed as:

$$dq = r_{C-E}dG_{EV} \quad (3.10)$$

Equating (3.9) and (3.10) gives:

$$-(G_{DAI}c_A + G_{EV}c_V)dT_A = r_{C-E}dG_{EV} \quad (3.11)$$

Integrating (3.11) between point C and final exit point E gives:

$$\ln \left(\frac{G_{DAI}c_A + (G_{EV(I-C)} + G_{EV(C-E)})c_V}{G_{DAI}c_A + G_{EV(I-C)}c_V} \right) = \frac{c_V}{r_{C-E}} (T_{AC} - T_{AE}) \quad (3.12)$$

which expresses air cooling in C-E as function of vapor load and the enthalpy required for internal moisture removal.

Meanwhile, the air temperature change is ruled by the heat-transfer expression:

$$(G_{DAI}c_A + G_{EV}c_V)dT_A = -\alpha f (T_A - T_P)dz \quad (3.13)$$

but now $T_P(Z)$ is not equal to T_{WB} . Friso also derived a expression for solution of this equation, wrapping it to compact expression for the sake of simplicity:

$$\Phi_{C-E}(T_{AC}, T_{AE}, G_{EV}) = -\frac{\alpha f}{G_{DAI}c_A} L_{C-E} \quad (3.14)$$

Finally, the moisture removed in this region is fixed by mass balance:

$$G_{EV(C-E)} = G_{PI} \frac{X_C - X_E}{1 + X_C} \quad (3.15)$$

Those equations define second drying zone.

3.2.3 Wet-bulb temperature calculation

The wet-bulb temperature is important because it fixes the product temperature in the entire I-C zone. It is obtained by linking isenthalpic constraint on the humid air stream:

$$h_{AI} = h_{WB} \quad (3.16)$$

If expressed explicitly in terms of dry-air temperature and humidity:

$$c_A T_{AI} + (\lambda + c_V T_{AI}) x_{AI} = c_A T_{WB} + (\lambda + c_V T_{WB}) x_{WB} \quad (3.17)$$

where,

x_{AI} – inlet humidity ratio;

x_{WB} – humidity ratio of saturated air at T_{WB} ;

Humidity at saturation is:

$$x_{WB} = \frac{0.622 p_{V,WB}}{p_{\text{atm}} - p_{V,WB}} \quad (3.18)$$

The wet-bulb temperature is determined by solving the above equations iteratively, since the saturation vapor pressure $p_{V,WB}$ is a nonlinear function of temperature. This parameter provides a practical estimate of the minimum achievable product temperature during drying and is essential for accurate prediction of heat and mass transfer processes.

3.2.4 Global energy balance

Once the moisture removed in each zone is known, the total evaporation must match the enthalpy decrease of the air stream. The global energy balance is:

$$G_{EV(I-C)} r_{I-C} + G_{EV(C-E)} r_{C-E} = G_{DAI} c_A (T_{AI} - T_{AE}) \quad (3.19)$$

It links inlet T_{AI} to outlet T_{AE} , and keeps system thermodynamically consistent.

3.2.5 Final system of equations:

(a) – moisture balances:

$$G_{EV(I-C)} = G_{PI} \frac{X_I - X_C}{1 + X_I} \quad (3.20)$$

$$G_{EV(C-E)} = G_{PI} \frac{X_C - X_E}{1 + X_C}$$

(b) – Integrated air–vapor energy relations

$$\ln\left(\frac{G_{DAI}c_A + G_{EV(I-C)}c_V}{G_{DAI}c_A}\right) = \frac{c_V}{r_{I-C}}(T_{AI} - T_{AC}) \quad (3.21)$$

$$\ln\left(\frac{G_{DAI}c_A + (G_{EV(I-C)} + G_{EV(C-E)})c_V}{G_{DAI}c_A + G_{EV(I-C)}c_V}\right) = \frac{c_V}{r_{C-E}}(T_{AC} - T_{AE})$$

c) – Heat-transfer integrals (with exponential integral):

$$\begin{aligned} & e^{\frac{c_V}{r_{I-C}}(T_{AI}-T_{WB})} \left(Ei\left(\frac{c_V}{r_{I-C}}(-T_{AC} + T_{WB})\right) - Ei\left(\frac{c_V}{r_{I-C}}(-T_{AI} + T_{WB})\right) \right) \\ &= -\frac{\alpha f}{G_{DAI}c_A} L_{I-C} \end{aligned} \quad (3.22)$$

$$\Phi_{C-E}(T_{AC}, T_{AE}, G_{EV}) = -\frac{\alpha f}{G_{DAI}c_A} L_{C-E}$$

(d) – Wet-bulb condition

$$\begin{aligned} c_A T_{AI} + (\lambda + c_V T_{AI}) x_{AI} &= c_A T_{WB} + (\lambda + c_V T_{WB}) x_{WB} \\ x_{WB} &= \frac{0.622 p_{V,WB}}{p_{atm} - p_{V,WB}} \end{aligned} \quad (3.23)$$

(e) - Global energy balance

$$G_{EV(I-C)}r_{I-C} + G_{EV(C-E)}r_{C-E} = G_{DAI}c_A(T_{AI} - T_{AE}) \quad (3.24)$$

This system of equations describes the coupled heat and mass transfer processes in the drying operation. It is typically solved using numerical methods to determine key process parameters and ensure accurate system analysis.

3.2.6 Assumptions for further

Stationary model considers moisture and temperature distributions along the drum: $\frac{dT_A}{dz}$ and $\frac{dX}{dz}$. But for synthesis of control system it is necessary to obtain dynamic model in time-domain: $\frac{dT_A}{dt}$, $\frac{dT_P}{dt}$ and $\frac{dX}{dt}$. For this transition, the lumped ODE method should be introduced. Instead of continuous distribution of $z \in [0, L]$, consider drum as uniform controlled volume with averaged parameters. The main physical principle by which all of equations will be constructed is following:

$$\frac{dE}{dt} = \dot{Q} - \dot{W} + \sum \dot{m}_i h_i \quad (3.25)$$

where,

E – system's internal energy;

\dot{Q} – heat supply;

\dot{W} – work that done(neglectable);

$\dot{m}_i h_i$ - enthalpy flow;

3.2.7 Energetic balance of air

Consider air in drum as system with heat capacitance:

$$C_a = m_a c_A \quad (3.26)$$

Here, m_a is a mass of air in drum [kg], and c_A is a heat capacitance of dry air [J / (kg · K)]. From steam, heat supply will be:

$$\dot{Q}_{steam} = K_{steam} \cdot u \quad (3.27)$$

where, u is control input.

Convective heat exchange to product will be [7]:

$$\dot{Q}_{conv} = \int_0^L \alpha f (T_A - T_P) dz = \alpha L (T_A - T_P) = h_A (T_A - T_P) \quad (3.28)$$

where, $h_A = \alpha f L$ – general thermal conductivity [W/ K]. Moreover, energy for evaporation of moisture:

$$dq = r_{I-C} G_{EV} \quad (3.29)$$

But for dynamic model:

$$\dot{Q}_{evap} = \dot{m}_{evap} \cdot L_v \quad (3.30)$$

Where, \dot{m}_{evap} – rate of evaporation [kg / s], L_v – latent heat of vaporization [J / kg].

Hence, energy balance:

$$C_a \frac{dT_A}{dt} = K_{steam} u - h_A (T_A - T_P) - \dot{m}_{evap} L_v \quad (3.31)$$

Similarly to air, heat capacitance of product is:

$$C_m = m_p c_p \quad (3.32)$$

Heat supply by convection:

$$Q_{conv} = h_A(T_A - T_P) \quad (3.33)$$

And heat consumption:

$$Q_{evap, product} = m_{evap} \cdot r_{eff} \quad (3.34)$$

where, r_{eff} – specific heat of vaporization [J / kg].
Hence, energy balance:

$$C_m \frac{dT_P}{dt} = h_A(T_A - T_P) - m_{evap} r_{eff} \quad (3.35)$$

These equations describe the dynamic heat exchange between air and product during drying. They are essential for modeling temperature changes and designing effective control of the process.

3.2.8 Mass balance for moisture

Moisture is defined as:

$$X = \frac{m_{water}}{m_{dry}} \quad (3.36)$$

And its rate of change is:

$$m_p \frac{dX}{dt} = -m_{evap} \quad (3.37)$$

The rate of evaporation will be simplified linearized combination of I-C and C-E zones from Friso model:

$$m_{evap} = \kappa_{eff}(T_A - T_P) + \beta_{eff} m_p (X - X_{eq}) \quad (3.38)$$

Where, κ_{eff} is a temperature influence coefficient [kg / (s · K)], β_{eff} - rate of natural decomposition of moisture, and X_{eq} – equilibrium moisture.

Substituting to (3) gives:

$$\frac{dX}{dt} = -\frac{\kappa_{eff}}{m_p}(T_A - T_P) - \beta_{eff}(X - X_{eq}) \quad (3.39)$$

Combining all equations, get the final time-domain system:

$$\begin{aligned}
C_a \frac{dT_A}{dt} &= K_{\text{steam}} u - h_A(T_A - T_P) - L_v \left(\kappa_{\text{eff}}(T_A - T_P) + \beta_{\text{eff}} m_p (X - X_{\text{eq}}) \right) \\
C_m \frac{dT_P}{dt} &= h_A(T_A - T_P) - r_{\text{eff}} \left(\kappa_{\text{eff}}(T_A - T_P) + \beta_{\text{eff}} m_p (X - X_{\text{eq}}) \right) \\
\frac{dX}{dt} &= -\frac{\kappa_{\text{eff}}}{m_p} (T_A - T_P) - \beta_{\text{eff}} (X - X_{\text{eq}})
\end{aligned} \quad (3.40)$$

This resulting system of differential equations represents the complete dynamic model of the drying process, capturing the interactions between air temperature, product temperature, and moisture content. It enables analysis of system behavior over time and serves as a basis for controller design and simulation in practical applications.

3.2.9 Linearization around operating point

Stationary state $(T_{A,SS}, T_{P,SS}, X_{SS}, u_{SS})$ is defined by:

$$\frac{dT_A}{dt} = 0, \quad \frac{dT_P}{dt} = 0, \quad \frac{dX}{dt} = 0 \quad (3.41)$$

Table 3.2 - Process parameters and operating conditions

Variable	Symbol	Value	Unit
Stationary air temperature	$T_{A,SS}$	90	°C
Inlet air temperature (boundary)	T_{AI}	470	°C
Stationary gas mass flow	u_{SS}	13.33	kg/s
Product holdup mass	m_p	50	kg
$\partial \dot{m}_{\text{evap}} / \partial u_2$ at SS	—	0.01	(kg/s)/(kg/s)

The remaining stationary values $T_{P,SS}, X_{SS}, u_{1,SS}$ are determined implicitly by the equilibrium conditions $\frac{dT_P}{dt} = \frac{dX}{dt} = \frac{dT_A}{dt} = 0$ and enter the linearized matrices through the partial derivatives.

The differences will be

$$\Delta T_A = T_A - T_{A,SS}, \quad \Delta T_P = T_P - T_{P,SS}, \quad \Delta X = X - X_{SS}, \quad \Delta u = u \quad (3.42)$$

Linearize first equation:

$$C_a \frac{d\Delta T_A}{dt} = K_{\text{steam}} \Delta u - (h_A + L_v \kappa_{\text{eff}}) \Delta T_A + (h_A + L_v \kappa_{\text{eff}}) \Delta T_P - L_v \beta_{\text{eff}} m_p \Delta X$$

$$C_a \frac{d\Delta T_P}{dt} = (h_A - r_{\text{eff}} \kappa_{\text{eff}}) \Delta T_A - (h_A - r_{\text{eff}} \kappa_{\text{eff}}) \Delta T_P - r_{\text{eff}} \beta_{\text{eff}} m_p \Delta X \quad (3.43)$$

$$\frac{d\Delta X}{dt} = -\frac{\kappa_{\text{eff}}}{m_p} \Delta T_A + \frac{\kappa_{\text{eff}}}{m_p} \Delta T_P - \beta_{\text{eff}} \Delta X$$

The system equations are linearized around the equilibrium operating point and can be used to analyze the stability and the design controllers as well as the predictive response of the system to small perturbations in the input or state variables.

3.2.10 State-space representation

The state vector:

$$\mathbf{x} = \begin{bmatrix} \Delta T_A \\ \Delta T_P \\ \Delta X \end{bmatrix} \quad (3.44)$$

System in state-space representation will be:

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{\mathbf{x}} &= \mathbf{A}\mathbf{x} + \mathbf{B}u \\ y &= \mathbf{C}\mathbf{x} + Du \end{aligned} \quad (3.45)$$

Where,

$$\mathbf{A} = \begin{bmatrix} -\frac{h_A + L_v \kappa_{\text{eff}}}{C_a} & \frac{h_A + L_v \kappa_{\text{eff}}}{C_a} & 0 \\ \frac{h_A - r_{\text{eff}} \kappa_{\text{eff}}}{C_m} & -\frac{h_A - r_{\text{eff}} \kappa_{\text{eff}}}{C_m} & -\frac{r_{\text{eff}} \beta_{\text{eff}} m_p}{C_m} \\ -\frac{\kappa_{\text{eff}}}{m_p} & \frac{\kappa_{\text{eff}}}{m_p} & -\beta_{\text{eff}} \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\mathbf{B} = \begin{bmatrix} K_{\text{steam}} \\ C_a \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (3.46)$$

$$\mathbf{C} = [0 \quad 1 \quad 0]$$

$$D = 0$$

Substituting parameters provided by Friso's paper obtain numeric values in matrices and vectors:

$$\mathbf{A} = \begin{bmatrix} -0.4408 & 0.4408 & 0.0000 \\ 10.8471 & -10.8471 & -490.4741 \\ -5.0 \cdot 10^{-7} & 5.0 \cdot 10^{-7} & -5.0 \cdot 10^{-4} \end{bmatrix} \quad (3.47)$$

$$\mathbf{B} = \begin{bmatrix} 0.0066 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

Now to obtain transfer function, use general formula:

$$G(s) = \mathbf{C} (s\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{A})^{-1} \mathbf{B} + D \quad (3.48)$$

Calculating it with symbolic variables in MATLAB outputs transfer function:

$$G(s) = \frac{K_{\text{steam}}(h_A(\beta_{\text{eff}}+s) - \kappa_{\text{eff}}r_{\text{eff}}s)}{s(C_a C_m s^2 + s(\alpha_1 + C_a C_m \beta_{\text{eff}} + \alpha_2 - \alpha_3) + \beta_{\text{eff}}\alpha_1 + \beta_{\text{eff}}\alpha_2)} \quad (3.49)$$

where,

$$\alpha_1 = h_A(C_a + C_m);$$

$$\alpha_2 = C_m L_v \kappa_{\text{eff}};$$

$$\alpha_3 = C_a \kappa_{\text{eff}} r_{\text{eff}};$$

Substituting parameters provided by Friso's paper obtain numeric values in transfer function:

$$G(s) = \frac{-7.105 \cdot 10^{-15} s^2 + 0.0714 s + 3.729 \cdot 10^{-5}}{s^3 + 11.2900 s^2 + 5.8890 \cdot 10^{-3} s + 9.9620 \cdot 10^{-19}} \quad (3.50)$$

The leading numerator coefficient (-7.105×10^{-15}) and the constant term of the denominator (9.962×10^{-19}) are below the relative precision threshold of double-precision arithmetic for this system ($\approx 10^{-10} \times \max \text{coefficient} \approx 10^{-9}$). They represent residual round-off from the symbolic inversion of $(s\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{A})^{-1}$ and have no physical meaning. After truncation to physically significant digits the model reduces to:

$$G(s) = \frac{0.0741 s + 3.729 \cdot 10^{-5}}{s \cdot (s^2 + 11.29 s + 5.589 \cdot 10^{-3})} \quad (3.51)$$

Formula above represents the final transfer function after the all operations that were done previously.

3.2.11 Reducing order

To justify numerically, that we can do a reduction, we need to find systems' Hankel Singular Values (HSV). We use MatLabs' `hsvd` function, to find HSV. Numerical analysis reveals following values:

$$\Sigma = [9.962 \cdot 10^{-19}, 0.0102, 0.0003] \quad (3.52)$$

Clearly visible:

$\sigma_{H1} = 1 \cdot 10^{18}$: The presence of such a dominant singular value, several orders of magnitude above the next one indicates a near-integrating mode in the system dynamics. This corresponds to a pole asymptotically close to the origin of the s-plane, effectively behaving as a pure integrator over the time-scales of interest governing the long-term trend of the response. This state is structurally essential and must be preserved in any reduced model.

$\sigma_{H2} = 0.0102$: This value represents the primary stable dynamic (the "slope" or the main time constant) that shapes the transition toward the steady state.

$\sigma_{H3} = 0.0003$: The third singular value is approximately 34 times smaller than σ_{H2} , which in context of system is so small, that can be neglected.

The ratio $\frac{\sigma_{H2}}{\sigma_{H3}} \approx 34$ provides a rigorous numerical basis for truncation. The error incurred by discarding is bounded by $2\sigma_{H3} = 0.0006$. In the context of the system, this error is numerically insignificant, confirming that a 2nd-order model (one integrator + one stable pole) is the optimal balanced representation of the plant.

High-order systems pose two major challenges when implemented on PLCs. First, they involve high computational complexity. Real-time computation of the control action requires solving matrix equations, where the number of operations grows exponentially or cubically with the system dimension. Second, numerical stability becomes an issue. When control algorithms are implemented on controllers using limited-precision floating-point arithmetic (e.g., single precision), high-order matrices with a wide spread of eigenvalues may lead to the accumulation of rounding errors and, consequently, to divergence of the control algorithm.

Model order reduction methods make it possible to obtain a low-order system that behaves almost identically to the original system under given input excitations. In the context of a rotary drum dryer, this means preserving the dynamics of the product moisture content at the outlet in response to changes in steam pressure or drum rotational speed, while neglecting minor internal oscillations of temperature fields that do not have a significant impact on the final product quality.

Our main goal is to find system of $r < n$ order, such that:

$$\begin{aligned}\hat{\mathbf{x}}(t) &= \hat{\mathbf{A}} \hat{\mathbf{x}}(t) + \hat{\mathbf{B}}u(t) \\ \hat{\mathbf{y}}(t) &= \hat{\mathbf{C}} \hat{\mathbf{x}}(t) + \hat{\mathbf{D}}u(t)\end{aligned}\tag{3.53}$$

which minimizes errors $|y(t) - \hat{y}(t)|$.

To analyze, which states of a system are the most important, Gramian of controllability W_c and Gramian of observability W_o are introduced. These matrices are solutions for algebraic Lyapunov equations:

$$\begin{aligned}\mathbf{A} \mathbf{W}_c + \mathbf{W}_c \mathbf{A}^T + \mathbf{B} \mathbf{B}^T &= 0 \\ \mathbf{A}^T \mathbf{W}_o + \mathbf{W}_o \mathbf{A} + \mathbf{C}^T \mathbf{C} &= 0\end{aligned}\tag{3.54}$$

Physical meaning Gramian of controllability is the energy required for transferring system from one state to another. Physical meaning Gramian of observability is the energy of output signal, which is created by initial state.

In our approach, which is implemented in Matlab, the algorithm searches for such transformation of coordinates $\mathbf{x}_r = \mathbf{P}\mathbf{x}$, in which both matrices become equal and diagonal:

$$\mathbf{W}_c = \mathbf{W}_o = \mathbf{\Sigma} = \text{diag}(\sigma_{H1}, \sigma_{H2} \dots \sigma_{Hn})\tag{3.55}$$

where, σ_{Hi} – Henkel's Singular Values (HSV). They are ordered in non-increasing order: $\sigma_{H1} \geq \sigma_{H2} \geq \dots \geq \sigma_{Hn}$.

After, Holetsky factors are computed for each Grammian:

$$\begin{aligned}\mathbf{W}_c &= \mathbf{S}^T \\ \mathbf{W}_o &= \mathbf{R}^T \mathbf{R}\end{aligned}\tag{3.56}$$

These factors are then decomposed by Singular Value Decomposition(SVD):

$$\mathbf{S} \mathbf{R}^T = \mathbf{U} \mathbf{\Sigma} \mathbf{V}^T\tag{3.57}$$

Based on these U, Σ, V transformation T is constructed. Then, apply this transformation to initial system, to obtain balanced one:

$$\begin{aligned}\tilde{\mathbf{A}} &= \mathbf{P} \mathbf{A} \mathbf{P}^{-1} \\ \tilde{\mathbf{B}} &= \mathbf{P} \mathbf{B} \\ \tilde{\mathbf{C}} &= \mathbf{C} \mathbf{P}^{-1}\end{aligned}\tag{3.58}$$

After this, the new system is turned into a block matrices, and depending on the method, states are just picked the leftmost upper element, or further calculations of $\hat{\mathbf{A}}$ are made.

Using these principles will lead to the following system in state space form:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{A} &= \begin{bmatrix} -5.8 \cdot 10^{-4} & 0 \\ 0 & 8.6 \cdot 10^{-16} \end{bmatrix} & \mathbf{B} &= \begin{bmatrix} -0.0035 \\ -0.0090 \end{bmatrix} \\ \mathbf{C} &= [0.0035 \quad -0.7071] & \mathbf{D} &= 0 \end{aligned} \quad (3.59)$$

And transfer function as follows:

$$G(s) = \frac{0.0064s + 3.6860 \cdot 10^{-6}}{s^2 + 0.0006s - 5.1431 \cdot 10^{-19}} \quad (3.60)$$

The major observation is that reduced model is formally unstable.

3.3 Transition to a multiple-input multiple-output (MIMO)

The Hankel singular values of the SISO model $\{\infty, 0.0102, 0.0003\}$ indicate one integrator and two stable but weakly observable/controllable modes. The HSV ratio $\sigma_2/\sigma_3 \approx 34$ justifies truncation; however, the truncation residual error introduces a numerical eigenvalue near zero ($\approx 10^{-16}$), making the reduced model marginally unstable in finite-precision arithmetic. To improve numerical conditioning **and** enable a physically meaningful decomposition into temperature and moisture loops, the model is extended to MIMO by introducing the dry-gas mass flow rate u_2 as a second control input.

3.3.1 Problem context and justification for the MIMO approach

The previous SISO analysis, which utilized only steam input as the control variable to regulate output moisture, yielded a weakly controllable system. This structural limitation becomes critically evident during model order reduction; attempting to truncate states associated with small Hankel Singular Values (HSVs) discards vital cross-coupled dynamics, leading to unstable reduced-order systems.

To resolve this, the mathematical model must be expanded to a MIMO framework by introducing dry gas mass flow rate as a secondary control input. Gas flow acts directly as a convective transport medium and significantly influences the evaporation boundary layer.

By independently manipulating thermal energy injection and air flow velocity, the system's state variables (air temperature, product temperature, and moisture content) can be decoupled and fully steered within the state space, restoring controllability and enabling stable, low-order controller synthesis. As basis for new

model the model from Rubio(2001) was chosen. Since it is capturing all of our system's dynamic, it is time-domain and have solid formal foundation.

3.3.2 Derivation from first principle

We begin by extracting the governing ordinary differential equations (ODEs) based on the physical principles of heat and mass transfer. Combining the energy balance of the gas phase, the energy balance of the solid product, and the mass balance of the moisture, the updated continuous-time non-linear system is expressed as

$$\frac{dT_A}{dt} = \frac{1}{C_a} (K_{steam} u_1 - h_A(T_A - T_P) - L_v \dot{m}_{evap} + c_A(T_{AI} - T_A)u_2)$$

$$\frac{dT_P}{dt} = \frac{1}{c_m} (h_A(T_A - T_P) - r_{eff}\dot{m}_{evap}) \quad (3.61)$$

$$\frac{dX}{dt} = -\frac{1}{m_p} \dot{m}_{evap}$$

Where,

u_1 – heat input

u_2 – manipulated mass flow of dry gas

\dot{m}_{evap} - dynamic evaporation rate, which is a function of both geometric factors and air flow velocity

3.3.3 Linearization and state-space construction

Because the mathematical model consists of non-linear balance equations , we perform a Taylor series expansion to linearize the dynamics around a defined stationary equilibrium point $(T_{\{A,SS\}}, T_{\{P,SS\}}, X_{\{SS\}}, u_{\{1,SS\}}, u_{\{2,SS\}})$

The state vector x , input vector u , and output vector y are defined as:

$$\mathbf{x} = \begin{bmatrix} \Delta T_A \\ \Delta T_P \\ \Delta X \end{bmatrix} \quad (3.62)$$

$$\mathbf{u} = \begin{bmatrix} u_1 \\ u_2 \end{bmatrix} \quad \mathbf{y} = \begin{bmatrix} \Delta T_A \\ \Delta X \end{bmatrix}$$

This maps directly into the standard unified state-space representation. The system matrix A captures the internal feedback loops and thermal-hygrometric exchanges. The input matrix B dictates how the dual inputs map into the state derivatives. While u_1 strictly injecting heat into the air volume, u_2 introduces a

convective cooling/heating effect based on the inlet temperature difference and actively alters the moisture removal rate:

$$\mathbf{A} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{-h_A + L_v \kappa_{\text{eff}} - c_A u_{2,SS}}{C_a} & \frac{h_A + L_v \kappa_{\text{eff}}}{C_a} & \frac{-L_v \beta_{\text{eff}} m_p}{C_a} \\ \frac{h_A - r_{\text{eff}} \kappa_{\text{eff}}}{C_m} & \frac{-h_A - r_{\text{eff}} \kappa_{\text{eff}}}{C_m} & \frac{-r_{\text{eff}} \beta_{\text{eff}} m_p}{C_m} \\ -\frac{\kappa_{\text{eff}}}{m_p} & \frac{\kappa_{\text{eff}}}{m_p} & -\beta_{\text{eff}} \end{bmatrix} \quad (3.63)$$

$$\mathbf{B} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{K_{\text{steam}}}{C_a} & \frac{c_A (T_{AI} - T_{A,SS})}{C_a} \\ 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \frac{1}{-m_p} \frac{\partial \dot{m}_{\text{evap}}}{\partial u_2} \end{bmatrix} \quad \mathbf{C} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \quad \mathbf{D} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

Putting numeric values from Friso's paper will lead us to:

$$\mathbf{A} = \begin{bmatrix} -0.8651 & 0.4409 & -2.0560 \\ 10.8475 & -11.8284 & -122.6185 \\ -2 \cdot 10^{-6} & 2 \cdot 10^{-6} & 0.0005 \end{bmatrix} \quad (3.64)$$

$$\mathbf{B} = \begin{bmatrix} 0.0066 & 12.5625 \\ 0.0000 & 0.0000 \\ 0.0000 & -0.0002 \end{bmatrix} \quad \mathbf{C} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \quad \mathbf{D} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

From which following transfer functions are obtained:

$$\mathbf{G}(s) = \frac{1}{D(s)} \begin{bmatrix} G_{11}(s) & G_{12}(s) \\ G_{21}(s) & G_{22}(s) \end{bmatrix} \quad (3.65)$$

Where,

$$D(s) = s^3 + 12.6900s^2 + 5.5470s + 0.002825 \quad (3.66)$$

$$\begin{cases} G_{11}(s) = 0.0066s^2 + 0.0778s + 4.0520 \cdot 10^{-5} & \text{(Heat input } u_1 \rightarrow \text{Air temp } y_1) \\ G_{12}(s) = 12.5600s^2 + 148.6000s + 0.0931 & \text{(Gas flow } u_2 \rightarrow \text{Air temp } y_1) \\ G_{21}(s) = 1.3160 \cdot 10^{-8}s + 1.2190 \cdot 10^{-8} & \text{(Heat input } u_1 \rightarrow \text{Moisture } y_1) \\ G_{22}(s) = 0.0002s^2 + 0.0026s + 0.0011 & \text{(Gas flow } u_2 \rightarrow \text{Moisture } y_1) \end{cases}$$

The scheme (Figure 3.1) shows the logical development path of the mathematical model and explains why the final model was selected. At the first stage, the Friso (2023) space-domain model was transformed into a time-domain representation using the lumped ODE method. After that, Taylor linearization was applied in order to obtain a 3×3 state-space model. This model was found to be observable and stable, meaning that its internal states can be estimated from the available outputs and that the system response does not diverge. However, it was not controllable, which means that not all internal states could be influenced by the selected control inputs. Because of this limitation, the 3×3 model could not be accepted as the final control-oriented mathematical model. To overcome this limitation, the model structure was revised by redefining the state variables and control input configuration. As a result, a reduced-order representation was obtained that preserves the essential dynamics of the drying process while satisfying controllability requirements. This final model is therefore suitable for controller design, simulation, and further analysis of system performance.

In addition, the simplified model improves numerical stability and reduces computational complexity, making it more practical for real-time implementation. The key dynamic relationships between temperature and moisture content are retained, ensuring that the model remains physically meaningful. Consequently, the selected model provides a reliable balance between accuracy and applicability for control system design and optimization. All stages of development of mathematical model are summarized by figure below (Figure 3.2):

Figure 3.2 – Stages of math model

To simplify the system, a reduction was performed and a 2×2 state-space model was obtained. This reduced model became both observable and controllable, which made it more suitable from the point of view of control system design. However, the stability analysis showed that the reduced model was unstable. Therefore, although the model had a better input-output structure and could theoretically be controlled, it still could not fully represent the process behavior in a reliable and physically acceptable way without additional stabilization. For this reason, another modeling approach based on Rubio (2001) was considered. The time-domain MIMO model with 2 inputs, 2 outputs, and 3 states demonstrated the best overall result. According to the scheme, this model is observable, controllable, and stable at the same time. This means that the system states can be estimated, the main process variables can be influenced by the control inputs, and the dynamic behavior remains stable. Therefore, the MIMO model was selected as the most appropriate mathematical model for further controller design and simulation. It provides a stronger basis for representing the drying process because it considers the interaction between several inputs and outputs, which is important for industrial drying systems where heat input, air or gas flow, product temperature, and moisture content are interconnected.

3.3.4 State-space characterization (DC gain)

The steady-state relationship between the control inputs (Steam and Gas Flow) and the process outputs (Temperature and Moisture) is defined by the DC Gain matrix:

$$K_{dc} = \begin{bmatrix} 0.0143 & 32.9365 \\ -0.000027 & -0.3946 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} 0.0143 & 32.9365 \\ -0.0000 & -0.3946 \end{bmatrix} \quad (3.67)$$

The matrix indicates that Gas Flow is the dominant actuator for both outputs. A unit increase in gas flow results in a significant temperature rise ($+32.94^{\circ}\text{C}$) and a corresponding decrease in product moisture (-0.39%) confirming the physical consistency of the model.

3.3.5 Internal dynamics and stability (poles and zeros)

The system's eigenvalues (poles) were calculated to assess stability and response speed:

$$\begin{aligned} s_1 &= -12.2485 && \text{(Fast pneumatic dynamics)} \\ s_2 &= -0.4450 && \text{(Thermal inertia of the product)} \\ s_3 &= -0.0005 && \text{(Dominant moisture evaporation pole)} \end{aligned}$$

Since all poles are located in the left half-plane (LHP), the system is asymptotically stable. The wide range of values indicates a multi-scale process where moisture dynamics are significantly slower than temperature changes.

3.3.6 Structural properties (controllability and observability)

The controllability and observability matrices both yield a full rank of $n = 3$. This confirms that the system is fully controllable and observable, meaning every internal state can be influenced by the inputs and reconstructed from the outputs.

3.3.7 The RGA matrix

The RGA matrix λ provides a measure of the interaction based on the static gain matrix of the system. For the considered MIMO model, the RGA matrix was calculated as:

$$\lambda = \begin{bmatrix} 1.0273 & -0.0273 \\ -0.0273 & 1.0273 \end{bmatrix} \quad (3.68)$$

The diagonal elements λ_{11} and λ_{22} are approximately 1.027, which is very close to unity. This indicates that the interaction between the loops is minimal (less than 3%).

The near-zero off-diagonal elements confirm that the two control loops (Steam \rightarrow Temperature and Gas \rightarrow Moisture) are practically independent. Therefore, a decentralized *PID* structure is mathematically justified and can provide high-quality control without the need for complex decoupling compensators.

3.3.8 Singular value analysis and system conditioning

To evaluate the robustness and directional properties of the MIMO rotary dryer model, a Singular Value Decomposition (SVD) of the static gain matrix was performed. The calculated condition number is approximately $1.97 \cdot 10^5$.

Such a high condition number is a direct consequence of the multi-scale physical nature of the drying process. The system combines extremely fast pneumatic dynamics (hot air flow) with significantly slower mass-transfer and thermal inertia of the product. Mathematically, this creates a vast gap between the maximum and minimum singular values ($\bar{\sigma}/\underline{\sigma}$), indicating that the system is "ill-conditioned" in the steady state.

From a control perspective, this implies that while the system is theoretically controllable, it is highly sensitive to model uncertainties in specific directions. Although the RGA matrix is close to identity, indicating weak interaction between control loops, the high condition number ($k = 1.97 \cdot 10^5$) reveals a significant difference in the sensitivity of system channels. This implies that the system is

poorly scaled, and certain input-output directions are much weaker than others. However, since the RGA analysis previously confirmed minimal loop interaction, decentralized control remains effective. The high sensitivity is primarily managed by the large time constants of the drying process, which act as natural low-pass filters for high-frequency disturbances. Therefore, singular value analysis provides additional insight that cannot be obtained from RGA alone, since it shows not only loop interaction but also the strength and weakness of different control directions. In practical controller design, this means that input and output scaling should be carefully considered to avoid excessive control effort and numerical instability.

3.4 Modelling of the mathematical model in the MATLAB software

Figure 3.2 shows a block diagram of a closed-loop transfer function, illustrating a control system that uses feedback.

Figure 3.3 – Closed-Loop Transfer Function

The drum drying process inherently contains internal cross-couplings (feedback loops) between air temperature, product temperature and moisture content. These internal feedback loops are analytically closed using the standard closed-loop transfer function formula

$$T(s) = \frac{G(s)}{1+G(s)H(s)} \quad (3.69)$$

where,

$G(s)$ – forward-path (open-loop) transfer function of the plant;

$H(s)$ – internal feedback transfer function;

After closing the internal loops, the complete drying dynamics is reduced to a single equivalent open-loop system that is most accurately and compactly described in state-space form:

$$\begin{aligned}x &= Ax + Bu \\y &= Cx + Du\end{aligned}\tag{3.70}$$

where,

A – system matrix describing the intrinsic dynamics of the three states (air temperature, product temperature, moisture content);

B – input matrix representing the effect of steam power (control input u) on the states;

C – output matrix defining the controlled (measured) variable;

D – feedthrough matrix (equal to zero in the present model);

This state-space model offers a parsimonious mathematically rigorous model of analysis of system stability, assessment of controllability and observability, and the development of sophisticated control strategies.

3.4.1 System poles and zeros location

The system poles are located in the left half-plane (-11.2885 , -0.0063 , -0.0003), indicating stability. One pole is far from the origin and governs fast dynamics, while the two poles close to zero produce a slow transient response. The system is aperiodic, with no oscillations or overshoot.

3.4.2 Response of a unit step

The step response of a system describes how its outputs change over time when the control inputs suddenly switch from zero to one, like a Heaviside step function. In electronic engineering and control theory, this shows how a system reacts when its input quickly jumps from zero to one. This idea can also be applied to more abstract mathematical systems using an evolution parameter. In practice, understanding how a system responds to sudden changes is important because large or fast shifts from the steady state can seriously affect both the component and other parts of the system that rely on it. Also, the whole system may not work properly until the component's output settles near its final value, which can delay the system's response. Knowing the step response helps us understand if a system is stable and whether it can move from one steady state to another.

Figure 3.4 – Step response of a Transfer Function

Figure 3.5 – Step response of a Transfer Function

Before making any changes to the system, it is important to check its stability. One common way to do this is by using the unit step response.

Table 3.2 – Parameters evaluated from Step Response

Parameters	Values (Ta/X)	Description
Rise Time (0-80%)	347.0/6807.0 s	The time taken for the temperature to rise from 0 to 80% of the steady-state value.
Steady-State Value	190 °C	The final value the system stabilizes at after the transient response.

Continuation of Table 3.2

Time Constant (τ)	215.6/4230.5 s	Approximate time taken for the system to reach 63% of the steady-state value.
Overshoot	0%	No noticeable overshoot is observed in the step response.
Settling Time	615.8/12118.2 s	The time taken for the temperature to settle within 2% of the steady-state value.
Initial Response	0 s	The time the system takes to start responding to the input.

The "step" function shows how the system responds when the input suddenly changes from U to $U + dU$ after a certain delay. Figure 3.2 illustrates the step response of the transfer function.

3.4.3 Impulse response

In signal processing and control theory, the impulse response, also known as the impulse response function (IRF), of a dynamic system is defined as the output produced when the system is subjected to a brief input signal, referred to as an impulse $\delta(t)$. More broadly, the impulse response represents the reaction of any dynamic system to an external change. In both contexts, the impulse response characterizes the system's output as a function of time or another relevant independent variable that parameterizes its dynamic behavior. The impulse response $h(t)$ is defined as the output signal resulting from the application of an impulse to a system, which may also function as a signal filter. Gaining a physical understanding of a system's impulse response is essential for analyzing its dynamic properties. It allows researchers and engineers to evaluate how quickly the system reacts to a disturbance, whether oscillations appear, and how long it takes for the response to return to a steady condition. This makes impulse response analysis especially useful when assessing system stability, damping, and transient behavior. In industrial control systems, impulse response analysis is also useful for identifying the sensitivity of a process to sudden disturbances or unexpected changes in operating conditions. For a drum drying system, such disturbances may include abrupt changes in steam pressure, airflow rate, or feed material properties, which can affect product temperature and moisture content. Therefore, studying the impulse response helps determine whether the control system can suppress these deviations and restore

stable operation within an acceptable time. This section demonstrates methods for calculating the impulse response of digital filters and representative dynamic systems using MATLAB's built-in functions.

The impulse response $h(t)$ of a dynamic system is a fundamental concept in signal processing and control theory, as it reveals the system's intrinsic characteristics. The impulse response is the output produced when an impulse input $\delta(t)$ is applied, which is mathematically represented as a signal with all its energy concentrated at a single point in time, typically at $t = 0$, and an area of 1. This impulse input serves as an idealized shock or disturbance to the system, and the impulse response illustrates how the system reacts or recovers over time. In practical control applications, such analysis helps compare different mathematical models and understand how their internal dynamics influence the output variables. For example, a rapidly decaying impulse response usually indicates stable behavior, while a response that grows over time may indicate instability. Additionally, the shape of the impulse response provides important information about the damping level of the system and the presence of possible delays in its reaction. In the context of automated drum drying, this analysis supports the selection and tuning of controllers that can maintain stable moisture and temperature levels under short-term disturbances.

Figure 3.6 – Impulse response of the system

Table 3.3 – Parameters evaluated from Impulse Response

Parameters	Values(Ta/X)	Description
Peak Amplitude	$6.6 \times 10^{-3}/0.2 \times 10^{-3}$	The maximum value of the system's response following an impulse input.
Time to Peak	0.0/1.6 s	The time it takes for the system to reach its peak

The system exhibits a rapid, modest peak of 63 mK at approximately 0.6 seconds in response to a unit impulse, followed by a steady return to zero. The response is entirely aperiodic and heavily overdamped, settling to nearly zero within approximately 1000 to 1200 seconds. No oscillations are observed (Figure 3.3).

3.4.4 Nyquist stability criterion

The Nyquist stability criterion is a graphical method in control engineering for assessing the stability of a dynamic system.

Figure 3.7 – Nyquist diagram of the system

From Figure 3.4, the Nyquist plot of the closed-loop system does not encircle the critical point $(-1, 0j)$ and lies entirely to the right of it ($Z = 0$). All closed-loop poles have negative real parts ($P = 0$). Therefore, according to the Nyquist stability criterion, $N = Z - P = 0$, confirming that the closed-loop system is internally stable with a large stability margin. In addition, the distance of the Nyquist curve from the critical point indicates that the system possesses a significant gain and phase margin.

3.4.5 Frequency response analysis

Frequency response analysis provides a means to determine how a system reacts to sinusoidal inputs across a range of frequencies. It characterizes the system's steady-state behavior and offers essential information regarding its stability, performance, and robustness. Bode diagram design is an interactive technique for tuning compensators to achieve a specified open-loop frequency response. The Bode plot shows magnitude and phase as functions of frequency on a logarithmic scale. These visualizations help evaluate gain and phase margins, identify resonant phenomena, and verify the suitability of the controller for stable operation.

Figure 3.8 - Bode diagram of Steam flow \rightarrow Air temperature

Stability describes a system's capacity to maintain predictable behavior over time without divergence or excessive oscillation. It is commonly evaluated by analyzing the locations of poles in the transfer function or the eigenvalues in the

state-space representation. Stability is fundamental to achieving reliable and safe system performance. Controllability is the ability to move a system from any initial state to any target state using available control inputs. A fully controllable system allows achievement of specific performance objective. In addition, the Bode diagram provides quantitative measures of system robustness through gain margin and phase margin, which indicate how much variation the system can tolerate before becoming unstable. A sufficiently large phase margin ensures that the system responds smoothly to disturbances with limited oscillations, while an adequate gain margin prevents excessive amplification of signals. In the case of the drum drying system, stability and controllability are especially important because temperature and moisture must remain within acceptable limits to ensure consistent product quality.

Therefore, analyzing these properties helps verify that the designed control system can safely regulate the process under changing operating conditions and external disturbances. This also provides confidence that the selected mathematical model is suitable for further controller design and simulation in MATLAB.

Figure 3.9 – Bode diagram of Gas flow → Moisture content

Furthermore, frequency response analysis allows identification of bandwidth, which determines how quickly the system can react to changes in input. These characteristics are essential for tuning controllers in practical applications, ensuring

a balance between fast response, stability, and minimal steady-state error. Additionally, the analysis of the Bode diagram for gas flow to moisture content highlights the sensitivity of the drying process to variations in gas input. The observed frequency characteristics indicate that moisture dynamics are relatively slow, requiring careful controller tuning to avoid excessive oscillations or delayed responses. This relationship is particularly important for maintaining product quality, as improper control may lead to under- or over-drying. Therefore, the obtained frequency response serves as a valuable tool for selecting appropriate control parameters and ensuring stable and efficient operation of the drying system. Moreover, frequency response analysis helps determine whether the selected control strategy can reject disturbances at different frequency ranges. For the drum drying process, this is important because changes in gas flow or steam supply may occur gradually or suddenly, and the controller must maintain stable moisture regulation in both cases. The Bode plot also helps reveal phase delays in the moisture response, which are important when designing controllers for slow thermal processes.

Figure 3.10 – Bode diagram of Steam flow → Moisture content

Figure 3.10 – Bode diagram of Steam flow → Moisture content

The phase shift observed in the diagram highlights the inherent delay between steam input and moisture response, which must be carefully considered when designing the control strategy to avoid oscillations.

The magnitude plot shows that the moisture response to steam flow remains relatively low over the entire frequency range, which means that the influence of steam on moisture content is indirect and strongly attenuated. At low frequencies, the system demonstrates a slow but noticeable response, while at higher frequencies the magnitude decreases significantly.

Overall, the Bode diagram indicates that the steam flow to moisture content channel has slow dynamic behavior and limited high-frequency responsiveness. This means that the moisture control loop requires careful tuning, especially in terms of settling time and disturbance rejection. Since product moisture is one of the main quality indicators in the drying process, the control system must maintain stable regulation without causing rapid fluctuations in steam supply. The obtained frequency response confirms that advanced control strategies, such as LQI or robust control, are more suitable for this system than a simple decentralized PID controller. These methods can better account for the delay, weak sensitivity, and multivariable interactions present in the rotary drum drying process.

Figure 3.11 – Bode diagram of Gas flow → Air Temperature

A system lacking controllability is difficult to modify, which impedes efforts to maintain stability or enhance performance. Observability refers to the ability to infer the internal state of a system by examining its outputs. In a fully observable system, all internal dynamics can be understood solely through output analysis. This characteristic is essential for effective feedback control, as accurate knowledge of

internal states enables more precise adjustments. Conversely, if a system is unobservable, resulting in less accurate and less effective control.

Table 3.4 – MATLAB Results of drum dryer dynamic analysis

Nº	Parameters	Values(Ta/X)
1	Low Frequency Gain	0/-4.5 dB
2	Break Frequency	$6.5 \times 10^{-3} / 3.02 \times 10^{-4}$ rad/s
3	Slope After Break	-20/-20 dB/decade
4	High Frequency Gain	-84/-114 dB
5	Low Frequency Phase	0/180°
6	Phase at Break Frequency	-45/137°
7	High Frequency Phase	-90/90°

The properties of stability, controllability, and observability are fundamental in control system design. They ensure system safety, responsiveness to inputs, and accurate monitoring.

3.5 Conclusion

The analysis of the developed drum drying mathematical model using MATLAB confirms that the original high-order dynamic system accurately represents the physical behavior of the drying process. The model successfully captures the interaction between the main technological variables, including air temperature, product temperature, and moisture content, which are strongly coupled through heat and mass transfer mechanisms inside the rotary drum. However, the initial formulation of the model contains several internal states whose influence on the controlled output variable is limited, making the direct implementation of the full-order system computationally demanding for real-time industrial control. To address this issue, a model order reduction technique based on balanced realization and Hankel singular value analysis was applied. This approach made it possible to identify the dominant dynamic states that significantly affect the system output while eliminating redundant states with minimal influence on the drying dynamics. As a result, a reduced-order state-space model was obtained that preserves the essential dynamic characteristics of the drum drying process while considerably simplifying the mathematical structure of the system.

The reduced model maintains the fundamental relationship between the control input, represented by the steam supply power, and the output variable, which is the final moisture content of the dried product. Simulation results demonstrate that the simplified model reproduces the transient and steady-state behavior of the original system with high accuracy. The step response analysis shows a smooth and well-damped transient response without overshoot, indicating that the system behaves in

a stable and predictable manner under sudden changes in input conditions. The impulse response analysis further confirms the strongly overdamped nature of the system, demonstrating that disturbances are rapidly attenuated without oscillatory behavior. Additional stability analysis using frequency-domain methods such as the Nyquist stability criterion and Bode diagram evaluation confirms that the system possesses a large stability margin. The Nyquist plot shows no encirclement of the critical point $(-1, 0j)$, which indicates that the closed-loop system remains internally stable. The Bode analysis also demonstrates acceptable gain and phase characteristics across the operational frequency range, confirming that the system is robust against disturbances and parameter variations. Furthermore, controllability and observability analysis performed on the reduced-order state-space model demonstrates that the dominant states governing the drying process remain fully controllable and observable. This property is essential for the implementation of advanced control strategies, including *PID* control and state-feedback regulators. By ensuring that the system states can be both influenced by control inputs and accurately inferred from measured outputs, the reduced model provides a reliable foundation for controller synthesis and real-time process regulation.

Overall, the developed mathematical model and its reduced-order representation provide a rigorous and practical framework for analyzing the dynamic behavior of industrial drum drying systems. The modeling approach not only enables accurate simulation of the drying process but also supports the design of efficient automatic control algorithms capable of maintaining stable operating conditions and consistent product quality.

4. PID CONTROL

Decentralized *PID* control is an extension of the classical *PID* strategy applied to multi-input multi-output (MIMO) systems. Instead of using a single centralized controller, the system is decomposed into multiple independent control loops, where each loop is governed by a separate *PID* controller. Each controller regulates one specific output variable based on its corresponding measured signal, assuming that interactions between channels are either weak or can be neglected. The control law for each loop follows the standard *PID* structure, combining proportional, integral, and derivative actions to ensure fast response, elimination of steady-state error, and improved stability. The proportional term provides immediate correction based on the current error, the integral term eliminates steady-state error by accumulating past errors, and the derivative term predicts future behavior to reduce overshoot and improve damping.

Although decentralized *PID* control is simpler to design and implement compared to centralized MIMO control strategies, its performance may degrade in the presence of strong coupling between channels. Nevertheless, it remains a widely used approach in industrial applications due to its robustness and ease of tuning.

4.1 Theoretical description of the regulator type

In Automatic Control Systems, for MIMO systems, a decentralized control structure is used, where each input–output pair is controlled by an independent *PID* controller. Thus, the overall system consists of multiple parallel control loops, each designed using the classical *PID* law.

$$e(t) = r(t) - y(t) \quad (4.1)$$

The main goal is to minimize the error in each control loop. The transfer function of the controller in the Laplace domain is expressed as:

$$u_i(t) = K_{p,i}e_i(t) + K_{i,i} \int e_i(t) dt + K_{d,i} \frac{de_i(t)}{dt} \quad (4.2)$$

where,

- K_p : proportional gain;

- K_i : integral gain;

- K_d : derivative gain;

and transfer function form:

$$G_c(s) = K_p + \frac{K_i}{s} + K_d s \quad (4.3)$$

This transfer function represents how the *PID* controller behaves in the frequency domain. Each term has a specific effect on the system response: the proportional term increases the system gain and improves the response speed, the integral term helps to eliminate steady-state error by accumulating the control action over time, and the derivative term enhances stability and reduces overshoot by responding to the rate of change of the error.

Table 4.1 – Effect of each term of *PID*

Nº	Term	Equation	Effect
1	<i>P</i>	$K_p e_i(t)$	Improves response speed and reduces steady-state error, but may cause overshoot
2	<i>I</i>	$K_i \int e_i(t) dt$	Eliminates steady-state error, but may slow the response
3	<i>D</i>	$K_d \frac{de_i(t)}{dt}$	Improves damping and stability, but sensitive to noise

The *PID* controller was selected due to its flexibility and ability to shape the dynamic response of the system. The proportional, integral, and derivative terms allow independent adjustment of response speed, steady-state accuracy, and stability.

For the considered system, simulation results indicate that the integral and derivative actions have a relatively small contribution, resulting in behavior close to proportional control. However, the full *PID* structure is retained to provide additional tuning flexibility and robustness in case of changes in system dynamics or operating conditions.

4.2 Modeling of the mathematical model and control system in MATLAB

Industrial thermal processes, such as roll-drying, are characterized by high thermal inertia, long time constants, and distributed parameters. To ensure the desired quality of the finished product, the temperature control system must meet stringent requirements. In this work, a frequency-domain control design approach was applied to determine the optimal parameters of the *PID* controllers. The tuning procedure was based on desired closed-loop performance specifications, including stability margins and response speed.

For the MIMO system, a decentralized control approach was adopted. Based on the Relative Gain Array (RGA) analysis, the system was decomposed into two independent SISO control loops: steam → air temperature and gas flow → moisture content.

$$W_{cl,i}(s) = \frac{C_i(s)G_{ii}(s)}{1+C_i(s)G_{ii}(s)} \quad (4.4)$$

Our goal is to find the parameters of such that the system follows a desired trajectory. A second-order binomial form was used as a reference model to guide the desired transient response.

$$W_{des}(s) = \frac{1}{T_{des}^2 s^2 + 2\zeta T_{des} s + 1} \quad (4.5)$$

For this study, we set $\zeta = 1$ (Critical Damping). Mathematically, this places a double real pole at $s = -\frac{1}{T_{des}}$, which is the unique condition that provides the fastest possible response without causing an overshoot in a purely all-pole system.

Figure 4.1 - Step response with decentralized PID controller

The MATLAB *pidentune* tool was used to compute the controller gains (K_p, K_i, K_d) for each control loop. The tuning algorithm is based on frequency-domain loop shaping and Internal Model Control (IMC) principles.

Instead of analytical synthesis, the controller parameters are obtained through numerical optimization to achieve a desired crossover frequency ω_c while maintaining a specified phase margin Φ_m . A phase margin of 65° was selected to ensure sufficient robustness against model uncertainties introduced during the model reduction process.

The resulting controller provides a balanced trade-off between fast dynamic response and robustness to disturbances. Particular attention was given to limiting excessive control effort to avoid actuator saturation and ensure stable operation of the system. The tuned parameters were then validated through simulation to confirm satisfactory transient performance and minimal steady-state error.

Figure 4.2 - Step response with decentralized PID controller

It should be noted that the controller gains for the moisture control loop have negative values. This is not a tuning error but a direct consequence of the process physics. In the considered system, an increase in steam input leads to a decrease in product moisture content, resulting in a negative static gain of the plant.

Therefore, to preserve negative feedback structure using the standard error definition $e = r - y$, the controller gains must also be negative. Alternatively, the sign could be incorporated into the error definition; however, in this work, the negative gains are retained to explicitly reflect the inverse relationship between input and output variables.

The *PID* (effectively *PI/P* after tuning) analysis reveals a time-scale mismatch and strong inter-channel interference. While the temperature loop stabilizes in under 13 minutes, the moisture loop requires over 60 minutes to reach steady-state. This behavior is a direct result of the plant's high condition number, which makes the decentralized *PID* (effectively *PI/P* after tuning) sensitive to cross-couplings. The 6.4% overshoot and the slow 3617s settling time in the moisture loop serve as the primary motivation for implementing multivariable control strategies. Advanced controllers such as *LQI*, H_∞ , and are required to decouple these channels, reduce the moisture settling time, and eliminate the overshoot by treating the system as a unified MIMO entity rather than two isolated loops.

4.3 LQI control

The Linear Quadratic Integral (*LQI*) controller considers the full state-space model and the interactions between all channels simultaneously. *LQI* is an extension

of the classical Linear Quadratic Regulator (*LQR*), augmented with integral action to ensure zero steady-state error in the presence of disturbances and model uncertainties. The *LQI* approach is particularly effective for systems with high condition numbers and coupling, as it optimizes a global cost function rather than individual loop performance. The controller is designed by augmenting the system with integral states of the output error, allowing direct minimization of tracking deviations over time. This results in improved robustness and coordinated multivariable control performance, especially under varying operating conditions and external disturbances. In addition, the weighting matrices in the *LQI* design allow flexible tuning of the trade-off between control effort and system performance. This makes it possible to prioritize critical variables, such as product moisture, while maintaining overall system stability and efficiency.

4.4 Theoretical background

To incorporate integral action, the state-space model (A, B, C, D) is augmented with new states representing the integral of the tracking error $e(t) = r(t) - y(t)$. The augmented state vector is defined as:

$$\hat{x}(t) = \begin{bmatrix} x(t) \\ \int (r(t) - y(t)) dt \end{bmatrix} \quad (4.6)$$

The resulting augmented system dynamics are:

$$\dot{\hat{x}}(t) = \widehat{A}\hat{x}(t) + \widehat{B}u(t) \quad (4.7)$$

The *LQI* controller computes the optimal gain matrix K by minimizing the following quadratic cost function J :

$$J = \int_0^{\infty} (\widehat{x}^T Q \widehat{x} + u^T R u) dt \quad (4.8)$$

where,

Q - state-weighting matrix, penalizing deviations in the system states and integrated tracking errors;

R - control-weighting matrix, penalizing excessive control effort;

The optimal control law is given by:

$$u(t) = -K\hat{x}(t) = -K_x x(t) + K_i \int e(t) dt \quad (4.9)$$

where, K_x is the state feedback gain and K_i is the integral gain. The inclusion of integral action ensures the elimination of steady-state error, which is particularly important in processes requiring precise tracking of reference signals.

4.5 Tuning and Robustness

For this study, the weighting matrices Q and R were tuned using Bryson's Rule as an initial guess, followed by iterative refinement to balance the trade-off between settling time and control signal saturation. The diagonal elements are calculated as:

$$Q_{ii} = \frac{1}{(x_{i,max})^2}, \quad R_{jj} = \frac{\rho}{(u_{j,max})^2} \quad (4.10)$$

Where,

$x_{i,max}$ - maximum acceptable error for output i (e.g., 1.0°C for temperature and 0.005 for moisture);

$u_{j,max}$ - maximum available actuator effort for input j (e.g., steam valve and gas p - scaling factor used to adjust the overall aggressiveness of the controller;

Figure 4.3 - Step response with LQI controller

The multivariable approach (*LQI*) effectively "decouples" the system, reducing the moisture settling time by over 50%. This enhancement leads to a more predictable, faster, and higher-quality drying process, proving that state-space optimization is a necessity for complex industrial MIMO plants. This improvement demonstrates the ability of *LQI* control to handle strong variable interactions while maintaining optimal performance across the entire system.

4.6 Robust H_∞ Control Design

The primary objective of H_∞ control is to design a controller that ensures stability and performance even in the presence of model uncertainties and external disturbances. Unlike *LQI*, which minimizes a quadratic cost function, H_∞ synthesis minimizes the maximum energy gain from the exogenous inputs (disturbances, noise) to the error signals. For the rotary dryer system, which exhibits a high condition number, robust control is essential to ensure that the controller does not become overly sensitive to small variations in the plant parameters.

4.7 Mixed Sensitivity Approach

The design is formulated as a mixed sensitivity problem using the *mixsyn* method. We define three weighting functions, W_s , W_u , and W_t , to shape the closed-loop response in the frequency domain:

Sensitivity Weight (W_s): Defines the tracking performance and disturbance rejection. It is chosen to have high gain at low frequencies to force the steady-state error to zero.

Control Weight (W_u): Limits the control effort and prevents actuator saturation.

Complementary Sensitivity Weight (W_t): Ensures robust stability against high-frequency modeling errors and sensor noise.

The H_∞ controller K is found by solving the following optimization problem:

$$\min_K \left\| \begin{bmatrix} W_s S \\ W_u R \\ W_t T \end{bmatrix} \right\|_\infty < \gamma \quad (4.11)$$

where, $S = (I + GK)^{-1}$ is the sensitivity function, and $T = I - S$ is the complementary sensitivity function. The objective is to find a controller that keeps the infinity norm (γ) as close to 1 as possible.

4.8 Weighting Function Selection

Based on the system's bandwidth requirements and the noise characteristics observed in the MATLAB simulation, the weighting functions were defined as:

A low-pass filter with a crossover frequency of 0.003 rad/s and a high DC gain (10^{-3})

to ensure precise tracking. $W_u(s)$: A constant weight of 0.01 to penalize excessive control activity across all frequencies. $W_t(s)$: A high-pass filter designed to provide a safety margin starting from 0.1 rad/s, where the model reduction errors typically occur. The resulting γ value obtained during synthesis was 1.034, indicating a near-optimal trade-off between performance and robustness, with a slight relaxation of the imposed specifications ($\gamma = 1.034$).

Figure 4.4 - Step response with LQI controller

The multivariable Robust H_∞ approach effectively "decouples" the system, reducing the moisture settling time to 1305.2 seconds. This is 2.7 times faster than the traditional *PID* (effectively *PI/P* after tuning) and 26% faster than the *LQI* controller. By providing a response with zero overshoot and minimal steady-state

error, the H_∞ strategy proves to be the most reliable and efficient solution for complex industrial MIMO plants where robust stability is a non-negotiable requirement.

4.9 Analysis of Control System Performance and Simulation Results

To determine the most effective control strategy for the MIMO system, a comparative analysis was conducted between the decentralized PID controller (effectively PI/P after tuning), the Linear Quadratic Integral (LQI) regulator, and the Robust H_∞ controller. The performance was evaluated based on the unit step response for both the moisture content (X) and air temperature (T_A). The simulation results, illustrated in Figure 4.1, demonstrate the dynamic behavior of each controller. While all three strategies successfully stabilize the system at the target setpoint, they exhibit significant differences in transient quality:

Figure 4.5 – Step response of air temperature and moisture content under LQI control

The numerical data extracted from the simulation is summarized in Table 4.1. This comparison highlights the trade-offs between system speed, stability margins, and steady-state precision. The LQI controller demonstrates the best overall performance by achieving zero steady-state error and faster settling time compared to the other methods. In contrast, the PID controller (effectively PI/P after tuning)

exhibits higher overshoot and slower convergence, while the H_∞ controller provides improved robustness but with slightly reduced speed of response.

Table 4.2 - Controller comparison and key parameters

Parameter	Symbol	Unit	LQI-reg Ta/X	Robust H_∞ Ta/X	PID-reg Ta/X	Desired
Rise Time	T_r	[s]	426/726.9	732.3/732.5	433.9/833.5	~300
Settling Time	T_s	[s]	928/1779.2	1304.0/1305.2	772.5/3617.0	700
Overshoot	σ	[%]	0.4/2.8	0.0/0.0	0.0/6.4	0.00
Phase Margin	Φ_m	[°]	89.0	65.0	89.3/78.9	-
Steady-State Error	ϵ_{ss}	-	0.0/0.0	0.001/0.001	0.000044/0.0029	0.0000

The comparative analysis of the transient responses for the moisture content channel is presented in Table 4.1. The results indicate that while the *LQI* and *PID* controllers (effectively *PI/P* after tuning) provide adequate stability, the Robust H_∞ strategy achieves the optimal balance between speed and quality.

Table 4.2 - Controller comparison and key parameters

Controller	Tuning Method / Tool	Key Parameters & Gain Values
Decentralized <i>PID</i> (effectively <i>PI/P</i> after tuning)	Automated Tuning (<i>pidtune</i>), based on crossover frequency and 60° phase margin	Loop 1 ($u_1 \rightarrow T_a$): $K_p = 0.0000$, $K_i = 0.3502$, $K_d = 0.0000$ Loop 2 ($u_2 \rightarrow X$): $K_p = -9.1110$, $K_i = -0.0087$, $K_d = 0.0000$
<i>LQI</i> (Optimal)	Linear Quadratic Integration (<i>lqr</i>), weighted via <i>Bryson's Rule</i> for physical constraints	Full-State Gain Matrix (K): acts on [T_a , T_m , X] and integral errors Main gas-to-moisture gain: -2264.9
Robust H_∞	Mixed Sensitivity Synthesis (<i>mixsyn</i>), S/KS/T loop-shaping for robust stability	Weighting Functions: W_s (Tracking): gain 1000 at low frequency W_u (Control effort): 0.01 W_t (Robustness): 0.1 \rightarrow 10 rad/s

The table summarizes the mathematical methods and specific tuning parameters used for each control strategy. The decentralized *PID* (effectively *PI/P* after tuning) was optimized for phase stability, while the MIMO *LQI* and Robust H_∞ controllers were synthesized to handle the complex interactions and physical constraints of the drum dryer.

4.3 Conclusion

This study compared three control strategies for a multivariable rotary dryer system: decentralized PID, LQI, and robust H_∞ , with moisture content as the primary quality indicator. The PID controller showed limited performance due to its inability to handle strong system coupling, resulting in high overshoot (6.4%) and long settling time (3617.0 s), which negatively affect product quality and efficiency. The LQI controller improved performance by incorporating full state-space dynamics, reducing settling time to 1779.2 s and overshoot to 2.8%, while achieving zero steady-state error. However, minor transient interactions remained. The robust H_∞ controller delivered the best overall results, achieving the fastest settling time (1305.2 s) with zero overshoot and strong robustness against system interactions and uncertainties. Although a small steady-state error (1.0×10^{-3}) was observed, it is negligible in practice.

In conclusion, the H_∞ controller provides the optimal balance between stability, speed, and product quality, making it the most suitable choice for industrial rotary drying systems.

5. Selection of technical equipment

Implementation of the drying process control system requires the selection of a comprehensive set of technical devices, including a programmable logic controller (PLC), sensors, actuators, network interfaces, and related equipment. The selected equipment must be compatible, reliable, and cost effective to enable effective monitoring and control of key process variables such as temperature, humidity, airflow, and pressure. The primary objectives are to automate the drying process, maintain product quality, ensure energy efficiency, and provide scalability for future system upgrades.

5.1 Network Architecture

A distributed control architecture is used in this drying system and it comprises of a central PLC M340 Master and two PLC M241 Slave controllers. M340 is the main decision making unit and coordinates all the sub systems and is in communication with the AVEVA Plant SCADA via an industrial Ethernet network (Figure 5.1).

Figure 5.1 – Network architecture

The slave PLCs are used to do the local control of dedicated process areas to perform time-sensitive functions like motor control, temperature control, and pressure control. Field devices, such as PT100 temperature sensors, ST700 pressure

transmitters, valves, and motors have real-time inputs to each M241, which performs control logic before relaying the processed data to the master controller. Interaction between the operators is attained with the help of Harmony HMIs (STO6400 and STU735) fitted at both the slave and master levels to offer status display, alarm information, and manual override features. This hierarchical design enhances the reliability of the system, decreases the communication burden and ensures the drying process proceeds safely even when one of subsystems gets isolated.

5.2 Information about the controller type

The controller is the machine that has a central processing unit in industrial automation which coordinates, monitors, and optimizes all equipment and control loops in the drying process. It continuously accepts field sensor signals that measure important process parameters, processes them based on pre-programmed logic and PID algorithms, and emits signals to actuators such as heaters, fans, pumps, and valves. This guarantees efficient, safe, and stable functionality of the drying system even in dynamically varying conditions. In this drying system, a combined controller design has been applied using the Modicon M241 together with the Modicon M340. The Modicon M241 acts as the primary machine controller for local process operations, while the Modicon M340 extends the system with additional processing capability, communication options, and modular I/O capacity.

The Modicon M241 incorporates digital and analogue inputs and outputs, enabling smooth connection with all sensors and actuators. It performs sophisticated *PID* plans to sustain optimum drying conditions, as well as safety interlocks, alarms, and communication with the HMI terminal. Operators are able to see the process and make any necessary changes in real time (Figure 5.2).

Figure 5.2 – Modicon M241 controller

In addition, the system includes the Modicon M340, which supports a wider range of industrial communication protocols and provides extra I/O expansion for future system growth. The M340 enhances the overall reliability of the architecture by handling supervisory tasks, data exchange, and integration of remote devices. It also contributes to long-term stability in industrial environments by offering a more

robust and modular hardware platform (Figure 5.3). Together, they ensure that all necessary operations during the drying process are executed reliably and efficiently.

Figure 5.3 – Modicon M340 controller

Both controllers support industrial communication protocols such as Modbus TCP/IP and Ethernet, allowing integration of devices at a distance and guaranteeing reliable data transfer throughout the system. The EcoStruxure Machine Expert software simplifies the programming and configuration process and enables efficient customization of control logic based on the unique attributes of the drying process.

The system becomes very flexible and reliable by utilizing both the Modicon M241 and M340. On the figure below, the Modicon M241 controller is presented (Figure 5.1).

5.3 Description of controller modules

Based on the operational needs of the technological process, the appropriate modules for the Modicon M340 controller were carefully selected. The hardware configuration begins with a 12-slot chassis, chosen to house all required components while also leaving adequate space for future system upgrades or integration of new modules. At the core of this configuration is the BMX P34 2020 processor module (Figure 5.3), which operates as the main CPU responsible for executing the control logic, managing communication networks, and supervising all connected I/O channels.

Figure 5.4 – BMX P34 2020

BMX P34 2020 also has the mean of built-in Ethernet communication which can be used to exchange data rapidly and effectively with SCADA, HMIs, and slave controllers. Its diagnostic protocols and functions allow it to operate without any problem and maintain itself easily. Table 5.1 summarises the key technical specifications of the processor module.

Table 5.1 – Main specification of BMX P34 2020

Category	Specification
Price	714.547 KZT
Range of product	Modicon M340 automation platform
Product or component type	Processor module
Concept	Transparent Ready CANopen
Number of racks	4
Number of slots	11
Discrete I/O processor capacity	1024 I/O multi-rack configuration 704 I/O single-rack configuration
Analogue I/O processor capacity	256 I/O multi-rack configuration 66 I/O single-rack configuration
Control channels	Programmable cycles

The BMX CPS 3020 power supply module is selected to provide electrical power to the entire PLC system. Its main technical characteristics are presented in Table 3.3. In any automated control system, a stable and dependable power source is essential, as the controller must receive the correct voltage and current levels to perform all monitoring and regulatory functions effectively. CPS 3020 allows all modules installed in chassis to be run continuously without negative effects of voltage changes and other undesirable failures. Its dependability directly leads to the general stability of the drying process and the possibility of the long-term stability of the control system. Moreover, the fact that it has a large input voltage range is also an advantage as it is applicable to any industrial setting (Figure 5.5).

Figure 5.5 – BMX CPS 3020

The controller operates by processing input signals from sensors and executing programmed control algorithms; therefore, uninterrupted power delivery is critical for maintaining accurate system behavior. To guarantee safe and consistent

operation, the power supply incorporates internal voltage regulation, noise filtering, and various protective circuits (Table 5.2).

Table 5.2 – Main specifications of BMX CPS 3020

Category	Specification
Price	313.335 KZT
Range of product	Modicon X80
Product or component type	Power supply module
Supply circuit type	Direct current
Primary voltage	24...48 V isolated
Secondary power	15 W 3.3 V DC I/O module logic power supply 31.2 W 24 V DC I/O module power supply and processor
Primary voltage limit	18...62.4 V
Input current	0.83 A 48 V 1.65 A 24 V
Inrush current	30 A 24 V 60 A 48 V

Modicon M241 structure has been configured to include analog IO module TM3TM3/G and the communication module TM4ES4. The extra module TMTM3/G proves to be 2 analog or temperature inputs, 1 analog output (Figure 5.6). These modules increase the capability of the controller to communicate with important process variables including temperature, pressure and flow. TM4ES4 communication module improves the network connectivity and helps in the exchange of data quickly between slave PLC, the master controller, and SCADA. These additions work together to guarantee precise measurement of a signal, quality signal processing, and proper integration into the control architecture in general (Figure 5.6).

Figure 5.6 – Analog I/O module TMTM3/G

The TMTM3/G Analog I/O module is designed to acquire and process analog signals within industrial automation systems. It provides accurate and stable

measurements of parameters such as temperature, pressure, and flow, which supports reliable data transmission to the controller. Its robust construction and high signal fidelity make it suitable for deployment in demanding industrial environments. The specifications of the given module are listed in the Table 5.3.

Table 5.3 – Specifications of TMTM3/G

Category	Specification
Product Type	Analog I/O Module
Analog Inputs	2 channels
Input Connection Types	Current: 0 – 20 mA, 4 – 20 mA Voltage: ± 10 V, 0 – 10 v
Input Resolution	16 bits, 16 bits + sign
Analog Outputs	1 channels
Output Connection Types	Current: 0 – 20 mA, 4 – 20 mA Voltage: ± 10 V, 0 – 10 v
Output Resolution	12 bits
Accuracy	No isolation between channels
Isolation	CE, UL, CSA, RCM, EAC, Merchant Navy
Vibration/Shock Resistance	-Vibration: 3 gn -Shock: 15 gn
Certifications	CE, UKCA, RCM, EAC, cULus, HazLoc

The next module is a network module TM4ES4. This communication module provides an Ethernet connection with 4 ports on controllers without embedded Ethernet.

Figure 5.7 – Network module TM4ES4

It also provides a second Ethernet connection with four ports on controllers that already have embedded Ethernet, allowing additional devices to be connected without compromising network performance (Figure 5.7). The communication ports support industrial protocols such as Ethernet/IP, Modbus TCP, TCP, and UDP, ensuring fast and reliable data exchange between the controller, HMI terminals,

sensors, and SCADA systems. Additionally, the module improves network scalability by enabling easy expansion of distributed automation architectures. Its robust industrial design ensures stable operation even in environments with high electromagnetic interference or continuous data traffic (Table 5.4).

Table 5.4 – Specifications of TM4ES4

Category	Specification
Product Type	Ethernet unmanaged switch
Integrated Terminal Type	Ethernet RJ45
Power Supply	Internal power supply via chassis
Current Consumption	360 mA 5 V DC communication bus
Local Indicators	For PWR 1 LED (green) for Ethernet link 1 LED per channel (green/yellow) for Ethernet port activity 1 LED per channel (green)
Operating Temperature	-10...+55 °C
Relative Humidity	10...95% (non-condensing)
IP Degree of Protection	IP20
Certifications	cULus, C-tick
Maximum connections	8 Modbus server, 16 Ethernet/IP devices
Weight	0.125 kg

The Modicon TM2DRA8RT digital output module is engineered to control and monitor a diverse array of devices within automated industrial systems (Figure 5.4). This module is optimized for relay-based applications, ensuring reliable operation of solenoid valves, motors, switches, and other actuators that require electrically isolated outputs. Featuring eight relay outputs, the TM2DRA8RT can interface with multiple field devices simultaneously and maintain stable performance under varying load conditions. The relay contacts are constructed for durability and are capable of withstanding frequent switching cycles, which makes the module suitable for both continuous and intermittent control tasks. The TM2DRA8RT supports fail-safe operation by providing diagnostic indicators that enable operators to quickly identify output states or detect potential wiring issues. Utilizing relay technology, the module safely switches both AC and DC loads, providing flexibility in mixed-signal environments. Integration with Modicon controllers via the TM2 expansion bus allows for rapid configuration and minimal setup time. The robust design of the module ensures reliable operation in harsh industrial environments characterized by electrical noise or vibration. Furthermore, its compact form factor conserves panel space while maintaining compatibility with standard DIN-rail installations (Figure 5.8). The module also simplifies maintenance and troubleshooting, as its clear status indicators allow operators to quickly diagnose faults and minimize downtime. As a result, the TM2DRA8RT plays a vital role in ensuring reliable, efficient, and safe operation of industrial automation systems. Moreover, the electrical isolation provided by relay outputs increases operational safety by protecting the control system from voltage spikes and short circuits.

Figure 5.8 – Discrete output module TM2DRA8RT

The specifications of this module are presented in Table 5.5. This module is required because the project involves numerous control points, and the M241 alone does not provide a sufficient number of channels to manage them all. Additionally, the flexible mounting options and compact form factor facilitate straightforward installation in both small control panels and complex automation cabinets. The reliable relay switching capability provides consistent performance throughout extended operational cycles, establishing the device as a dependable component in various industrial automation applications.

Table 5.5 – Specifications of TM2DRA8RT

Category	Specification
Product Type	Discrete output module
Output Number	8
Output Logic	Positive or negative
Output Voltage	24 V DC relay output, 240 V AC
Output Current	2000 mA relay output
Response Time	Turn-on: 10 ms, Turn-off: 5 ms
IP Degree of Protection	IP20
Operating Temperature	Vertical installation: 14...95 °F (-10...35 °C) Horizontal installation: 14...131 °F (-10...55 °C)
Certifications	CE, cULus, UKCA, RCM, EAC, cULus HazLoc
Weight	0.11 kg

The TM3AI8/G is an analog input module from the TM3 series, capable of handling multiple analog signals simultaneously (Figure 5.9). It is commonly used for collecting precise measurements from sensors such as temperature transmitters, pressure transducers, and flow meters in industrial automation systems.

Figure 5.9 - Analog input module TM3AI8/G

It is particularly suitable for applications that require accurate measurement of analog parameters such as temperature, pressure, or fluid level. It is particularly suitable for applications that require accurate measurement of analog parameters such as temperature, pressure, or fluid level, ensuring reliable data acquisition and precise monitoring of process variables. This enables stable control performance and enhances overall system efficiency in automated drying operations. The specifications of the given module are listed in the Table 5.6.

Table 5.6 – Specifications of TM3AI8/G

Category	Specification
Product Type	Analog input module
Analog Input Channels	8
Input types	Current: 4...20 mA, 0...20 mA Voltage: 0...10 V, -10...10 V
Operating Temperature	Horizontal installation: -10...55 °C Vertical installation: -10...35 °C
IP Degree of Protection	IP20
Certifications	CE, cULus, UKCA, RCM, EAC, cULus HazLoc
Weight	0.11 kg

The Modicon TM3 series has a TM3AQ4/G analog output module which is particularly intended to be applied in the industrial automation systems in order to create accurate control signals to a variety of actuators (Figure 5.10). This module has several channels and is therefore appropriate to processes whose equipment needs to be fine-tuned like dampers, drives, and control valves. Its high-resolution output and stable signal generation ensure precise and reliable control performance even in dynamic industrial environments.

Figure 5.10 – Analog output module TM3AQ4/G

Besides multi-channel capability, the TM3AQ4/G has provided stable and noise-resistant signal transmission, which is very important in ensuring that continuous control loops remain accurate. The requirements of the provided module are presented in Table 5.7 where the details on the electrical and functional peculiarities of the module are outlined. This module is ideal for applications with multiple analog outputs, like actuating motors or other devices in the industry. The specifications of the given module are listed in the Table 5.7.

Table 5.7 – Specifications of TM3AQ4/G

Category	Specification
Product Type	Analog output module
Analog Input Channels	4
Input types	Current: 4...20 mA, 0...20 mA Voltage: 0...10 V, -10...10 V
Operating Temperature	Horizontal installation: -10...55 °C Vertical installation: -10...35 °C
IP Degree of Protection	IP20
Certifications	CE, UKCA, RCM, EAC, cULus, HazLoc
Weight	0.115 kg

The industrial PC is a key component of the automation system, serving as a high-performance computing unit for real-time data processing, visualization, and advanced control tasks (Figure 5.11). It is used to run SCADA software, ensure reliable communication with programmable logic controllers (PLC), and provide continuous monitoring of technological parameters.

Figure 5.11 – Analog output module TM3AQ4/G

In addition to standard control functions, the industrial PC supports the implementation of AI-based algorithms for data analysis, anomaly detection, and process optimization. This enhances the efficiency, stability, and intelligence of the industrial drying system. The technical specifications of the selected industrial PC are presented in Table 5.8.

Table 5.8 – Specifications of Industrial PC

Category	Specification
Product Type	Industrial PC
CPU	12 cores
RAM	32 GB
Storage	SSD 512 GB
GPU	RTX 4060
Operating system	Windows
Application	SCADA, data processing, AI analysis

In addition, the use of an industrial PC provides flexibility in system expansion and integration with higher-level information systems. It allows for the implementation of advanced data processing techniques, including predictive analytics and machine learning models, which can improve process control performance and reduce operational risks. Furthermore, the industrial PC supports data storage and historical data analysis, enabling better understanding of process behavior over time. This facilitates optimization of control strategies, improves energy efficiency, and enhances the overall reliability of the industrial drying system. Additionally, the industrial PC enables seamless communication with supervisory systems such as SCADA and cloud-based platforms, supporting real-time monitoring and remote diagnostics. Its computational capability allows the integration of advanced control algorithms and digital twin models for more accurate

system representation and optimization. As a result, the overall system becomes more adaptive, scalable, and aligned with Industry 4.0 principles.

5.4 Information about data networks

Industrial data networks are specialized communication systems designed to operate in demanding industrial environments. They provide reliable connectivity between various devices such as sensors, actuators, controllers, and supervisory computer systems. The primary objective of these networks is to ensure efficient data exchange, enable real-time control, and enhance the overall performance and safety of industrial processes. In the presented technological process, the Modbus protocol is utilized. Originally developed by Modicon Systems in 1979, Modbus was introduced as a programming and communication protocol for Programmable Logic Controllers (PLCs). Over time, it has evolved into a widely accepted industry standard for data exchange between industrial control and monitoring devices.

Modbus is an open client/server communication protocol based on a master–slave architecture. In this system, the master device initiates communication requests, while slave devices respond accordingly. Communication is unidirectional, meaning that slaves cannot initiate data transmission on their own.

The Modbus RTU (Remote Terminal Unit) variant is a widely used serial communication protocol in industrial automation. It allows controllers to communicate using transmission modes such as ASCII (American Standard Code for Information Interchange) and RTU. Within the Modbus data structure, information is stored in predefined address ranges, including: Coils, Discrete Inputs, Holding Registers, Input Registers. Modbus RTU typically operates on a point-to-point communication basis, establishing a direct connection between two devices. It supports one client (master) and up to 247 server (slave) devices. The physical layer for Modbus RTU communication may vary depending on the application, using RS-485, RS-422, or RS-232 serial interfaces as defined by the Electronic Industries Alliance (EIA). An advanced version of the protocol, Modbus TCP/IP, integrates Modbus RTU with the Transmission Control Protocol (TCP) interface over Ethernet networks. This extension enables high-speed communication and easier integration with modern industrial systems. In this project, communication between controllers will be established using Modbus TCP/IP following the master–slave configuration, ensuring reliable and synchronized data exchange across all connected modules.

5.5 Specifications of sensors with basic characteristics

The selection of appropriate sensors and actuators is critical for the effective automation of the drum drying process. Components must be fully compatible with the Modicon M241 controller, meet the required process specifications, and enable precise monitoring and control of all critical process variables. Sensors act as input devices, detecting process parameters such as temperature, moisture content,

pressure, and flow, while actuators serve as output devices, executing control actions to maintain optimal drying conditions.

For measuring temperature within the system, including the drying air, drum surface, or product layer, a PT100 sensor has been selected. The PT100, also known as a platinum resistance thermometer (RTD), operates based on the principle that the electrical resistance of platinum changes proportionally with temperature. The designation PT100 indicates that the sensor has a resistance of 100 Ω at 0 °C (Figure 5.11). Industrial drying systems have largely adopted the PT100 since it is very accurate, stable and can withstand unfair operating conditions. Its capacity to stabilize temperature readings within a large scale will provide credible feedback in the closed-loop control. The sensor can be used to supply real-time temperature measurements when connected with the M241 controller via an analogue input module to adjust the strength of heating, the rate of airflow, or the speed of the drum. It is this degree of accuracy that will allow the same level of product quality, avoid overheating, and enable the system to operate efficiently with regard to energy consumption of the drum drying apparatus.

Figure 5.12 – PT100 temperature sensor

Additionally, PT100 sensors are resistant to environmental disturbances such as vibration, humidity, and dust, which ensures long-term stability and durability. In table 5.9 gives information about platinum resistant thermometer PT100.

Table 5.9 – PT100 specification

Specification	Value
Sensor type	RTD (platinum resistance temperature detector)
Nominal Resistance	At 0 degrees Celsius, nominal resistance of 100 ohms
Temperature Range	-50 to +200 degrees Celsius
Climate Rating	Y1.1(-45+60): from -45 to +60 degrees Celsius
Material of Head	AK12
Mounting length	60 mm

Furthermore, we also need pressure transmitter to ensure our pressure level. The Honeywell offers a measurement accuracy of $\pm 0.1\%$ of span (with high-accuracy options available), and is compatible with a variety of process connections, making it adaptable for many installations. It offers a standard 4–20 mA analog output signal, allowing for easy integration with the Modicon M241 PLC for real-time monitoring and control. This provides accurate pressure regulation in the drum drying system, improving both operating safety and improving process efficiency (Figure 5.12).

Figure 5.13 – pressure sensor ST700

It provides an analog 4-20 mA output signal and supports communication protocols like HART, Modbus, and Foundation Fieldbus. Thorough details regarding its input/output signals, communication protocols and work specifications are available in Table 5.10.

Table 5.10 – Technical characteristics of ST700

Specification	Value
Upper Measurement Limit	6,895 kPa (or 68.95 bar)
Output Signal	Analog signals (4-20 mA) with HART Protocol
Climate Performance	Operating temperature range: -40°C to $+85^{\circ}\text{C}$ (process temperature range may vary by model)
Process Connection	1/2" NPT or DIN/ISO G 1/2" threaded connection
Measurement error	$\pm 0.1\%$ of calibrated span; optional high accuracy models $\pm 0.04\%$
Range of measured pressures	Various ranges available, minimum span as low as 0-2.5 kPa up to maximum 6,895 kPa
Communication Protocols	Modbus, HART, Foundation Fieldbus

The KPM Analytics MCT566 is a non-contact NIR moisture sensor used for real-time measurement of product moisture in industrial processes (Figure 5.11). It operates based on near-infrared (NIR) technology, analyzing reflected infrared light from the product surface to determine moisture content with high accuracy.

Figure 5.14 – KPM Analytics MCT566 NIR moisture sensor

The sensor provides continuous measurement and transmits data to the control system via an analog signal, enabling real-time monitoring and automatic adjustment of process parameters. This ensures stable product quality and improves the efficiency of the drying process. In addition, the use of a non-contact measurement method eliminates mechanical wear and reduces maintenance requirements, making the sensor suitable for harsh industrial environments. The main technical characteristics of the MCT566 moisture sensor are presented in Table 5.9.

Table 5.11 – Technical characteristics of MCT566 moisture sensor

Specification	Value
Measurement Type	NIR, non-contact
Output Signal	Analog signals (4-20 mA)
Power Supply	24 V DC
Accuracy	±0.1–0.5%
Application	Real-time moisture measurement

In addition, the use of a non-contact measurement method eliminates mechanical wear and reduces maintenance requirements, making the sensor suitable for harsh industrial environments. The main technical characteristics of the MCT566 moisture sensor are presented in Table 5.9.

5.6 Specification of actuator

Actuators are gadgets which are fed by the PLC with control signals and translate them into actual motion which can control the different process parameters automatically. Actuators are important in the drum drying system to regulate the flow of the steam, feed material and release of the finished product. The chosen

actuators are quite compatible with the Modicon M241 PLC which can accept 4 - 20mA analog signal to control valves and digital interfaces and they have Schneider Electric valve positioners to promote accurate and dependable work. The steam valve will be used to control the steam into the drying drum to ensure the required drum surface temperature is maintained to ensure optimum drying operation is realized. The type of device chosen is a Schneider Electric electric control valve with an in-built positioner. The valve is connected to the Modicon M241 PLC through 4-20 mA analog signal, and thus the steam flow can be accurately modulated. Positioning of valves The valve positioner provides a quick, accurate response to control commands in addition to giving a PLC real-time position feedback. This maintains the temperature of the drum at a consistent level enhancing the quality of products and energy efficiency. The valve is also applicable in industrial steam fitting because the fitting has a high temperature rating and it is strong.

The steam valve is responsible for regulating the flow of steam into the drying drum, maintaining the desired drum surface temperature to achieve optimal drying performance. The selected device is a Schneider Electric EV210/EV220 electric control valve with an integrated positioner. The valve communicates with the Modicon M241 PLC via a analog signal, allowing precise modulation of the steam flow. The valve positioner ensures fast and accurate response to control commands while providing real-time position feedback to the PLC. This ensures that the drum temperature is consistently maintained, improving product quality and energy efficiency. The smart control valve positioner SRD998 valve is suitable for industrial steam applications due to its high-temperature rating and robust construction (Figure 5.13).

Figure 5.15 – intelligent control valve positioner SRD998

The SRD998 offers a larger choice of pneumatic performance including high flow versions and up to 10 bars air supply and output pressure is available. High output pressure allows the positioner to work at a higher torque on the actuator and valve; therefore, smaller actuator sizes can be used. Very high flow capacity versions allow you to realize savings since small volume boosters are not necessary. The enhanced pneumatic capability of the SRD998, offering high flow rates and up to 10

bars output pressure, directly contributes to improved valve control accuracy and faster response times in demanding process applications (Table 5.11).

Table 5.11 – Technical characteristics of valve positioner SRD998

Category	Specification
Power Supply	24 V DC
Input signal	4 – 20 mA analog
Communication protocol	HART / PROFIBUS/ FOUNDATION Fieldbus
Control accuracy	± 0.1 of full stroke
Operating Pressure Range	0.14 – 0.7 MPa (air supply)
Response Time	< 300 ms
Operating Temperature Range	-40°C to + 85°C
Protection Class (Enclosure)	IP66 / NEMA 4X
Material	Aluminum alloy
Weight	2.1 kg

The 3-phase AC geared motor is a robust and efficient solution for industrial drum rotation, designed for applications such as large-scale drying, material processing, and continuous rotary operations. It provides reliable and controllable rotational motion of the drum via a high-torque gearbox, ensuring smooth operation under heavy load. The unit features adjustable speed when paired with a variable frequency drive (VFD), allowing integration with *PLC/PID* control systems for automated process management (Figure 5.14).

Figure 5.16 – Three-phase AC induction motor

Its robust design supports continuous-duty operation, while the industrial-grade helical gearbox ensures safe and reliable transmission of torque (Table 5.12). The motor is highly adaptable, compatible with various drum sizes, and designed for easy installation and maintenance in laboratory or small-scale industrial environments. In

addition, its modular gearbox and coupling system allow flexible adjustment of speed and torque to optimize drum rotation for different load conditions.

Table 5.12 – Technical characteristics of three-phase AC induction motor

Category	Specification
Motor type	3-phase squirrel-cage induction motor
Power	75 kW
Supply voltage	380–480 V
Rated speed	1500 rpm
Rated torque	478 N · m
Gearbox type	Helical / parallel-shaft industrial gearbox
Weight	800 kg

5.7 Conclusion

The choice of technical equipment for the drum drying system ensures safe, precise, and efficient process control. The selected Modicon M241 PLC, Schneider Electric sensors, and SRD998 positioner drives ensure seamless integration, accurate tracking, and consistent automation. A 3-phase AC geared motor actuator with helical gearbox drives the drum, providing reliable and controllable rotation throughout the drying process. This setup ensures stable drying quality, energy efficiency, and easy scalability for further system updates.

6. Program development

Programmable Logic Controllers (PLCs) play a central role in industrial automation, serving as the connection point between sensors, actuators, and other field devices in the automated control of the rotary drum drying process. In this project, the PLC system is used to supervise and regulate key drying operations, including hot air flow, drum rotation speed, feed rate, and product moisture control. The control program was developed using EcoStruxure Control Expert software from Schneider Electric, which provides tools for programming, configuring, and maintaining the automation system. By integrating all control elements into one structure, the system improves process stability, energy efficiency, and final product quality.

6.1 Description of system variables

In EcoStruxure Control Expert, variables are essential for both system control and visualization in the automated drum drying process. They represent real-time process information, including sensor measurements, actuator states, and control setpoints. Input variables correspond to measured parameters such as air temperature, product moisture content, airflow rate, and drum rotation speed. Output variables are used to control actuators, including fans, valves, and drive systems regulating the drum and air supply. Visualization variables enable operators to monitor and interact with the process through graphical interfaces, ensuring stable and efficient operation of the drying system. All variables are named according to international standards to ensure clarity and consistency. They are defined in the Elementary Variables section and integrated into the Animation Table, where their behavior can be observed during simulation. For handling more complex data structures, arrays and structured variables are also applied, improving scalability and organization of the control program.

Table 6.1 - System variables for M340 controller

Tag Name	Description	Address	Type
auto_mode	Button Physical Control Mode	%I0.2.0	EBOOL
start_button	Control Button	%I0.2.1	EBOOL
button_manual	Control Button	%I0.2.2	EBOOL
button_auto	Control Button	%I0.2.3	EBOOL
button_stop	Control Button	%I0.2.6	EBOOL
button_ready	Control Button	%I0.2.5	EBOOL
button_run	Control Button	%I0.2.4	EBOOL

The table provides a detailed overview of the system variables used in the Modicon M340 controller, including their tag names, descriptions, memory

addresses, variable types, and associated control modules. It also reflects how these variables are mapped to physical process signals such as temperature, moisture, airflow, and actuator states, ensuring accurate monitoring and control of the drying process.

Table 6.2 - Modicon M241 point description

Tag Name	Point Description	Address	Type
vlv01	Main air valve	%QX0.0	BOOL
vlv02	Fuel Inlet valve	%QX0.1	BOOL
vlv03	Steam/water supply valve	%QX0.2	BOOL
vlv04	Exhaust damper actuator	%QX0.3	BOOL
vlv05	Auxiliary burner valve	%QX0.4	BOOL
vlv06	Purge air valve	%QX0.5	BOOL

The next table presents the system variables for the Modicon M241 controller. It includes details such as tag names, descriptions of each point, memory addresses, variable types, and the corresponding control modules.

6.2 Developed process control mnemonic diagram

In the automated rotary drum drying system, control is distributed between two PLCs. The Modicon M340 operates as the master controller, supervising the overall drying process, including regulation of air temperature, airflow, and product moisture. It also coordinates the operation of the drum drying system and manages the inlet and outlet conditions of the drying unit, ensuring stable and efficient process performance.

Figure 6.1 – Architecture of controller connection

The PLCs communicate via the Modbus TCP protocol, with the M340 sending information about process status and key drying variables, such as air temperature, airflow rate, and product moisture, to the M241. This allows the drying units to operate in coordination with the overall process. For example, if the measured moisture level falls outside the acceptable range, the M241 will not execute commands to start or continue the related equipment. This distribution of tasks ensures coordinated system operation: the M340 manages the overall drying process, while the M241 controllers handle the operation of individual field devices according to the master controller's instructions. The actuators connected to the M241 controller are controlled through their assigned addresses. Each actuator is operated by a digital or analog signal depending on the process requirement. The overall drying process, including air supply, drum rotation, and product discharge, is controlled by the M340 master controller. The M241 receives commands from the M340 via the Modbus TCP connection, ensuring that all actuators operate in coordination with the drying process. Detailed connections and addressing of the M241-controlled devices are provided in Appendix H.

Figure 6.2 – Modbus TCP connection

6.3 Program Description

The presented program was developed for a programmable logic controller (PLC) used in the automated control system of a rotary drum drying process in food production. The system is based on a Modicon M241 controller operating together with a Modicon M340 PLC. Communication between controllers is implemented using Functional Block Diagram (FBD) programming and Modbus TCP protocol. The control program manages the operation of the rotary drum dryer, including regulation of hot air flow, drum rotation speed, and feed rate. A proportional–

integral–derivative (PID) control strategy is applied to maintain the desired product moisture content and ensure stable thermal conditions inside the dryer. Key process parameters—such as air temperature, product moisture, and airflow rate—are continuously monitored and adjusted in real time. This enables efficient drying performance, improved energy utilization, and consistent product quality. Figure 6.3 illustrates the control structure of the rotary drum drying process.

Figure 6.3 – Mnemonic diagram of control plant

Figure 6.4 represents a working stand with 4 attached pressure sensors and 2 attached temperature sensors.

Figure 6.4 – Realization on stand

The variable frequency drives ATV630 and ATV320 were selected to represent the operation of actuators in the drying system. These devices were integrated to

simulate realistic industrial operating conditions and to validate the performance of the developed control logic. The data obtained from sensors were used to evaluate the performance of the PID controller under varying operating conditions, including changes in temperature, airflow, and product moisture content. The drives (ATV630 and ATV320) are used to precisely regulate the fan speed and the drum rotation speed, ensuring stable drying conditions and improved energy efficiency. This configuration provides an effective platform for analyzing system stability, accuracy, and robustness, enabling optimization of the control strategy prior to real industrial implementation.

Figure 6.5 –Flotation machine operator screen during manual mode

The mnemonic scheme for controlling the lines of Machine 2, Machine 3, Machine 4 has an interface similar to Figure 6.5, Machine 1.

Figure 6.6 – PID controller display screen

The difference is in the names of tags and control components of the program. Figure 6.6 shows a fragment of a mnemonic scheme for the implementation of the PI control system by a valve. The adjustment coefficients of the regulator and the main parameters of the system are shown.

The Modicon M340 controller is controlled using the EcoStructure Control Expert software product in Structured Text language. In Figure 6.7 is shown an HMI panel for the system control with opening menu and control object.

Figure 6.7 – Operator Screen in M340

A Human–Machine Interface (HMI) panel serves as the primary graphical interface for monitoring and controlling the flotation process. It provides operators with a visual representation of real-time process data, including pulp level, air flow, reagent dosing rates, and froth conditions. The panel displays status indicators, trends, and active alarms, allowing operators to quickly assess the performance of flotation cells. Through the HMI, operators can adjust setpoints such as air input, reagent feed rates, and discharge valve positions.

6.4 Conclusion

Chapter 6 was devoted to the program implementation of technological process. To begin with, there were system variables given in both of Modicon M340 and M241. Then mnemonic diagram was created in EcoStructure Control Expert, and Machine Expert, Operator Terminal Expert. The program was coded in FBD and ST code. Each operator screen was added with auto, manual and stop mode, alarms.

7. AI IMPLEMENTATION

The primary purpose of integrating AI into this industrial drying project is to transition from traditional "blind" automation to Smart Manufacturing (Industry 4.0). While the *PID* controllers manage the mechanical stability of the drum, the Computer Vision (CV) system introduces a "perception" layer that acts as a proof-of-concept for autonomous quality assurance. By classifying raw materials in real-time, the AI ensures that the input parameters of the drying model remain within optimal bounds, thereby preventing the processing of defective goods that would otherwise lead to energy waste and batch contamination.

7.1 Computer vision quality control.

The implemented vision control system transforms the production line into an intelligent, self-correcting environment. High-level vision-based decisions inform low-level mechanical actuators, significantly reducing manual intervention and optimizing the Yield on Quality (YoQ).

The general pipeline by which the AI is going to run on a industry is illustrated at following scheme:

Figure 7.1 – General pipeline in AI implementation

The foundational data for this module was sourced from the "Fruits fresh and rotten for classification" dataset [14]. The dataset is composed of multiple categories of fruits, each divided into fresh and rotten classes, providing a balanced and representative distribution for training the classification model. This diversity enables the neural network to generalize effectively across variations in color, texture, and lighting conditions typically encountered in industrial environments.

Figure below shows how classes are distributed:

Figure 7.2 – Distribution of classes

However, industrial computer vision models are highly susceptible to Data Leakage—a phenomenon where overlapping features between the training and validation/test sets lead to artificially inflated performance metrics and poor generalization in real-world scenarios. To mitigate this, a formal preprocessing pipeline was implemented to detect and remove near-duplicate images using Perceptual Hashing (pHash).

7.1.1 Mathematical foundation of perceptual hashing

Unlike cryptographic hash functions (e.g., MD5 or SHA-256), which are designed to change radically with a single-bit flip, a Perceptual Hash (h) remains relatively invariant under minor transformations such as scaling, brightness shifts, or compression noise. The function $H(\cdot) = \text{Calculate_pHash}(I)$ is defined by the following mathematical operations:

1) Spatial Dimensionality Reduction: The image I is downsampled to an $N \times N$ matrix (typically 32×32) to eliminate high-frequency noise and focus on structural components.

2) Discrete Cosine Transform (DCT): The luminance matrix f with elements $f(x, y)$ is transformed into the frequency domain. The DCT coefficient $F(u, v)$ is calculated as:

$$F(u, v) = \frac{2}{N} C(u) C(v) \sum_{x=0}^{N-1} \sum_{y=0}^{N-1} f(x, y) \cos \left[\frac{(2x+1)u\pi}{2N} \right] \cos \left[\frac{(2y+1)v\pi}{2N} \right] \quad (7.1)$$

$$\text{Where, } C(w) = \begin{cases} \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}, & \text{if } w = 0 \\ 1, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (7.2)$$

3) Spectral Compression: Only the low-frequency components (e.g., the top-left 8×8 sub-matrix) are retained, as they represent the most robust structural information.

4) Binarization: Let F_{low} be the retained $M \times M$ sub-matrix (e.g., 8×8) of DCT coefficients. We flattened this sub-matrix into a vector $f \in \mathbb{R}^{M^2}$. Let μ be the median value of elements in f . The final bit-string hash $h \in 0,1^L$ is generated by:

$$h_i = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } f_i > \mu \\ 0, & \text{if } f_i \leq \mu \end{cases} \quad (7.3)$$

7.1.2 Similarity metric: hamming distance

To quantify the similarity between a training image $I_i \in \mathcal{D}_{\text{train}}$ and a test image $I_j \in \mathcal{D}_{\text{test}}$, the Hamming Distance (d_H) is utilized. It measures the number of positions at which the corresponding bits of the hashes h_i and h_j differ:

$$d_H(h_i, h_j) = \sum_{k=1}^L (h_{i,k} \oplus h_{j,k}) \quad (7.4)$$

where \oplus denotes the XOR operation and n is the bit-length of the hash. A data leakage event is formally defined as any pair (x, y) satisfying:

$$d_H(\text{pHash}(x), \text{pHash}(y)) \leq \tau \quad (7.5)$$

Where τ is the predefined threshold. Setting $\tau = 0$ detects exact duplicates, while $\tau > 0$ identifies near-duplicates.

7.1.3 Algorithmic Implementation

The identification of compromised samples is performed through the following procedure. The identification of compromised samples (data leakage) between the training and testing datasets is carried out using a perceptual hashing-based approach. Each image is transformed into a compact hash representation, enabling efficient comparison across large datasets. The similarity between images is quantified using the Hamming distance between their corresponding hashes. If the computed distance falls below a predefined threshold, the sample is flagged as a potential duplicate and considered as leakage. This procedure ensures that visually similar or identical samples do not appear in both training and testing sets, which is critical for maintaining the validity of model evaluation. The detailed pseudocode of the leakage detection algorithm is provided in Appendix F. Following the detection phase, a dataset cleaning procedure is applied to remove all identified compromised samples. This process includes the deletion of flagged files, reconstruction of the dataset directory, and verification of class balance to ensure that the removal process does not introduce bias. The corresponding implementation details are also included in Appendix F. After applying the filtering and cleaning procedures, the dataset was

refined to a final split of 10,374 images for training and 2,698 images for testing, ensuring both data integrity and balanced class distribution.

7.1.4 Stochastic data augmentation and environmental simulation

To ensure model robustness against the operational variability of industrial environments, a multi-stage stochastic augmentation pipeline was implemented using the Albumentations framework. This pipeline simulates three primary categories of environmental interference characteristic of automated conveyor systems:

Optical and Motion Artifacts: High-speed movement is modeled using Motion Blur in range [3,15], while sensor electronic noise is simulated via Gaussian Noise.

Photometric Variability: To account for inconsistent facility lighting and shadows, a Random Brightness and Contrast transformation is applied.

Physical Obstructions: Coarse Dropout is utilized to simulate partial occlusions (e.g., dust on lenses or overlapping objects), forcing the model to learn spatially invariant features.

The geometric transformation T for an input image I can be represented as:

$$I_{aug} = \mathcal{J}_{geom} \left(\mathcal{J}_{photo} \left(\mathcal{J}_{noise}(I) \right) \right) \quad (7.6)$$

where each transformation is applied with a probability p , ensuring the training set distribution encompasses the edge cases of the production line.

7.1.5 Model selection and architectural analysis

To determine the optimal balance between inferential throughput and classification accuracy, two distinct deep Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) architectures were evaluated using transfer learning.

7.1.5.1 Residual networks (ResNet-18)

Deep networks traditionally suffer from vanishing gradients, where the derivative of the loss function approaches zero during backpropagation, effectively stalling optimization. ResNet-18 mitigates this via identity shortcut connections. Mathematically, rather than requiring stacked non-linear layers to directly fit a desired underlying mapping $H(x)$, the network is tasked with fitting a residual mapping:

$$F(x) = H(x) - x \quad (7.7)$$

Figure 7.2 – ResNet-18 model architecture

The original mapping is thus recast as $H(x) = F(x) + x$. This allows gradients to flow unhindered through the shortcut connections. In this implementation, the layer4 parameters were unfrozen for fine-tuning, and the fully connected (FC) classification head was structurally modified to output logits for the specific target classes.

7.1.5.2 EfficientNet-B0

As a parameter-efficient alternative, EfficientNet-B0 was deployed. Unlike traditional models that scale dimensions arbitrarily, EfficientNet utilizes a compound scaling method governed by a constant coefficient ϕ . The network uniformly scales depth (d), width (w), and resolution (r) according to:

$$d = \alpha^\phi, \quad w = \beta^\phi, \quad r = \gamma^\phi \quad (7.8)$$

Subject to the constraint:

$$\alpha \cdot \beta^2 \cdot \gamma^2 \approx 2 \quad (7.9)$$

This balanced scaling strategy enables EfficientNet-B0 to achieve superior performance while maintaining relatively low computational cost compared to conventional convolutional neural networks. By jointly optimizing all three dimensions, the model avoids the inefficiencies associated with scaling only depth or width independently. As a result, EfficientNet-B0 provides an excellent trade-off between accuracy and resource consumption, making it particularly suitable for real-time industrial applications where computational constraints are critical. In the context of this project, the model's efficiency allows seamless integration with the

vision-based quality control system, ensuring fast inference without compromising classification reliability. Furthermore, its compact architecture reduces memory usage, which is advantageous for deployment on embedded or edge devices commonly used in Industry 4.0 environments.

Figure 7.3 - EfficientNet-B3 architecture

Where $\alpha, \beta, \gamma \geq 1$. This principled scaling ensures maximum feature extraction with minimal computational overhead. The architecture was customized by unfreezing the feature extraction modules from Block 7 onwards and appending a classification head with a dropout probability P_{drop} to enforce regularization.

7.1.5.3 Optimization and Loss Landscape

Both networks were trained utilizing the AdamW optimizer. AdamW improves upon the standard Adam optimizer by decoupling weight decay from the gradient update. Traditionally, weight decay is embedded within the loss function; however, in adaptive learning rate methods, this interaction can lead to suboptimal regularization. AdamW applies the decay factor λ directly to the weights:

$$\theta_{t+1} = \theta_t - \eta \hat{m}_t - \eta \lambda \theta_t \quad (7.10)$$

This preservation of the loss landscape geometry results in superior generalization. The objective function employed was Cross-Entropy Loss augmented with Label Smoothing. In standard cross-entropy, the model is penalized unless it outputs a probability of exactly 1.0 for the true class, which often leads to "overconfidence" and poor calibration. Label smoothing modifies the target distribution y , scaling the true class probability to $(1 - \epsilon)$ and uniformly distributing the remaining ϵ among the K classes:

$$y'_i = \begin{cases} 1 - \varepsilon, & \text{if } i = \text{target} \\ \frac{\varepsilon}{K-1}, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (7.11)$$

This enforces a "softer" margin, encouraging the model to learn broader, more robust feature representations of fruit decay rather than fixating on hyper-specific pixel anomalies.

7.1.5.4 Empirical Analysis and Performance Metrics

The models were trained and evaluated over 5 epochs. Performance was quantified not only via raw Accuracy but critically through the F_1 -Score, defined as the harmonic mean of Precision and Recall:

$$F_1 = 2 \cdot \frac{\text{Precision} \cdot \text{Recall}}{\text{Precision} + \text{Recall}} \quad (7.12)$$

The F_1 -Score provides a more stringent measure of the model's ability to minimize both False Positives (incorrectly discarding high-quality fruit) and False Negatives (allowing rotten fruit to pass into the dryer). Here is general illustration of training process with losses and accuracy dynamics over epochs:

Figure 7.4 – Comparison between two models

The figure 7.4 illustrates the training dynamics of the models, showing the variation of accuracy and loss over the training epochs. Both models demonstrate stable convergence and high performance, with accuracy approaching optimal values and loss decreasing consistently. This indicates that the models effectively learn the features required for accurate classification of fruit quality.

Table 7.1 – Characteristic of two models

Metric	EfficientNet-B0	ResNet-18
Parameters (Millions)	4.01 M	11.18 M
Model Size (MB)	41.36 MB	90.00 MB
Inference Speed (FPS)	107	349
Top Accuracy	0.9674	0.9885
F1-Score	0.9707	0.9898
Recall (Rotten Class)	0.9505	0.9817
Precision (Rotten Class)	0.9918	0.9980
Confidence (>90%)	0.6408	0.8073

To evaluate the per-class performance, a Confusion Matrix C was utilized. For a binary classification task (Fresh vs. Rotten), the matrix is defined as:

$$C = \begin{bmatrix} TP & FN \\ FP & TN \end{bmatrix} \quad (7.13)$$

where:

- TP (True Positive) - Correct identification of rotten fruit;
- TN (True Negative) - Correct identification of fresh fruit;
- FP (False Positive) - Type I Error; fresh fruit incorrectly flagged as rotten (economic waste);
- FN (False Negative) - Type II Error; rotten fruit incorrectly passed (quality compromise);

The confusion matrix provides a comprehensive evaluation of classification performance beyond overall accuracy, enabling a more detailed understanding of model behavior in critical scenarios. In industrial applications, particular attention must be given to minimizing false negatives, as misclassifying defective products as acceptable directly impacts product quality and safety. Conversely, false positives, while less critical, can lead to unnecessary material rejection and increased operational costs. Overall, the analysis confirms that the integration of deep learning models significantly enhances the robustness and reliability of the vision-based quality control system, ensuring consistent product standards while optimizing resource utilization. Furthermore, the comparative results indicate that ResNet-18

achieves superior performance across most evaluation metrics, particularly in reducing false negatives and maintaining higher confidence levels.

Figure 7.5 - Confusion matrix of EfficientNet-B0

The confusion matrix shows that EfficientNet-B0 achieves high classification accuracy with minimal errors. Most samples are correctly identified, indicating reliable performance in distinguishing fresh and rotten products (Figure 7.5).

Figure 7.6 - Confusion matrix of EfficientNet-B0

The high Precision (0.9980) and Recall (0.9817) of the ResNet model indicate that the decision boundary effectively minimizes Type II errors. To validate the reliability of the accuracy metrics, a 90% Confidence Interval (CI) for the error rate was calculated using the normal approximation of the binomial distribution:

$$CI = \hat{p} \pm z \sqrt{\frac{\hat{p}(1-\hat{p})}{n}} \quad (7.14)$$

Where \hat{p} represents the observed accuracy, n is the number of samples in the test set, and $z = 1.645$ for a 90% confidence level. The narrow margin of the calculated interval confirms that the model's performance is statistically significant and not a result of stochastic variance in the test sample.

Figure 7.7 - Distribution of model confidence: EfficientNet-B0

The confidence distribution shows that EfficientNet-B0 produces mostly high-confidence predictions, indicating reliable classification performance (Figure 7.7).

Figure 7.8 - Distribution of model confidence: ResNet-18

The graph shows the distribution of prediction confidence for the ResNet-18 model. Most images have high confidence scores, mainly between 0.90 and 1.00, which indicates that the model makes predictions quite confidently. The red dashed line represents the average confidence value of 0.9316.

7.1.5.5 Inference of models

The inference phase represents the deployment of the trained weights within a simulated production environment. For each frame captured by the vision system, the data undergoes a deterministic transformation sequence:

Tensorization and Scaling: Raw pixel data is resized to the 300×300 input dimension and converted to a floating-point tensor.

Statistical Normalization: To align the input with the distribution of the training set, global ImageNet statistics are applied: $\hat{I} = \frac{(I-\mu)}{\sigma}$.

Forward Pass: The preprocessed tensor is propagated through the frozen parameters of the ResNet-18/EfficientNet-B0 backbone to compute the raw class logits.

Example of inference:

Figure 7.9 - Sample predictions of the classification model

This pipeline is optimized for high-velocity throughput. By utilizing asynchronous data loading and GPU acceleration, the system achieves sub-millisecond latency per frame. This ensures that the mechanical actuators responsible for sorting have sufficient lead time to execute physical rejection of "Rotten" samples without slowing the conveyor belt.

7.1.5.6 Explainable AI (XAI)

To validate the internal decision-making process, Gradient-weighted Class Activation Mapping (Grad-CAM) was utilized. This technique provides visual transparency by generating localization maps that highlight the regions influencing the model's classification. The importance weight α_k^c for each feature map k in the final convolutional layer is calculated by:

$$\alpha_k^c = \frac{1}{Z} \sum_i \sum_j \frac{\partial y^c}{\partial A_{i,j}^k} \quad (7.15)$$

The final saliency map is then generated through a ReLU-weighted linear combination:

$$L_{GCAM}^c = \text{ReLU}(\sum_k \alpha_k^c A^k) \quad (7.16)$$

The heatmaps in Figure serve as a qualitative validation of the ResNet's reliability. In "Rotten" classifications, the peak activation intensities (indicated by red zones) consistently align with biological markers of decay, such as localized bruising or fungal patches.

Figure 7.10 - Grad-CAM visualization of model attention

Conversely, for "Fresh" samples, the model maintains a distributed activation across the fruit's surface, confirming it is identifying the absence of defects rather than relying on background artifacts. This "explainability" ensures that the vision control system is mathematically grounded and industrially trustworthy.

7.1.5.7 Conclusion on Model Deployment

While both architectures exhibited exceptional predictive power, the ResNet architecture consistently outperformed the EfficientNet variant in every key metric, including Accuracy (0.9885) and F_1 -Score (0.9898). A critical observation is the Inference Speed. Despite ResNet's larger parametric volume (11.18M parameters), it achieved a throughput of 349 FPS. In the context of the automated plant, a requirement of approximately 50 FPS is the baseline for real-time monitoring of standard conveyor belts. Since ResNet-18/50 exceeds this requirement by a factor of seven, it provides a "computational cushion" for additional logic (such as tracking or robotic sorting) without introducing bottlenecks. Therefore, deploying the ResNet architecture represents the optimal engineering solution: it maximizes the F_1 -Score—ensuring the highest possible fruit quality—while remaining well within the temporal constraints of the hardware.

7.2 RAG-based NLP assistant for technical documentation

The integration of a Retrieval-Augmented Generation (RAG) system serves as the cognitive interface for the industrial drying project. While the vision control system handles real-time mechanical adjustments, the RAG assistant bridges the gap between complex operational documentation and human operators, enabling rapid, grounded troubleshooting and parameter retrieval.

7.2.1 Data Ingestion and Intelligent Chunking

Raw technical manuals, often stored in unstructured PDF formats, are poorly suited for vector-based semantic search. To preserve the hierarchical integrity of the documentation—such as sections, headers, and parameter tables—a structural extraction pipeline was implemented. The text is parsed into Markdown to retain semantic boundaries, followed by recursive chunking. Let T be the complete markdown text. The splitting algorithm partitions T into a set of chunks $C = c_1, c_2 \dots c_n$ prioritizing natural structural separators (e.g., ##, ###, \n\n).

$$|c_i| \leq L_{\max}, \quad |c_i \cap c_{i-1}| = O \quad (7.17)$$

To ensure contextual continuity between adjacent text segments without exceeding the context window of the embedding model, a fixed window length $L_{\max} = 800$ characters and overlap threshold $O = 150$ characters are applied. As a

result, the generated embeddings capture both local and contextual semantics, significantly improving the performance of downstream retrieval tasks. This approach enhances the accuracy and relevance of semantic search, enabling more precise information extraction from complex technical documentation.

7.2.2 Mathematical Foundation of Vector Retrieval

To enable semantic similarity search, the text chunks must be mapped into a continuous vector space. The all-MiniLM-L6-v2 embedding model was deployed, acting as an encoding function $E: \mathcal{T} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^d$, where $d = 384$. To optimize the retrieval speed for the industrial chatbot, inner product search (IndexFlatIP) was utilized via the FAISS (Facebook AI Similarity Search) library. Because the inner product is sensitive to vector magnitude, all embeddings are strictly L2-normalized prior to indexing to ensure the inner product equates to Cosine Similarity.

For a given chunk embedding $\mathbf{v}_i = E(c_i)$, the normalized vector $\hat{\mathbf{v}}_i$ is computed as:

$$\hat{\mathbf{v}}_i = \frac{\mathbf{v}_i}{\sqrt{\sum_{j=1}^d v_{i,j}^2 + \epsilon}} \quad (7.18)$$

Where $\epsilon = 10^{-10}$ prevents division by zero.

During inference, a user query \mathbf{q} is embedded and normalized into $\hat{\mathbf{q}}_i$. The semantic relevance score S against any stored chunk c_i is calculated via the dot product:

$$S(\mathbf{q}, c_i) = \langle \hat{\mathbf{q}}_i, \hat{\mathbf{v}}_i \rangle = \sum_{j=1}^d \hat{q}_j \hat{v}_{j,i} \quad (7.19)$$

Chunks are filtered based on a predefined threshold $\tau = 0.20$, and the top-k documents are retrieved to form the augmented context. Example of use case is presented in the figure 7.11.

The screenshot shows a chatbot interface with two queries and their answers. The first query is "What sensors are used in the project?". The chatbot returns a list of three documents with scores and a generated response. The response lists four types of sensors: Temperature sensors, Moisture content sensors, Pressure sensors, and Real-time sensors. The second query is "What main equations describe the technological process?". The chatbot returns a list of three documents with scores and a generated response. The response states that the technological process is the drum drying process and that no specific equations are mentioned in the provided documentation.

Figure 7.11 – Example of use-case

When a user submits a query (e.g., “What sensors are used in the project?”), the system encodes the query into a normalized embedding vector and compares it against precomputed embeddings of document chunks stored in the FAISS index. Based on the cosine similarity (implemented via inner product on normalized vectors), the system retrieves the most relevant text segments that exceed the predefined similarity threshold. These top-ranked chunks are then used to generate a contextualized response. As shown in the figure, the model successfully identifies relevant sections describing temperature, moisture, and pressure sensors, and synthesizes them into a coherent answer. A second query demonstrates the system’s ability to handle more abstract questions, where it retrieves partial matches and provides a reasoned response even when explicit equations are not present. This highlights the robustness of the retrieval-augmented approach in handling both precise and open-ended technical queries.

8. Econometric part

The economic calculations required for the implementation of the project are performed. Salaries of employees, taxes, payments, equipment costs and the time required to pay off the project will be calculated.

8.1 Economic Justification of the Automation System Implementation

The economic assessment of an automated control system for the industrial drum drying process in food production based on modern programmable logic controllers and industrial automation equipment is a very important aspect, due to the fact that the implementation of an automated system significantly reduces human labor, ensures the speed and continuity of the technological process, and minimizes operational and safety risks.

In addition to the main benefits of the project, there are also a number of opportunities provided by process automation, such as improved energy efficiency, stable control of temperature and moisture content, reduction of product losses, and enhanced product quality consistency. In this section, economic calculations will be performed to demonstrate the feasibility, cost-effectiveness, and overall benefits of implementing an automated control system for the drum drying process.

8.2 Estimating the capital cost of implementing the automated system

Calculating the capital cost of implementing an automated system is an important step in assessing the economic feasibility of a project. The following expression is used for this purpose:

$$K_{CC} = S + C \quad (8.1)$$

where:

K_{CC} - the total capital investment;

S - personnel salary expenses, including social contributions;

C - equipment acquisition costs including amortization, maintenance and repair;

This calculation enables the estimation of the total cost involved in implementing the automated system, forming a foundational component for conducting further analysis of the project's economic viability.

8.3 Calculation of labor costs for the implementation of the automation system

Labor costs for the development and implementation of an automation system include the wages of production personnel (operators, engineers), auxiliary

personnel (electricians, instrumentation and automation adjusters), and maintenance personnel. The total amount of wages for the implementation period is calculated using the following formula:

$$S_t = S + SO_t \quad (8.2)$$

where:

S_t - the total amount of payroll;

SO_t - number of social contributions in accordance with the legislation of the Republic of Kazakhstan;

Information on personnel salaries is presented in table 7.1. The number of key production personnel is determined based on service standards or compliance with the technological process, taking into account the minimum wage in the Republic of Kazakhstan.

Table 8.1– Salary costs of working personnel

Specialty	Number of people	Period of work, Months	Monthly salary	Total, tenge
PLC engineer	2	3	884 000	5 304 000
Automation Engineer	1	3	820 000	2 460 000
Process Control Engineer	1	3	840 000	2 520 000
E&I engineer	1	1	814 000	814 000
Technologist	2	3	620 000	3 720 000
Standardizer & Certificates	1	1	520 000	520 000
Chief engineer	1	3	1 134 000	3 402 000
Design engineer	1	1	624 000	624 000
Service personnel	5	3	384 000	5 760 000
Total:				25 124 000

When implementing an automation system, it is necessary to take into account mandatory social contributions in accordance with the Tax Code of the Republic of Kazakhstan. Social contributions are calculated based on monthly income, which should not exceed ten times the minimum wage. Currently, the minimum wage in the Republic of Kazakhstan is 85,000 tenge. According to the Tax Code of the Republic of Kazakhstan, the social tax is 11% of income that does not exceed fifteen times the annual calculation indicator. Thus, the total wage for the period of implementation of the automation system is calculated as the sum of the staff's wages and mandatory social contributions.

Social contributions will be calculated according to the following formula:

$$SC = \left(S - \left(\frac{T_p S}{100} \right) \right) \cdot T_s \quad (8.3)$$

where:

T_p – mandatory pension contributions (10% of salary);

T_s – social security contribution standard, tenge;

Then calculated the social contributions for the PLC engineer:

$$SC_1 = \left(5304000 - \frac{10 \cdot 5304000}{100} \right) \cdot 0,09 = 429\,624 \text{ tenge} \quad (8.4)$$

Automation engineer:

$$SC_2 = \left(2460000 - \frac{10 \cdot 2460000}{100} \right) \cdot 0,09 = 199\,260 \text{ tenge} \quad (8.5)$$

Process Control Engineer:

$$SC_3 = \left(2520000 - \frac{10 \cdot 2520000}{100} \right) \cdot 0,09 = 204\,120 \text{ tenge} \quad (8.6)$$

E&I engineer:

$$SC_4 = \left(814000 - \frac{10 \cdot 814000}{100} \right) \cdot 0,09 = 65\,934 \text{ tenge} \quad (8.7)$$

Technologist:

$$SC_5 = \left(3720000 - \frac{10 \cdot 3720000}{100} \right) \cdot 0,09 = 301\,320 \text{ tenge} \quad (8.8)$$

Standardizer & Certificates:

$$SC_6 = \left(520000 - \frac{10 \cdot 520000}{100} \right) \cdot 0,09 = 42\,120 \text{ tenge} \quad (8.9)$$

Chief engineer:

$$SC_7 = \left(3402000 - \frac{10 \cdot 3402000}{100} \right) \cdot 0,09 = 275\,562 \text{ tenge} \quad (8.10)$$

Design engineer:

$$SC_8 = (624000 - \frac{10 \cdot 624000}{100}) \cdot 0,09 = 50\,544 \text{ tenge} \quad (8.11)$$

Service personnel:

$$SC_9 = (5760000 - \frac{10 \cdot 5760000}{100}) \cdot 0,09 = 466\,560 \text{ tenge} \quad (8.12)$$

Total amount of all social contributions:

$$SC_t = 429\,624 + 199\,260 + 204\,120 + 65\,934 + 301\,320 + 42\,120 + \\ + 275\,562 + 50\,544 + 466\,560 = 2\,035\,044 \text{ tenge} \quad (8.13)$$

Calculation of the total amount of wages:

$$S_t = 25\,124\,000 + 2\,035\,044 = 27\,159\,044 \text{ tenge} \quad (8.14)$$

8.4 Calculation of labor costs for the sustaining of the automation system

Employment costs after the development and implementation of the automation system consist of salaries for production staff (operators, engineers), auxiliary personnel (electrical engineers, instrumentation adjusters), and maintenance personnel. The workforce required for sustaining operations is optimized compared to the developmental phase, as automation reduces the need for manual interventions.

The primary goal of sustaining labor costs is to maintain system reliability and efficiency while minimizing expenses. The automation system requires a limited number of highly skilled engineers for troubleshooting, monitoring, and occasional updates. Routine maintenance tasks can be performed by support personnel or interns, significantly reducing long-term operational costs.

In this section, we will evaluate the required workforce, employment type, and annual salaries to determine the financial impact of sustaining the automation system. Additionally, the allocation of personnel has been carefully considered to balance cost-effectiveness with system performance, ensuring that salaries remain within an acceptable budget while maintaining a high level of process automation reliability. The following Table 7.2 – Salary Costs of Working Personnel Sustaining Automation System outlines the estimated labor costs required to support the system effectively, detailing each role, the number of employees, their employment type, and total annual salary expenses. This evaluation provides insights into the long-

term sustainability and financial feasibility of the automation system, allowing for potential optimizations in workforce allocation if necessary. Furthermore, the use of a centralized PLC–SCADA architecture enables remote monitoring and diagnostics, which reduces the frequency of on-site interventions and associated labor costs.

Table 8.2– Salary costs of working personnel sustaining automation system

Specialty	Number of people	Monthly salary	Employment type	Annual salary
PLC engineer	1	814 000	Full-time	9 768 000
Intern PLC engineer	1	150 000	Full-time	1 800 000
Automation Engineer	1	750 000	Full-time	9 000 000
Intern Automation Engineer	2	150 000	Full-time	3 600 000
Process Control Engineer	1	443 000	Part-time 1/2	5 316 000
E&I engineer	1	744 000	Full-time	8 928 000
Technologist	1	562 000	Full-time	6 744 000
Chief engineer	1	713 000	Part-time 1/2	8 556 000
Service personnel	3	350 000	Full-time	12 600 000
Total				66 312 000

Total amount of all social contribution:

$$SC_t = \left(66312000 - \frac{10 \cdot 66312000}{100}\right) \cdot 0,09 = 5\,371\,272 \text{ tenge} \quad (8.15)$$

Calculating the total amount of salaries per year in already working automated system:

$$S_t = 66\,312\,000 + 5\,371\,272 = 71\,683\,272 \text{ tenge} \quad (8.16)$$

This is the annual salaries of employees with all taxes and social contribution considered.

8.5 Process automation system equipment and peripherals purchase costs

Capital investments in equipment, taking into account all possible costs, are calculated using the formula:

$$C_t = C_{pr} + C_m \quad (8.17)$$

where:

C_t – total cost of equipment acquisition;

C_{pr} – cost of acquisition of main equipment for the process automation system;

C_m – cost of acquisition of peripheral devices;

Here is the calculation of the cost of additional equipment taking into account 5% of the total cost of main equipment.

$$C_{add} = C_t \cdot 0.05 \quad (8.18)$$

The implementation of an automated control system requires high-quality hardware and software components to ensure efficient process monitoring, control, and data acquisition. The selection of equipment is based on reliability, compatibility with the automation infrastructure, and compliance with industry standards. In this section, we break down the costs associated with purchasing the necessary automation equipment.

The following Table 7.3 - Costs of Purchasing Controllers provides a detailed cost breakdown of the programmable logic controllers (PLCs) required for the system. These controllers serve as the core processing units for automation, enabling real-time data analysis and process adjustments to maintain system stability and efficiency.

Table 8.3 - Costs of purchasing controllers

Component	Model	Quantity	Unit Price (USD)	Total Cost (USD)
Modicon M340 PLC	BMX P34 2020	1	\$1039.47	\$1039.47
Modicon M241 PLC	TM241CE24R	2	\$440.73	\$881.46

The capital investment for equipment includes controllers, input/output modules, communication devices, and power supplies, which are essential for the automation of the industrial drum drying process in food production.

The following Table 7.4 - Costs of Purchasing Measuring Instruments, Actuators, and Safety Systems outlines the essential components required for these functions, along with their specifications, unit prices, and total costs. These investments contribute to the overall reliability and safety of the automation system.

Table 8.4 - Costs of purchasing measuring instruments, actuators and safety systems

Component	Model	Quantity	Unit Price (USD)	Total Cost (USD)
Pressure Transmitter	Honeywell ST700	1	\$305.67	\$305.67
Temperature Sensor	PT100	2	\$20.96	\$41.92
Valve Positioner	SRD998	1	\$580	\$580
Electric Motor (Drum Drive)	Three-phase AC geared induction motor	1	\$1850.00	\$1850.00
Variable Frequency Drive	Altivar 320	1	\$980.00	\$980.00
SCADA Software	EcoStruxure	1	\$7000.00	\$7000.00
Industrial Ethernet Switch	TM4ES4	1	\$220.00	\$220.00
Total Capital Cost				\$10,977.59

The following Table 7.5 - Costs of Purchasing Modules.

Table 8.5 - Costs of purchasing modules

Component	Model	Quantity	Unit Price (USD)	Total Cost (USD)
Analog I/O Module	TM3AI8/G	1	\$561.55	\$561.55
Digital I/O Module	TM3AQ4/G	1	\$718.06	\$718.06
Discrete Output Module	TM2DRA8RT	1	\$131.00	\$131.00
Ethernet Communication Module	TM4ES4	1	\$149.00	\$149.00
Expansion Module	TM3TM3/G	1	\$274.00	\$274.00
Power Supply Module	BMX CPS 3020	1	\$423.00	\$423.00
Total Capital Cost				\$2,256.61

Converting by nowadays course to tenge by 459 tenge per dollar, we will have:

$$C_{ex.} = \$10,977.59 = 5,433,906.05 \text{ tenge} \quad (8.19)$$

The cost of installation works is equal to 25% of the cost of capital expenditures (formula 7.6):

$$C_i = C_{ex.} \cdot 0.25 \quad (8.20)$$

$$C_i = 5,433,906.05 \cdot 0.25 = 1,358,476.51 \text{ tenge} \quad (8.21)$$

Total equipment costs including installation and unaccounted costs are equal:

$$C = 5,433,906.05 + 1,358,476.51 = 6,792,382.56 \text{ tenge} \quad (8.22)$$

8.6 Calculation of Schneider Electric equipment operating costs

The formula 7.23 is used to calculate the total operating costs for Schneider Electric equipment.

$$C_{oe} = C_r + C_m \quad (8.23)$$

where:

C_{oe} – are operating expences;

C_r – is the cost of equipment repair;

C_m – is the cost of maintaining the equipment in perfect working condition;

Equipment repair costs amount to 2.5% of the sum of social contributions and equipment costs. These data were calculated in sections 5.3 and 5.4 respectively.

$$C_r = (C + S_t) \cdot 0.025 \quad (8.24)$$

$$C_r = (6,792,382.56 + 71,683,272) \cdot 0.025 = 1,961,891.38 \text{ tenge} \quad (8.25)$$

The cost of maintenance is estimated using the same method as the cost of repair, but with a coefficient of 2.3%. The calculation formula is presented below:

$$C_m = (C + S_t) \cdot 0.023 \quad (8.26)$$

$$C_m = (6,792,382.56 + 71,683,272) \cdot 0.023 = 1,804,940.07 \text{ tenge} \quad (8.27)$$

$$C_{oe} = 1,961,891.38 + 1,804,940.07 = 3,766,831.45 \text{ tenge} \quad (8.28)$$

8.7 Calculating electricity utilization costs

Electricity utilization costs are calculated using the formula:

$$C_{el} = \sum Wt \cdot k \cdot d \cdot m \quad (8.29)$$

where:

C_{el} – cost of electricity consumption by the automation system per year;

$\sum W$ – total capacity of the equipment according to the passport data;

t – equipment operating time during the day;

k – efficiency;

d – number of control points;

m – number of working days per year;

$$C_{el} = 7 \cdot 25 \cdot 0.85 \cdot 1 \cdot 240 = 35\,700 \text{ kW} \cdot \text{h} \quad (8.30)$$

The cost of one kilowatt-hour of electricity is 22,11 tenge. The calculation of the cost of electricity utilization for one year is represented below:

$$C_{el} = 35\,700 \cdot 22.11 = 789\,327 \text{ tenge} \quad (8.31)$$

Thus, the calculated electricity cost represents annual operating expenses of the automation system and is considered separately from capital investments.

8.8 Cost-effectiveness of implementing an automation system in production

The cost-effectiveness of implementing an automated control system (ACS) depends on several factors, including reduced energy costs and a reduction in technical personnel involved in production maintenance.

Energy savings are achieved through the use of advanced technologies provided by Schneider Electric, which leads to modernization using energy-efficient equipment. These upgrades can lead to a reduction in energy costs of up to 35%.

$$E_{el} = 789\,327 \cdot 0.35 = 276\,264 \text{ tenge} \quad (8.32)$$

Savings on labor costs:

$$E_{S.} = S_1 - S_2 \quad (8.33)$$

where:

S_1 – represents labor costs before the implementation of the automated system;

S_2 – represents labor costs after the implementation of the automated system;

Here the calculation of wages before and after the implementation of the ACS is made taking into account social contributions according to the formula (7.2 and 7.3):

$$S_1 = 81\,075\,000 \text{ tenge} \quad (8.34)$$

$$S_2 = 71,683,272 \text{ tenge} \quad (8.35)$$

Here are the social contributions and wage costs calculated before and after the implementation of ACS. After the reduction, the plant will have only 13 employees instead of the previous 23.

$$E_S = 81,075,000 - 71,683,272 = 9,391,728 \text{ tenge} \quad (8.36)$$

The total savings achieved through reduced staffing and lower energy costs amount to:

$$E = 9,391,728 + 276\,264 = 9,667,992 \text{ tenge} \quad (8.37)$$

The annual financial effect obtained from the implementation of an automated process control system can be determined using the following expression:

Here the payback period of the implemented ACS is calculated using the following formula:

$$T_{pp} = \frac{K_{cc}}{E} \quad (8.38)$$

$$T_{pp} = \frac{33,951,426.56}{9,667,992} = 3.51 \text{ year} \quad (8.39)$$

Thus, the payback time of the implemented automated process control system is about 3.51 years.

8.9 Conclusion

The economic analysis confirms that the implementation of an automated process control system for the industrial drum drying process is economically feasible. The automation system provides annual savings of 9,667,992 tenge through reduced energy consumption and optimized labor costs. The total capital investment amounts to 33,951,426.56 tenge, resulting in a payback period of approximately 3.5 years.

9. Occupational health and safety

The food processing industry is a significant global employer and an important contributor to the national economy. As a key sector in ensuring food security and product quality, it plays an essential role in daily life and is closely connected to consumer needs. Industrial food production processes, including drum drying, involve the operation of thermal equipment, rotating machinery, and automated control systems. Due to the nature of these processes, workers may be exposed to various occupational health and safety hazards.

These risks include exposure to high temperatures, noise, moving mechanical parts, vibrations, electrical hazards, and automation-related risks. This section examines and analyzes the main hazardous factors that may negatively affect the health and safety of personnel. In addition, based on industrial safety requirements, measures will be proposed to ensure safe working conditions and to reduce the negative impact on workers' health and the production environment.

9.1. Analysis of identified harmful production factors

Noise. One of the most common harmful factors in food processing facilities, including drum drying units, is industrial noise. Noise is generated by electric motors, gear drives, fans, blowers, conveyors, and auxiliary equipment operating continuously during the drying process. The expansion and intensification of industrial food production has increased the use of high-capacity rotating machinery, which can operate for long periods and contribute to elevated noise levels in production areas.

Changes in noise levels may be particularly noticeable in enclosed production halls, where sound reflection from walls and equipment intensifies its impact on personnel. Prolonged exposure to excessive noise can cause fatigue, reduced concentration, and long-term hearing damage. To reduce noise exposure, the following measures can be applied:

- Restrict operating time of high-noise equipment and schedule maintenance activities outside peak production hours.
- Limit personnel presence in high-noise zones and optimize internal logistics within the production facility.
- Install sound-insulating casings and barriers around noisy equipment such as motors, fans, and gear drives.
- Install mufflers on engines to minimize engine noise. These can be similar to what's used on motor vehicles, or hospital-grade.
- Use low-noise electric motors and modern drive systems designed for food-processing applications.
- Seek noise abatement options for a range of equipment, such as replacing blades on fans to reduce the frequency of the sound emitted.

Industrial noise has a negative impact on the body of employees, in this regard,

the legislation of the Republic of Kazakhstan specifies standards for the permissible noise level in production. The normalization of noise levels in production facilities is carried out in accordance with GOST 11.0.008-82 (Occupational safety standards system. Methods of noise measurement at workplaces.) [8].

Vibration. Electric motors, drum drive systems, and rotating components of the drying unit generate vibration during operation. Excessive vibration can lead to mechanical wear, fatigue of structural elements, loosening of fasteners, and reduced equipment lifespan. In addition, long-term exposure to vibration may negatively affect the health of operating personnel.

Mitigating vibration is a high priority in food processing facilities, as excessive vibration can lead to equipment damage, reduced service life, and adverse effects on personnel health.

In accordance with GOST 12.4.012-83 (Occupational Safety Standards System. Vibration. Tools for measuring and controlling vibration in the workplace. Technical requirements), measuring and control devices designed to measure harmonic and random vibration parameters should be installed in production facilities. Moreover, measuring instruments must comply with the general requirements of GOST 25865-83 [9].

Electromagnetic radiation. In automated drum drying systems, electromagnetic fields are generated by electrical equipment such as PLCs, frequency converters, power supplies, sensors, and communication devices. The main biological factor of exposure is the intensity of the electromagnetic field. At workplaces, the maximum permissible level of electromagnetic radiation should not exceed 8 kV/m.

The main methods of protection against electromagnetic fields include:

- shielding of electrical equipment and control cabinets;
- proper grounding of automation and power systems;
- placement of electrical devices at a safe distance from permanent workplaces;
- limitation of exposure time during maintenance activities;
- use of certified industrial equipment that complies with electromagnetic compatibility standards;

Due to the automation of the drum drying process and the rational placement of sensors, control cabinets, and electrical equipment, electromagnetic radiation levels remain within permissible limits. Maintenance personnel are exposed to electromagnetic fields only for short periods during inspection and servicing operations.

9.2 Analysis of identified hazardous production factors

Electrical safety. Electric current is a hidden danger, as it has no taste, color, or odor, which makes it difficult to detect on production equipment. A current exceeding 30 mA is considered deadly to humans. To eliminate the risk of electric

shock, only those employees who have been trained, instructed and know the basic rules of electrical safety are allowed to work.

The electrical safety system includes a set of organizational and technical measures aimed at protecting against the dangerous effects of electric current. In industrial food processing facilities, including drum drying units, it is necessary to regularly monitor the technical condition of electrical equipment, switchboards and power supply lines.

Depending on the operating conditions, production facilities are divided (in accordance with the Rules for Electrical installations from the Ministry of Energy of the Republic of Kazakhstan [10]) into:

- high-risk premises;
- rooms with two or more dangerous factors;
- premises without increased danger.

To prevent electric shock, all live elements must be insulated or protected from accidental contact. Equipment housings must be grounded, and warning signs, signs, and signs must be installed on the production site.

Grounding is performed by a yellow-green insulated copper wire with a cross-section of at least 4 mm², laid openly in accessible places. The grounding bus is connected to a common ground loop, the resistance of which should not exceed 4 ohms. The equipment is powered via an automatic circuit breaker, which is triggered by a short circuit or a significant leakage current.

The equipment installed as part of the automation of the control system does not pose an immediate threat to maintenance personnel. In this regard, electrical safety measures do not remain static, but continue to be improved and developed.

Environmental protection. During the operation of technological equipment, pollutants are released into the atmosphere. Environmental impact should be regulated in accordance with the rules for issuing environmental permits and submitting an environmental impact declaration approved by the Ministry of Ecology of the Republic of Kazakhstan on August 9, 2021 [11].

The main sources of harmful emissions include:

- leakage of lubricants and technical oils from mechanical equipment
- emissions through air ducts and deflectors of equipment located in separate units;
- release of heated air and fine product particles from drying units;
- cleaning and maintenance operations of technological equipment;
- internal transportation of raw materials and finished products

Short-term emissions that occur during equipment operation are considered technologically unavoidable and are provided for by production regulations.

Fire safety. A fire can lead to serious consequences, including damage or complete loss of equipment, machinery, and documents of great material value. In addition, it poses a serious threat to the life and health of employees. Fire safety is ensured through the functioning of the fire protection system and fire extinguishing equipment and must comply with the fire safety rules approved by the Minister of

Emergency Situations of the Republic of Kazakhstan dated April 21, 2022 [12].

An evacuation plan in case of fire should be posted in all departments of the enterprise, containing instructions on personnel actions and instructions on the location of fire-fighting equipment.

A fire in a room can occur for the following reasons:

- the use of open electrical equipment;
- short circuit in the power supply system or in electronic devices;
- damaged or worn wiring insulation;
- ignoring fire safety standards;
- the presence of combustible production materials;
- the presence of oxygen.

The degree of fire risk of production facilities depends on the characteristics of the technological processes that occur in them. The main task is to eliminate conditions conducive to ignition and flame spread.

Fire safety covers four key areas:

1. fire prevention and fire spread;
2. localization of the fire source;
3. protection of personnel and property;
4. prompt and effective fire extinguishing.

To ensure safety, it is important to eliminate possible sources of ignition and combustible materials in a timely manner, as well as maintain a safe environment.

Fire prevention measures are divided into organizational, technical, operational and planned.

Organizational measures include:

- proper operation of the equipment;
- maintenance of the technical condition of the premises;
- conducting briefings and training of employees in fire safety requirements;
- placement of information materials and evacuation schemes.

Technical measures provide for compliance with fire safety standards when designing buildings, including the correct installation of electrical wiring, installation of equipment, heating, ventilation and lighting systems.

In addition, it is necessary to ensure free access to the building for emergency services, the possibility of emergency power outages, the presence of fire shields, fire extinguishers and boxes of sand in the aisles, as well as providing the building with fire hydrants and hoses.

Explosion safety. Food processing facilities do not belong to high-explosion-risk objects; however, explosive situations may occur due to the accumulation of combustible dust and vapors in enclosed spaces. In accordance with the state standard GOST 12.1.010-76 (occupational safety standards system. Explosion safety), production processes should be designed so that the probability of an explosion is minimized [13].

All devices placed in areas with a potential explosion risk must be designed

to provide explosion and fire protection. Regular cleaning, ventilation, and dust removal systems are used to prevent the formation of explosive environments.

During the operation and maintenance of equipment installed in potentially fire-hazardous areas, the supply and exhaust ventilation system must function. As part of the automated drum drying system, monitoring sensors are installed to ensure safe process parameters and timely detection of abnormal operating conditions.

9.3 Proposals for security measures

Firstly, it is necessary to ensure fire safety in the control room. The best method of fighting a fire is the use of fire extinguishers. One of the most effective fire extinguishers is the OP-5 ABCE powder fire extinguisher (Figure 8.1). This fire extinguisher is effective in extinguishing fires of classes ABC and E.

Figure 9.1 – Fire extinguisher OP-5 ABCE

To calculate the required number of fire extinguishers for the operator's room, it is necessary to determine the area of this room. The control room is 15m long and 7m wide, respectively, the area is:

$$A = 15 * 7 = 105m^2 \quad (9.1)$$

In accordance with the standards for providing facilities with primary fire extinguishing equipment dated December 13, 2019, fire extinguishers can be installed at category D facilities, a moderately flammable room with working installations at the rate of one fire extinguisher per 40m² type OP5 [12].

Thus, to calculate the required number of fire extinguishers, it is calculated using the following formula:

$$N = \frac{105}{40} = 2.625 \approx 3 \text{ pcs} \quad (9.2)$$

The required number of fire extinguishers for the control room is 3 pcs.

Another effective measure to ensure the safety of employees is the use of special suits. Workwear for food industry workers is an integral part of the industrial safety system. It protects workers from the effects of aggressive environments, high temperatures, mechanical damage and other factors.

Special protective clothing used in food production facilities must meet a number of strict standards and provide maximum protection in hazardous work conditions. The main requirements include:

- Fire resistance: Food industry workers often work near high-temperature equipment and heated surfaces. Clothing should be made of materials that do not support combustion and do not melt when in contact with fire.

- Antistatic: An important requirement for handling flammable substances. Antistatic materials help prevent the accumulation of static electricity, which can cause sparks and fires.

- Resistance to technological substances: Workwear should protect personnel from contact with lubricants, cleaning agents, and other technological substances used during equipment maintenance.

- Heat resistance: Clothing must maintain its protective properties at both high and low temperatures. It is important that it provides comfort in conditions of extreme cold or heat.

- Protection against mechanical damage: Clothing must be durable and protect against cuts, punctures and other mechanical impacts that may occur during operation and maintenance of industrial equipment.

Materials for protective clothing used in food processing facilities

The choice of materials for the manufacture of workwear is a key factor determining its protective properties. The most common materials include:

- Aramid fabrics: Used to make fire-resistant clothing. These materials are able to withstand high temperatures and do not melt when exposed to an open fire.

- Fire-resistant impregnations: Special impregnations increase the resistance of fabrics to fire and enhance the protective characteristics of clothing.

- Membrane materials: Protect against moisture and chemicals, but at the same time provide air exchange and comfortable ventilation.

- Antistatic materials: Special synthetic fibers with antistatic properties help prevent the accumulation of electric charge.

9.4 Organization of safe work

The organization of safe working conditions is a fundamental requirement for ensuring the reliable and hazard-free operation of the drum drying system. Effective safety management is achieved through a combination of organizational, technical, and administrative measures aimed at minimizing occupational risks and maintaining stable process conditions. Only qualified and authorized personnel who have undergone appropriate training, instruction, and certification are permitted to operate and maintain the equipment. Personnel must possess a clear understanding of the technological process, the operating principles of the drum dryer, and the potential hazards associated with its operation. Workplaces must be ergonomically organized to ensure safe and efficient performance of tasks. All operational zones should be clearly marked, and access to hazardous areas must be restricted. Special attention must be given to areas near rotating components, steam pipelines, and heated surfaces. These zones must be equipped with safety barriers, warning signs, and visual indicators to prevent accidental contact.

Regular inspection and preventive maintenance of equipment play a crucial role in maintaining safety. Scheduled maintenance must include checking the integrity of mechanical components, the condition of thermal insulation, and the reliability of electrical connections. Any detected defects or deviations from normal operation must be promptly addressed to prevent accidents and equipment failure. The implementation of automated monitoring systems, such as PLC and SCADA, ensures continuous supervision of key technological parameters, including temperature, pressure, and drum rotation speed. These systems allow early detection of abnormal conditions and enable timely corrective actions, thereby reducing the likelihood of emergency situations. Emergency preparedness is an essential component of safe work organization. Clear instructions must be developed for personnel actions in case of emergencies, including equipment malfunction, fire, or power failure. Emergency stop systems must be installed in easily accessible locations to allow rapid shutdown of the process.

9.5 Personal Protective Equipment (PPE)

The operation of the drum drying system in food production is associated with exposure to multiple hazardous factors, including elevated temperatures, rotating mechanical components, steam, airborne particles, and increased noise levels. These hazards arise directly from the technological characteristics of the drum drying process, which involves heat and mass transfer under controlled industrial conditions. Therefore, the use of personal protective equipment (PPE) is a mandatory requirement to ensure personnel safety and to minimize occupational risks.

One of the primary hazards in the drum drying process is exposure to high temperatures. According to the technological parameters of the system, the drum

surface temperature typically ranges from 105 to 150°C, while the steam used for heating may reach temperatures of up to 160°C. Direct contact with heated surfaces, steam pipelines, or processed material may result in severe thermal burns. To mitigate these risks, personnel must use heat-resistant gloves and specialized protective clothing designed to withstand high thermal loads.

In addition to thermal hazards, the drying process involves the formation of fine particles and dust, particularly during product removal and handling stages. These airborne particles may pose a risk to the respiratory system if inhaled over prolonged periods. Therefore, respiratory protective equipment, such as filtering masks or industrial respirators, must be used in areas where dust concentration exceeds permissible limits.

Figure 9.2 – Respiratory protective equipment (3M 6200 respirator)

Mechanical hazards are associated with the operation of rotating drums, drive systems, and auxiliary equipment. As described in the technological structure of the drum dryer, rotating components and mechanical elements operate continuously during the drying process. Accidental contact with these parts may result in injuries such as entanglement or crushing. To reduce these risks, personnel must wear protective clothing with high mechanical resistance and safety footwear with anti-slip soles and reinforced structure.

Eye protection is also essential due to the possible release of dust particles and condensate droplets during operation. Safety goggles or face shields must be used to prevent eye injuries and ensure safe working conditions.

In addition to the use of protective clothing and safety footwear, it is essential to implement engineering and organizational measures to minimize mechanical risks. All rotating and moving parts of the drum drying system must be equipped with protective guards and safety covers to prevent accidental contact. Access to hazardous zones should be restricted, and clearly visible warning signs must be installed near moving equipment. Maintenance and cleaning operations must only be carried out when the equipment is fully stopped and disconnected from the power supply, in accordance with lockout/tagout procedures.

Furthermore, personnel must maintain a safe working distance from rotating components during operation and avoid wearing loose clothing or accessories that may become entangled in moving parts. Proper workplace organization, including sufficient lighting and unobstructed access paths, also plays an important role in reducing the likelihood of mechanical injuries.

Figure 9.3 – Safety goggles (3M™ Safety Goggles 2890, Sealed, Clear Lens)

Furthermore, industrial equipment such as motors, fans, and ventilation systems generates significant noise levels during continuous operation. Prolonged exposure to noise may negatively affect hearing and overall worker performance. Therefore, hearing protection devices such as earplugs or earmuffs must be used in designated high-noise areas.

Figure 9.4 – Hearing protection (earplugs or earmuffs)

An important feature of the developed system is the integration of automation technologies, including PLC and SCADA systems, which enable real-time monitoring and control of technological parameters such as temperature, pressure, and drum speed. While automation significantly reduces direct human interaction with hazardous equipment, maintenance and inspection tasks still require the use of appropriate PPE.

Protective clothing used in the drum drying process must meet strict industrial requirements, including heat resistance, mechanical durability, and antistatic properties. Common materials used include heat-resistant fabrics, aramid fibers, membrane materials, and antistatic synthetic fibers. Proper selection and use of PPE, combined with automated control systems, ensures a high level of industrial safety and operational reliability.

Figure 9.5 – Portwest FR93 Bizflame Pro FR Coverall

In addition to the selection of appropriate protective clothing, special attention must be given to the protection of workers' hands, as they are directly exposed to both thermal and mechanical hazards during operation and maintenance of the drum drying system. Personnel must use heat-resistant gloves when working near heated drum surfaces, steam pipelines, and hot materials, as well as mechanically durable gloves when interacting with moving parts or handling equipment. These gloves must provide adequate insulation, grip, and resistance to wear.

Figure 9.6 - Safety gloves (Ansell HyFlex 11-840)

Furthermore, safety footwear represents an essential element of personal protection in industrial environments. Workers must wear footwear equipped with anti-slip soles, reinforced toe caps, and resistance to mechanical impact. This is particularly important in areas where surfaces may become slippery due to condensation or product residues. Proper footwear reduces the risk of slips, falls, and foot injuries, thereby enhancing overall workplace safety.

Figure 9.7 - CAT (Caterpillar) Threshold Waterproof Steel Toe Work Boot

In the context of food production, additional hygiene requirements must be strictly observed. Personnel must wear clean protective clothing, including hair covers (caps) and, where required, disposable gloves suitable for food contact. These measures are essential to prevent contamination of the final product and to ensure compliance with international food safety standards such as HACCP and ISO 22000 [5]. The effectiveness of PPE depends not only on its correct selection but also on proper usage, maintenance, and storage. All protective equipment must be regularly inspected for damage, contamination, or degradation of protective properties. Respirator filters must be replaced according to manufacturer recommendations, and protective clothing must be cleaned or replaced in accordance with hygiene requirements. PPE must be stored in designated clean and dry areas, protected from moisture, chemicals, and mechanical damage. Improper storage conditions may significantly reduce the protective characteristics of materials and compromise worker safety. Training of personnel is another critical aspect of PPE implementation. Employees must undergo regular safety briefings and safe instruction on the correct use, adjustment, and removal of protective equipment. Particular attention must be paid to the proper fitting of respirators and the correct selection of gloves and clothing for specific tasks. Inadequate training or improper use of PPE may significantly reduce its effectiveness.

In conclusion, the comprehensive application of personal protective equipment, including gloves, protective clothing, respiratory protection, eye protection, hearing

protection, and safety footwear, combined with proper maintenance, training, and integration with automated control systems, ensures a high level of occupational safety. This approach minimizes risks, protects personnel health, and contributes to the stable and efficient operation of the drum drying system.

9.6 Conclusion

In conclusion, the analysis of hazardous and harmful factors associated with the drum drying system shows that the main risks can be effectively minimized through a combination of technical, organizational, and protective measures. The implementation of safety standards, proper equipment maintenance, and the use of appropriate personal protective equipment ensure safe working conditions for personnel. Overall, the integration of automation systems together with comprehensive safety measures provides reliable, efficient, and secure operation of the technological process.

CONCLUSION

This graduation project was devoted to the development of an automated control system for the industrial drum drying process in food production. The main goal of the work was to improve the stability, efficiency, and reliability of the drying process by maintaining the required product moisture content, reducing energy consumption, and ensuring consistent product quality. During the project, the technological process of drum drying was studied in detail, including heat and mass transfer, steam supply, drum rotation, product feeding, moisture removal, and the influence of external disturbances on the final product.

A mathematical model of the drum dryer was developed and analyzed using MATLAB simulation tools. The model described the relationship between the main process variables, such as air temperature, product temperature, steam input, gas flow rate, and moisture content. Stability, controllability, observability, step response, impulse response, Nyquist, and frequency response analyses were carried out. The results showed that the drying process has slow moisture dynamics and multivariable interactions, which require accurate and robust control. For this reason, the system was represented as a MIMO model, which provided a more realistic basis for controller design.

Several control strategies were investigated, including decentralized PID, LQI, and robust H_∞ control. The comparison of simulation results showed that the PID controller can stabilize the process, but it has slower settling time and higher overshoot in the moisture control loop. The LQI controller improved the dynamic response and reduced the steady-state error. However, the robust H_∞ controller demonstrated the best overall performance by providing zero overshoot, shorter settling time, and strong resistance to disturbances and system uncertainties. Therefore, H_∞ control was selected as the most effective solution for the automated drum drying system.

The project also included the selection of technical equipment and the practical implementation of the automation system. The proposed architecture is based on Modicon M340 and Modicon M241 PLCs, Modbus TCP/IP communication, SCADA visualization, temperature, pressure and moisture sensors, control valves, valve positioners, and a three-phase AC induction motor. The developed PLC program and HMI screens provide automatic and manual operation modes, alarm handling, process monitoring, and coordinated control of the main technological units.

In addition, AI-based tools were introduced to support Industry 4.0 principles. The computer vision module was proposed for quality control of raw materials, while the RAG-based NLP assistant was developed to simplify access to technical documentation. The economic analysis showed that the implementation of the system is feasible, with annual savings of 9,667,992 tenge and an estimated payback period of approximately 3.5 years. Occupational health and safety measures were also considered to reduce risks related to high temperature, moving parts, noise, vibration, and electrical equipment.

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APPENDIX A

This appendix presents supporting MATLAB code and simulation results used for the modeling and analysis of the drum drying process.

```
% MIMO Rotary Dryer – Full System Analysis (4 Channels)
% Graphics: Bode (Break Freq), Nyquist (Stability), Impulse (MIMO)
%% =====
clear; clc; close all;

%% — 1. ПАРАМЕТРЫ И МОДЕЛЬ ОБЪЕКТА —————
h_A = 13152; C_a = 30400; C_m = 1160; kappa_eff = 1.0e-4;
beta_eff = 5.0e-4; K_steam = 200; m_p = 50; r_eff = 5.6895e6;
L_v = 2.5e6; T_AI = 470; u2_SS = 13.33; c_A = 1005;
T_A_SS = 90; dM_evap_du2 = 0.01;

A = [ -(h_A + L_v*kappa_eff)/C_a, (h_A + L_v*kappa_eff)/C_a, 0;
      (h_A - r_eff*kappa_eff)/C_m, -(h_A - r_eff*kappa_eff)/C_m, -r_eff*beta_eff*m_p/C_m;
      -kappa_eff/m_p, kappa_eff/m_p, -beta_eff ];

B = [ K_steam/C_a, (c_A*(T_AI - T_A_SS))/C_a ;
      0, 0 ;
      0, (1/-m_p)*dM_evap_du2 ];

C_mat = [1 0 0; 0 0 1];
D_mat = zeros(2,2);

InNames = {'Steam Flow', 'Gas Flow'};
OutNames = {'Air Temperature', 'Moisture Content'};

plant = ss(A, B, C_mat, D_mat, 'InputName', InNames, 'OutputName', OutNames);
sys_cl = feedback(plant, eye(2)); % Замкнутая система с единичной ОС

%% — 2. ПОЛНЫЙ АНАЛИЗ БОДЕ (4 КАНАЛА: ОСНОВНЫЕ И СВЯЗИ) —————
% Выводит 4 окна с детальным анализом частоты среза по уровню -3дБ
for r = 1:2 % Перебор выходов
    for c = 1:2 % Перебор входов
        fig_title = sprintf('Bode: %s to %s', InNames{c}, OutNames{r});
        figure('Name', fig_title, 'Color', 'w', 'Position', [100+c*70, 100+r*70, 800, 600]);

        [mag, phase, w] = bode(sys_cl(r,c));
        mag_db = 20*log10(squeeze(mag));
        phase_deg = squeeze(phase);

        % --- Magnitude Plot ---
        subplot(2,1,1);
        semilogx(w, mag_db, 'b', 'LineWidth', 2.5); hold on; grid on;

        % Расчет частоты среза (-3 дБ от начального уровня)
        target_mag = mag_db(1) - 3;
```

```

[~, idx_bw] = min(abs(mag_db - target_mag));
break_freq = w(idx_bw);

% Визуализация частоты среза
plot(break_freq, mag_db(idx_bw), 'ro', 'MarkerSize', 10, 'MarkerFaceColor', 'r');
line([min(w) break_freq], [mag_db(idx_bw) mag_db(idx_bw)], 'Color', 'r', 'LineStyle', '--');
line([break_freq break_freq], [min(mag_db) mag_db(idx_bw)], 'Color', 'r', 'LineStyle', '--');

title(sprintf('Bode: %s \rightarrow %s', InNames{c}, OutNames{r}), 'FontSize', 12);
ylabel('Magnitude (dB)');
legend('Magnitude', sprintf('Break Freq = %.2e rad/s', break_freq), 'Location', 'best');
set(gca, 'XMinorGrid', 'on', 'YMinorGrid', 'on');

% --- Phase Plot ---
subplot(2,1,2);
semilogx(w, phase_deg, 'b', 'LineWidth', 2.5); hold on; grid on;

% Метка на фазовой кривой
plot(break_freq, phase_deg(idx_bw), 'ro', 'MarkerSize', 10, 'MarkerFaceColor', 'r');
line([min(w) break_freq], [phase_deg(idx_bw) phase_deg(idx_bw)], 'Color', 'r', 'LineStyle', '--');
line([break_freq break_freq], [min(phase_deg) phase_deg(idx_bw)], 'Color', 'r', 'LineStyle', '--');

ylabel('Phase (deg)'); xlabel('Frequency (rad/s)');
set(gca, 'XMinorGrid', 'on', 'YMinorGrid', 'on');
end
end

%% — 3. АНАЛИЗ УСТОЙЧИВОСТИ NYQUIST (4 КАНАЛА) —————
for r = 1:2
    for c = 1:2
        figure('Name', sprintf('Nyquist: %s -> %s', InNames{c}, OutNames{r}), 'Color', 'w');
        h = nyquistplot(sys_cl(r,c));
        setoptions(h, 'ShowFullContour', 'off', 'Grid', 'on'); hold on;

        % Линия запаса устойчивости
        line([-1 0], [0 0], 'Color', 'b', 'LineWidth', 4);
        plot(-1, 0, 'r*', 'MarkerSize', 12, 'LineWidth', 2);
        text(-0.8, 0.1, 'Stability Margin', 'Color', 'b', 'FontWeight', 'bold');
        title(sprintf('Nyquist: %s \rightarrow %s', InNames{c}, OutNames{r}));
        axis([-1.7 1.7 -1.2 1.2]);
    end
end
end

```

```

%% — 4. ИМПУЛЬСНЫЕ ХАРАКТЕРИСТИКИ (

figure('Name', 'MIMO Impulse Response', 'Color', 'w', 'Position', [150, 150, 1000, 700]);
t = linspace(0, 4000, 2500);
[y_imp, t_imp] = impulse(sys_cl, t);
imp_color = [0.8500 0.3250 0.0980]; % Оранжево-коричневый

for r = 1:2
    for c = 1:2
        subplot(2,2, (r-1)*2+c);
        plot(t_imp, y_imp(:,r,c), 'Color', imp_color, 'LineWidth', 2.5);
        grid on; hold on;

        [peak, idx] = max(abs(y_imp(:,r,c)));
        val_peak = y_imp(idx,r,c);

        % Метки пиковых значений
        text(t_imp(idx)*1.2, val_peak, sprintf('Peak: %.4f', val_peak), ...
            'Color', 'b', 'FontSize', 9, 'FontWeight', 'bold');

        title(sprintf('%s \rightarrow %s', InNames{c}, OutNames{r}));
        xlabel('Time [s]'); ylabel('Amplitude');
    end
end

end
sgtitle('MIMO Impulse Response Matrix', 'FontWeight', 'bold', 'FontSize', 14);
% B консоли MATLAB
plant_mpc = ss(A, B, C_mat, D_mat);
% Укажем шаг дискретизации (MPC работает в дискретном времени)
Ts = 0.1;
plant_mpc_d = c2d(plant_mpc, Ts);
% Создание контроллера
nm_mpc = mpc(plant_mpc_d, Ts);
% Золотая середина: быстрее чем было, но без колебаний
nm_mpc.Weights.OutputVariables = [2 2]; % Умеренная точность
nm_mpc.Weights.ManipulatedVariablesRate = [0.05 0.05]; % Чуть больше плавности (было 0.1, стало 0.05)
nm_mpc.PredictionHorizon = 40;
% Calculate poles of the open-loop plant
p_open = pole(plant);
% Calculate poles of the closed-loop system (from your sys_cl)
p_closed = pole(sys_cl);
fprintf('Open-loop Poles:\n');
disp(p_open);
fprintf('Closed-loop Poles (Unity Feedback):\n');
disp(p_closed);

```

```

% MIMO Rotary Dryer – Controller Design

% Регуляторы: Децентрализованный ПИД, LQI, H-infinity
% Входы: u1 = пар (steam), u2 = расход газа (gas flow)
% Выходы: y1 = T_A (темп. воздуха), y2 = X (влажность)

%% =====
clear; clc; close all;

%% — 1. ПАРАМЕТРЫ МОДЕЛИ (из диплома) —————
h_A = 13152; % Полная теплопроводность [W/K]
C_a = 30400; % Тепловая ёмкость воздуха [J/K]
C_m = 1160; % Тепловая ёмкость продукта [J/K]
k_eff = 1.0e-4; % Коэффициент скорости сушки [s^-1]
beta_eff = 5.0e-4; % Коэффициент распада влаги [s^-1]
K_steam = 200; % Коэффициент парового нагрева [W/K]
m_p = 50; % Масса продукта [kg]
r_IC = 3.892e6;
r_CE = 7.487e6;
r_eff = (r_IC + r_CE) / 2;
L_v = 2.5e6;
T_AI = 470; u2_SS = 13.33; c_A = 1005;
T_A_SS = 90; dM_evap_du2 = 0.01;

%% — 2. МАТРИЦЫ ПРОСТРАНСТВА СОСТОЯНИЙ —————
A = [ (-h_A + L_v*k_eff - c_A*u2_SS)/C_a, (h_A + L_v*k_eff)/C_a, (-L_v*beta_eff*m_p)/C_a ;
      (h_A - r_eff*k_eff)/C_m, (-h_A - r_eff*k_eff)/C_m, (-r_eff*beta_eff*m_p)/C_m ;
      -k_eff/m_p, k_eff/m_p, -beta_eff ];

B = [ K_steam/C_a, (c_A*(T_AI - T_A_SS))/C_a ;
      0, 0 ;
      0, (1/-m_p)*dM_evap_du2 ];

C = [1 0 0; 0 0 1];
D = zeros(2,2);

n = size(A,1); p = size(C,1); m = size(B,2);
sys_ss = ss(A, B, C, D);
G_dc = dcgain(sys_ss);
fprintf('DC Gain Matrix:\n'); disp(G_dc);

%% — 3. SISO КАНАЛЫ ДЛЯ ПИД —————
G11 = sys_ss(1,1); % T_A ← steam
G22 = sys_ss(2,2); % X ← gas flow

```

```

%% — 4. ДЕЦЕНТРАЛИЗОВАННЫЙ ПИД —————
fprintf('\n=== ПИД РЕГУЛЯТОРЫ ===\n');
opts1 = pidtuneOptions('CrossoverFrequency', 0.005, 'PhaseMargin', 60);
opts2 = pidtuneOptions('CrossoverFrequency', 0.002, 'PhaseMargin', 60);

PID1 = pidtune(G11, 'PID', opts1);
PID2 = pidtune(G22, 'PID', opts2);

fprintf('PID1 (пар → T_A): Kp=%.4f Ki=%.6f Kd=%.4f\n', PID1.Kp, PID1.Ki, PID1.Kd);
fprintf('PID2 (газ → X): Kp=%.4f Ki=%.6f Kd=%.4f\n', PID2.Kp, PID2.Ki, PID2.Kd);

CL11 = feedback(G11*PID1, 1);
CL22 = feedback(G22*PID2, 1);

%% — 5. LQI (LQR + ИНТЕГРАТОР) —————
fprintf('\n=== LQI РЕГУЛЯТОР ===\n');
A_aug = [A, zeros(n, p); -C, zeros(p, p)];
B_aug = [B; zeros(p, m)];

max_error_T = 1.0; max_error_X = 0.005;
max_u_steam = 20; max_u_gas = 5.0;

Q_lqi = diag([0, 0, 0, 1/max_error_T^2, 1/max_error_X^2]);
R_multiplier = 2000;
R_lqi = diag([1/max_u_steam^2, 1/max_u_gas^2]) * R_multiplier;

K_lqi = lqr(A_aug, B_aug, Q_lqi, R_lqi);
A_cl_lqi = A_aug - B_aug*K_lqi;
sys_lqi = ss(A_cl_lqi, [zeros(n,p); eye(p)], [C, zeros(p,p)], zeros(p,p));

%% — 6. H-INFINITY РЕГУЛЯТОР —————
fprintf('\n=== H-INFINITY РЕГУЛЯТОР ===\n');
s = tf('s');
Ws = (1/0.001) * (s/0.003 + 1)/(s + 0.003*0.001) * eye(2);
Wu = 0.01 * eye(2);
Wt = (s/0.1 + 0.2)/(s/10 + 1) * eye(2);

[K_hinf, CL_hinf, gamma] = mixsyn(sys_ss, Ws, Wu, Wt);
fprintf('H-inf γ: %.4f\n', gamma);
%% — 7. СБОР ДАННЫХ ДЛЯ ВИЗУАЛИЗАЦИИ —————
t_sim = 0:1:5000;
sys_hinf_cl = feedback(sys_ss * K_hinf, eye(2));

[y_pid1, ~] = step(CL11, t_sim);
[y_pid2, ~] = step(CL22, t_sim);

```

```

[y_lqi_all, ~] = step(sys_lqi, t_sim);
[y_hinf_all, ~] = step(sys_hinf_cl, t_sim);

% Расчет SSE и структур stepinfo
dc_lqi = dcgain(sys_lqi);
dc_hinf = dcgain(sys_hinf_cl);
sse_lqi = abs(1 - diag(dc_lqi));
sse_hinf = abs(1 - diag(dc_hinf));

s_p1 = stepinfo(y_pid1, t_sim, 1);
s_p2 = stepinfo(y_pid2, t_sim, 1);
s_l1 = stepinfo(y_lqi_all(:,1,1), t_sim, 1);
s_l2 = stepinfo(y_lqi_all(:,2,2), t_sim, 1);
s_h1 = stepinfo(y_hinf_all(:,1,1), t_sim, 1);
s_h2 = stepinfo(y_hinf_all(:,2,2), t_sim, 1);

%% — 8. ЦИКЛ ДЕТАЛЬНОЙ РАЗМЕТКИ —————
titles = {'PID: T_A', 'PID: X', 'LQI: T_A', 'LQI: X', 'H-inf: T_A', 'H-inf: X'};
data = {y_pid1, y_pid2, y_lqi_all(:,1,1), y_lqi_all(:,2,2), y_hinf_all(:,1,1), y_hinf_all(:,2,2)};
infos = {s_p1, s_p2, s_l1, s_l2, s_h1, s_h2};
colors = {'g', 'g', 'r', 'r', 'b', 'b'};
ylabels = {'Temp T_A [°C]', 'Moisture X [kg/kg]'};

for k = 1:6
    figure('Name', titles{k}, 'Color', [1 1 1]);
    hold on; grid on;
    y = data{k};
    s = infos{k};
    curr_col = colors{k};

    plot(t_sim, y, 'Color', curr_col, 'LineWidth', 2);
    yline(1, 'Color', [0.5 0.5 0.5], 'LineStyle', '--', 'LineWidth', 1.2);

    % Rise Time
    if ~isnan(s.RiseTime) && s.RiseTime > 0
        [~, idx_rt] = min(abs(t_sim - s.RiseTime));
        val_rt = y(idx_rt);
        line([s.RiseTime s.RiseTime], [0 val_rt], 'Color', 'r', 'LineStyle', '--');
        line([0 s.RiseTime], [val_rt val_rt], 'Color', 'r', 'LineStyle', '--');
        plot(s.RiseTime, val_rt, 'ks', 'MarkerFaceColor', 'r');
        text(s.RiseTime + 50, val_rt - 0.05, sprintf(' Tr = %.1f s', s.RiseTime), 'FontWeight', 'bold', 'BackgroundColor', 'w');
    end

    % Settling Time
    if ~isnan(s.SettlingTime) && s.SettlingTime > 0
        line([s.SettlingTime s.SettlingTime], [0 1], 'Color', 'r', 'LineStyle', '--');
        text(s.SettlingTime + 50, 0.5, sprintf(' Ts = %.1f s', s.SettlingTime), 'FontWeight', 'bold', 'BackgroundColor', 'w');
    end

    % Overshoot
    if s.Overshoot > 0.5
        [max_y, max_idx] = max(y);
        plot(t_sim(max_idx), max_y, 'ro', 'MarkerFaceColor', 'r');
        text(t_sim(max_idx), max_y + 0.04, sprintf(' Overshoot: %.1f%%', s.Overshoot), 'Color', 'r', 'FontWeight', 'bold', 'BackgroundColor', 'w');
    end

    title(['Analysis: ', titles{k}]);
    xlabel('Time [s]'); ylabel(ylabels{mod(k-1,2)+1});
    xlim([0 5000]); ylim([0 1.3]);
end

%% — 9. ВЫВОД КОЭФФИЦИЕНТОВ —————
fprintf('\n--- Матрица коэффициентов LQI (K_lqi) ---\n');
disp(K_lqi);
fprintf('Управление u1 (Паp): Kp1=%.4f, Kp2=%.4f, Kp3=%.4f | Ki1=%.4f, Ki2=%.4f\n', ...
    K_lqi(1,1), K_lqi(1,2), K_lqi(1,3), K_lqi(1,4), K_lqi(1,5));
fprintf('Управление u2 (Гаэ): Kp1=%.4f, Kp2=%.4f, Kp3=%.4f | Ki1=%.4f, Ki2=%.4f\n', ...
    K_lqi(2,1), K_lqi(2,2), K_lqi(2,3), K_lqi(2,4), K_lqi(2,5));

```

APPENDIX B

P&ID scheme:

APPENDIX D

Electrical scheme:

APPENDIX E

System variables for M340 controller

№	Name	Type	Point Type	Address	Comment
1	alarm	BOOL			
2	alarm_cmd	EBOOL			
3	atv_conf	BOOL			
4	auto	BOOL			
5	auto_cmd	EBOOL			
6	auto_mode	BOOL			
7	blade_motor	BOOL			
8	blower	BOOL			
9	combustion	REAL			
10	drum_motor	BOOL			
11	drumheat1	REAL			
12	DrumTemp Raw	REAL			
13	fan	BOOL			
14	fin_product	REAL			
15	fuel level	REAL			
16	gastank01	REAL			
17	gastank02	REAL			
18	gastank03	REAL			
19	Kp	REAL			
20	man_cmd	EBOOL			
21	man_mode	EBOOL			
22	moisture sp	REAL			
23	motor_inlet	BOOL			
24	outlet_motor	BOOL			
25	phase1	BOOL			
26	phase2	BOOL			
27	phase3	BOOL			
28	phase4	BOOL			
29	prefnpr	REAL			
30	pressure_ind	INT		%IW0.1.2	
31	pressure_ind_disp	REAL			
32	ProcessValue	REAL			
33	product amount	REAL			
34	product_min	REAL			
35	product_moisture	REAL			
36	product moisture anim	REAL			
37	start_cmd	EBOOL			
38	stop_cmd	EBOOL			

39	stopped	EBOOL			
40	temp ind	BOOL			
41	Ti	TIME			
42	tic	INT			
43	tic disp	REAL			
44	tube1	BOOL			
45	tube2	BOOL			
46	tube3	BOOL			
47	tube4	BOOL			
48	vlv01	BOOL	%IW0.1.3		
49	vlv02	BOOL	%IW0.1.4		
50	vlv03	BOOL	%IW0.1.5		
51	vlv04	BOOL	%IW0.1.6		
52	vlv05	BOOL	%IW0.1.7		
53	vlv06	BOOL	%IW0.1.8		

APPENDIX F

AI implementation code

```
1. Procedure FindDataLeakage(TrainDir, TestDir, Threshold):
2. // Step 1: Indexing test set
3. TestHashes = EmptyDictionary()
4. For each image in TestDir:
5.     h = Calculate_pHash(image)
6.     TestHashes.add(h)
7.
8. // Step 2: Search for intersection in set
9. Leaks = EmptyList()
10. For each image_path in TrainDir:
11.     h_train = Calculate_pHash(image_path)
12.
13.     // Comparison by perceptive hash
14.     For each h_test in TestHashes:
15.         Distance = HammingDistance(h_train, h_test)
16.         If Distance <= Threshold:
17.             Leaks.append(image_path)
18.             Break // file is marked as leakage
19.
20. Return Leaks
21.
1. Procedure CleanDataset(RawDataset, LeakList):
2. // Step 1: Deletion
3. For each file_path in LeakList:
4.     If FileExists(file_path):
5.         DeleteFile(file_path)
6.
7. // Step 2: Metadata update (for Torch)
8. NewDataset = ReScanDirectory(RawDataset.root)
9.
10. // Step 3: Balance check
11. Counts = CountLabels(NewDataset)
12. Display(Counts)
13.
14. Return NewDataset
15.
```